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Off-pump Versus On-pump Coronary Artery Bypass Surgery: Early Experience In Queen Alia Heart Institute

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Abstract

Objectives: The aim of this retrospective single-center study was to examine the different risk factors in coronary artery surgery and to compare the short term outcomes of coronary artery bypass using the heart lung machine or without using it.

Patients and Methods: The study included 722 patients who underwent coronary artery bypass grafting from January 2004 to December 2005 in Queen Alia Heart Institute. Forty two patients had off-pump technique, while the remaining (680), had the on-pump technique. Preoperative risk factors were studied; perioperative and postoperative courses were analyzed.

Results: The 2 groups were homogeneous with regard to age distribution (56.5 vs. 58.5 years), male sex (64% vs. 62%). The preoperative risk factors were comparable. Atrial fibrillation was significantly higher in the on-pump patients ($p=0.005$), similarly 44% of the on-pump patients needed blood transfusion, while only 19% of the off-pump needed that. In hospital mortality rate was (off-pump 2.4% vs. on-pump 3.1%), perioperative myocardial infarction (off-pump 4.8% vs. on-pump 6.6%) and stroke (off-pump 2.4% vs. on-pump 4.7%). Length of stay in the cardiac intensive care unit was shorter in off-pump group (18 vs. 32 hours), and the total hospital stay period was also shorter for the off-pump patients (4.5 vs. 6.5 days). Acute renal failure occurred equally in both groups (7.1% each). Off-pump patients had less average blood loss (410 vs. 650 ml).

Conclusion: Off-pump coronary artery bypass grafting seems to reduce the total length of hospital stay, operative morbidity, and the need for inotropic support and blood transfusion.

Keywords: Coronary Artery Bypass, Off-pump Coronary Artery Bypass, Cardiopulmonary Bypass, Outcomes, Cardioplegia

INTRODUCTION

Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting (CABG) performed with Cardiopulmonary Bypass (CPB) has become a well established treatment modality for patients with coronary artery disease; it is a routine procedure with a mortality rate of 2-3% in elective cases. It provides a motionless, bloodless surgical field that allows optimal conditions for the construction of coronary anastomoses [1-4].

Despite advances in perfusion technology, cardiopulmonary bypass is still believed by many to be a major cause of post operative morbidity, and that had a major impact in the revival of interest in performing CABG on the beating heart [5]

OPCAB, which avoids tissue ischemia and systemic inflammatory responses, is gaining popularity as a feasible alternative to conventional CABG with CPB and displaying a trend toward lower rates of morbidity and mortality [6]

As a result of increased surgical experience and the development of enabling technology, such as stabilization and exposure devices, OPCAB surgery has become increasingly accessible and technically feasible. However, the major concern remains raised whether OPCAB is superior to that performed with the heart lung machine and the heart being chemically arrested [7]. Our mission in the future will be to apply the coronary revascularization approaches available to different subsets of patients in a way that maximizes long-term benefit and minimizes short-term risk.

In this review of our institutional data, preoperative risk factors and postoperative outcomes were analyzed for consecutive patients who underwent isolated, primary CABG either by OPCAB or on CPB.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

The medical records of 722 patients who underwent CABG surgery during the period from January 2004 to December 2005 in Queen Alia Heart Institute (QAHI) were reviewed. Forty two (6%) patients were operated on with the OPCAB technique, while 680(94%) with CABG and CPB. The optimal surgical strategy for each patient was determined on an individual basis by the attending surgeon.

All patients who are >60 years old, were routinely screened by carotid Doppler assessment. The patients who required carotid endarterectomy were excluded from the study.

The present study examined several factors that have been said to complicate coronary artery revascularization. Such proposed risk factors were: age, sex, hypertension, Diabetes Mellitus (DM), Canadian Cardiovascular Society(CCS) classifications of functional limitation related to angina, New York Heart Association (NYHA) classification of functional limitation related to heart disease, previous sternotomy, angiographic data related to the number of the diseased coronary arteries and status of the left ventricular function. Intraoperative records of inotropic support, type of grafts used and the coronary targets revascularized were also analyzed. Early outcomes that were addressed are: early extubation from the ventilatory support, issues related to the magnitude of blood loss and the requirements for blood transfusion, Atrial Fibrillation(AF), Acute Renal Failure(ARF), characterized by creatinine rise >2mg/dl postoperatively, Cardiac Intensive Care Unit(CICU) and hospital stay periods, stroke, Myocardial Infarction(MI) and in-hospital mortality.

Surgical technique: All patients were operated through a standard median sternotomy incision. The conduits that were used are: Left Internal Mammary Artery (LIMA), Right Internal Mammary Artery (RIMA), radial artery and great saphenous vein. The internal mammary harvest was performed under direct vision. Saphenous vein harvest was performed by an open technique and the radial artery harvest from the non-dominant forearm after performing an Allens test.

ON-PUMP GROUP: Cardiopulmonary bypass was established by standard distal ascending aortic cannulation and single double stage venous cannulation of the right atrium. Heparin was given at a dose of 3mg/kg to achieve an Activated Clotting Time (ACT) of 480 seconds. Normothermic perfusion with antegrade intermittent cold crystalloid cardioplegia was used in all patients, and retrograde blood cardioplegia in 2/3 of them. After the completion of the last proximal anastomosis, protamine sulfate was given to reverse the effects of heparin in a 1:1 ratio.

OFF-PUMP GROUP: Heparin was given before distal division of the internal mammary artery in a dose of 1 mg/kg with supplemental doses to maintain heparinization and reversed with protamine sulfate in a 1:1 ratio after the completion of the last proximal anastomosis. To stabilize the coronary targets on a beating heart, a special device called Octopus 2 (Medtronic Inc, Minneapolis, MN) was used, and pericardial traction sutures were used to position the heart in an appropriate way. Little displacement of the heart was needed to expose the Left Anterior Descending (LAD); diagonal and proximal right coronary arteries. However, exposure of the circumflex branches and the Posterior Descending Artery demanded a combination of maneuvers such as tilting and rotating of the operating table, opening of the right pleura and sometimes giving beta blockers to induce a controlled bradycardia, which were, in away, facilitating distal anastomosis on the beating heart.

All patients in both groups were transferred to the Cardiac Intensive Care Unit (CICU); with early extubation was the aim whenever appropriate. Both groups received low molecular weight heparin which was administered on the second day of the surgery in a dose of 1 mg/kg in two divided doses till the patient is fully mobilized.

RESULTS

Over a 2 year period, 722 patients underwent coronary artery revascularization at QAHI. Two techniques were used: CABG with CPB (680) cases, while the remaining (42), had OPCAB technique. All preoperative data and risk factors are detailed in Table- 1.

The 2 patient populations, CABG with CPB and OPCAB were comparable with regard to mean age, male sex, preoperative MI(within 6 months of surgery), CCS class, NYHA class, hypertension, DM, smoking, previous sternotomy, PVD, and history of CVA.

Table I: Preoperative Patient Characteristics and Risk Factors

Parameters	CPB n=680	OPCA B n=42	P Value
Age(Years)			
Mean	56.6	58.5	
Range	39-78	42-79	
Male Sex (%)	433(64)	59(62)	
Previous MI < 6 months (%)	72(11)	6(14)	0.62
CCS class III or IV (%)	140 (21)	14 (33)	0.08
NYHA class III or IV (%)	112(16)	9 (21)	0.53
Hypertension (%)	528(78)	32 (76)	0.97
DM (%)	210 (31)	13 (30)	0.99
Smoking (%)	410(60)	26 (62)	0.96
Previous sternotomy (%)	59 (8.7)	3 (7.1)	1.0
PVD (%)	75 (11)	9 (21)	0.07
History of CVA (%)	42 (6.2)	3 (7.1)	0.74
MI=Myocardial Infarction, CCS= Canadian Cardiovascular Society classifications of functional limitation related to angina, NYHA= New York Heart Association, DM=Diabetes Mellitus, PVD= Peripheral Vascular Disease, CVA = Cerebrovascular Accident			

Patients with fewer diseased coronary arteries, specifically single or double vessels, prevailed significantly in the OPCAB group (SVD 48%, p= 0.0004; DVD 36%, p= 0.007). Triple vessel disease prevailed in the CPB group (p= 0.0001). Left main disease was (10%) in the CABG with CPB group and (9.5%) in the OPCAB group (p=1.0) (Table -2).

Complete revascularization dominated in CABG with CPB patients (68% CABG with CPB vs. 43% OPCAB; p= 0.002), and less need for inotropic support was needed in the OPCAB group (9.5% OPCAB vs. 28% CABG with CPB; p=0.01). The types of vascular conduits used for coronary bypass were comparable between the 2 groups (Table-2).

Table II: Angiographic Data

	CPB n=680	OPCAB n=42	P Value
LVEF, %			
Good >50%	311(46)	18(43)	0.92
Moderate 30%-50%	285(42)	15 (36)	0.52
Poor <30%	84 (12.4)	9(21)	0.17
SVD (%)	152(22)	20(48)	0.0004
DVD (%)	121(18)	15(36)	0.0074
TVD (%)	336(49)	3(7.1)	0.0001
Left main stem disease (%)	71(10)	4(9.5)	1.0
LVEF=Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction, SVD=Single Vessel Disease, DVD=Double Vessel Disease, TVD=Triple Vessel Disease.			

Table III: Intraoperative Data

	CPB n=680	OPCAB n=42	P Value
Vascular conduits used			
LIMA (%)	587(86)	33(79)	0.24
RIMA (%)	18(3)	2(5)	0.33
Radial artery (%)	166(24)	11(26)	0.94
SVG graft (%)	651(96)	38(91)	0.12
Inotropic support (%)	188(28)	4(10)	0.01
Complete revascularization (%)	462(68)	18(43)	0.0015
LIMA=Left Internal Mammary Artery, RIMA=Right Internal Mammary Artery, SVG= Saphenous Vein Graft.			

Table-3 summarizes the early outcomes of all patients. The outcome with the highest incidence rate, with statistical significance was AF, which occurred mostly in CABG with CPB patients (32% vs. 12%; p=0.005). The need for blood transfusion was significantly higher in CABG with CPB (44% vs. 19%; p= 0.003). In-hospital mortality and MI were more frequent in CABG with CPB patients, although not significantly so (3.1% CABG with CPB vs. 2.4% OPCAB; p=1.0) and (6.6% CABG with CPB vs. 4.8 % OPCAB; p= 1.0) respectively

In regard to stroke, early extubation from respiratory assistance, and reopening for bleeding, all of them were more frequent in CABG with CPB patients, although not significantly so. Acute renal failure occurred equally in both groups (Table-3).

The mean intensive care unit and hospital stay periods were higher in CABG with CPB than in OPCAB patients (32 vs. 18 hours), (6.5 vs. 4.5 days) respectively. The average blood loss was remarkably higher also in CABG with CPB (650 vs. 410 ml).

Table IV: early postoperative outcomes

	CPB n=680	OPCAB n=42	P Value
Extubation in less than 6 hours (%)	470(69)	31(74)	0.64
Patients needed transfusion (%)	296(44)	8(19)	0.003
Reopening for bleeding (%)	71(10)	8(19)	0.79
Atrial fibrillation (%)	217(32)	5(12)	0.005
In-hospital mortality (%)	21(3.1)	1(2.4)	1.0
Stroke (%)	32(4.7)	1(2.4)	0.71
MI (%)	45(6.6)	2(5)	1.0
ARF (%)	48(7.1)	3(7.1)	0.76
Average blood loss (ml)	650(390-1700)	410(180-720)	
In-hospital stay period (days)	6.5(5-38)	4.5(3-11)	
CICU stay period (hours)	18(12-32)	32(16-56)	
MI=Myocardial Infarction, ARF=Acute Renal Failure, CICU=Cardiac Intensive Care Unit			

DISCUSSION

Conventional CABG with CPB had been considered as the standard surgical procedure for myocardial revascularization, as it allows surgeons to perform coronary bypass with greater control and precision [8]. CPB is associated with a number of adverse consequences that are primarily related to the systemic inflammatory responses elicited by the activation of cellular and humoral mediators when circulating blood elements come into contact with the non-physiological surfaces of the heart lung machine [9]. The biochemical, cellular and molecular aspects of these inflammatory responses are believed to contribute to post operative myocardial, renal, and neurological, coagulopathic, and multiple organ dysfunctions [10, 11].

Proponents of OPCAB had examined the impact of this technology on perioperative myocardial function and clinical outcome [12], early mortality and MI are clearly of most value. Electrocardiography and perioperative troponin I release are non-invasive tests and are useful in the diagnosis of acute myocardial infarction. In this study there were 2 cases of acute MI as per pre-defined electrocardiographic or troponin I release in the OPCAB group compared to 45 cases in the CABG with CPB group, although MI was more frequent in the CABG with CPB (6.6%) compared to OPCAB group (4.8%), but it did not show any statistical significance ($p=1.0$). The OPCAB group required less inotropic pharmacological support in the perioperative period in comparison with CABG with CPB (9.5% vs. 28%, $p=0.01$).

One patient died during the in-hospital period in the OPCAB group while 21 in the CABG with CPB group. Among the 21 deaths in the CABG with CPB group, 5 patients died suddenly after an acute MI, 10 died of low cardiac output syndrome, 3 died of acute renal failure and the last 3 died of new neurologic events. Among the OPCAB group the only mortality which was encountered, was due to an acute MI. These data suggest that despite the new technical advances in terms of myocardial protection in CABG with CPB, there is still an important transient myocardial injury during cardioplegic arrest. Although this did not affect significantly the rates of mortality (3.1% vs. 2.4% $p=1.0$), or the incidence of MI (6.6% vs. 4.8% $p=1.0$), it may have an impact for the increase in postoperative morbidity.

The use of cardiopulmonary bypass is considered to be a major determinant of perioperative stroke during on-pump surgery [13]. Since most strokes are believed to result from atheroemboli, avoidance of aortic cannulation, aortic clamping and cardiopulmonary bypass should

reduce the risk of perioperative stroke [1]. However, partial aortic clamping remains a potential cause for embolic stroke during OPCAB [15]. Post OPCAB stroke rates ranging from 0.8-6% have been reported [16]. This study showed that one (2.4%) patient had ischemic stroke in the OPCAB group compared to 32 (4.7%) in the CABG with CPB group, which did not show any statistical significance ($p=0.7$). Preoperative risk factors of stroke: History of Cerebrovascular Accident (CVA), Peripheral Vascular Disease (PVD), DM, smoking, and hypertension were comparable between the two groups. However, stroke prevention remains one of the most important unresolved issues in coronary surgery today.

Atrial fibrillation is one of the most common arrhythmias occurring after CABG surgery [17]. AF is frequently not tolerated by the patients, inducing various symptoms such as temporary hemodynamic instability, shortness of breath and has been shown to substantially lengthen the hospital stay [18]. This study showed significant reduction in the incidence of AF in OPCAB group compared to the CABG with CPB (12% vs. 32% $p=0.005$). There is no uniting mechanism explaining AF associated with CABG surgery, rather a complex interplay of a number of related factors [8]. Large prospective randomized controlled trials by Scione and colleagues [19] showed that CPB with cardioplegia is the main independent predictor of post operative AF in patients undergoing coronary artery revascularization, since ischemia with OPCAB is regional, whereas in CABG with CPB it is usually global, which may have a detrimental effect on the atrial myocardium, resulting in the generation of atrial arrhythmias.

The overall CICU and hospital stay periods in the OPCAB group were significantly shorter than in the CABG with CPB (18 vs. 32 hours), (4.5 vs. 6.5 days) respectively. These could be explained by the lesser incidence of AF, strokes and the earlier extubation in OPCAB vs. CABG with CPB. Three large meta-analyses have reported that the duration of in-hospital stay is substantially reduced in patients who undergo OPCAB (20-22). With the increasing numbers of coronary artery operations being performed, efficient use of hospital resources becomes even more important and OPCAB surgery has been clearly shown to have cost benefits, due mainly to a decreased length of stay in the CICU and an overall decrease in in-hospital stay [23].

This study showed a significant decrease in post operative blood loss measured as average total chest tube drainage in OPCAB group compared to CABG with CPB (410 vs. 650 ml), and rate of take back to the theater to secure bleeding issues (7.1%

vs. 10%). As might be expected from the higher chest tube drainage, it was shown also a significantly greater transfusion requirement in the on-pump group. It is worth noting that less than one quarter (24%) of the patients in the off-pump group required transfusion compared with over half (51%) of the patients in the on-pump group ($p=0.001$). The less use of blood and blood products post operatively in patients, who underwent off-pump surgery, may be translated into a better outcome or substantial reduction in costs. However, not to be neglected considering the risk of disease transmission and inflammatory reactions that may adversely affect recovery, hospital stay, and progress.

Contrary to previous published trials [24, 25], we were unable to demonstrate any differences in the incidence of acute renal failure between the 2 groups (7.1% each, $p=0.76$), which may suggest little benefit attributable to beating heart surgery in regard to renal outcome.

CONCLUSION

Off-pump coronary artery by pass grafting seems to reduce the total length of hospital stay, operative morbidity, and the need for inotropic support and blood transfusion.

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ST Segment Elevation Myocardial Infarction, In-hospital and 30 Day Outcome in a Single Centre in Baghdad

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Abstract

Background: The aim is to delineate characteristics, risk factors, treatments and outcomes of patients presenting with ST Segment Elevation Myocardial Infarction (STEMI) who were admitted to Ibn Al-Bitar Hospital for Cardiac Surgery and to examine adherence to current guidelines.

Patients and Methods: All patients with acute myocardial infarction whom were admitted to Ibn Al-Bitar Hospital for Cardiac Surgery in Baghdad were included in this observational prospective study which was conducted from September 2007-June 2008. Data on treatment delay, therapeutic strategies, duration of hospitalization, and 30-days outcome were collected.

Results: There were 68 patients (55male & 13 female) with mean age of 55.65±10.60 ranging from 27- 80 years. Only 50% of patients presented within 6 hours of onset of chest pain and thrombolytic was given only to 44.1% of them. In-hospital mortality was 13.2% .Traditional risk factors as being male, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and smoking among others were present in our patients. There was a delay in the presentation of most of the patients and a small percentage of them received thrombolytic therapy and no one had mechanical revascularization. The guidelines were strictly adhered to regarding most of in hospital and discharge medications.

Conclusion: Many patients in this study did not receive thrombolytic therapy and the in-hospital mortality was high. Improving the outcome in AMI requires the collaboration of different institutions in the community and requires the development of our diagnostic, therapeutic and organizational tools.

Keywords: Myocardial infarction, Iraq, thrombolytic therapy Bypass.

INTRODUCTION

Over the last few years, there have been significant changes in the diagnosis and management of patients with acute myocardial infarction (AMI), with greater emphasis on immediate diagnosis and risk stratification in order to design an increasing number of therapeutic options to fit patients' risk profile. Despite several published randomized trials and guidelines, the extent to which recommended treatments are applied to practice remains uncertain. The organizational aspects affecting time delays in delivering reperfusion therapy, including transport by an ambulance service and early diagnosis and treatment in the emergency room, are largely unknown and may show great differences within different hospitals.

Current knowledge of characteristics, management and outcome of patients with AMI stems from randomized clinical trials (RCT) in highly selected and often low-risk populations. On the other hand, international surveys and registries have shown that the adherence to RCT derived guidelines is strongly affected by differences in multiple cultural, regional and epidemiological aspects [1-6] Aims of this observational

study were to determine time delays, management strategies and outcomes as well as extent of adherence to guidelines in unselected patients with ST elevation acute myocardial infarction (STEMI) admitted or referred to Ibn Al-Bitar hospital for cardiac surgery in Baghdad and followed for 30 days after discharge.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

Sixty eight patients with AMI were observed in Ibn Al-Bitar Hospital for Cardiac Surgery in Baghdad and during the period from September 2007- June 2008. 55 patients were (80.9%) males and 13 patients were (19.1%) females. The mean age was a 55.56 ± 10.60 year ranging from 27-80 years.

All patients were observed during hospital stay and for 30 days thereafter. No interference in the patients' diagnostic, therapeutic, and invasive intervention prescribed by cardiologists in charge of patient were made by the study group.

ST segment elevation myocardial infarction was defined by the presence of ST segment elevation ≥ 1 mm (≥ 2 mm in V1 to V3) in two or more contiguous leads. Patients with complete left bundle branch block (LBBB), paced rhythm or other abnormalities that made it impossible to analyze the ST segment were defined as having an AMI with undetermined electrocardiographic (ECG) location. Pre-hospital delay was defined as the time interval between symptom onset and the first arrival at hospital. Delay of reperfusion treatment was defined as the time interval between arrival at hospital and start of thrombolysis (door-to-needle time) or primary coronary angioplasty (door-to-balloon time).

All patients had demographic variables and full cardiovascular history taken including whether the patient has had prior episodes of myocardial ischemia, such as stable or unstable angina, myocardial infarction, coronary artery bypass surgery, or percutaneous coronary intervention. Evaluation of the patient's complaints focusing on onset of chest discomfort, associated symptoms, sex and age-related differences in presentation, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, possibility of aortic dissection, risk of bleeding, and clinical cerebrovascular disease. In addition the details on time between onset of chest pain and presentation to our hospital, method of transport, full cardiovascular evaluation, initial ECG findings, ordering a continuous ECG monitoring, result of blood tests including cardiac troponin, length of hospital stay and characteristics of the diagnostic and the therapeutic intervention used to treat their acute myocardial infarction during hospital stay were documented.

Data were collected by specialized physician and verified by a cardiologist. Information was obtained by chart review, by direct interview with patient and his or her family and by interviewing the treating cardiologist upon admission of patients to our hospital.

The cause of death during hospitalization and for 30 days documented and classified as cardiac and non cardiac. Cardiovascular deaths were sub

classified into: 1- recurrent myocardial infarction by definition had to occur >24 hours after the onset of the index myocardial infarction (if patient died within the same hospital admission or within 7 days of the recurrent infarction the cause of death fit to recurrent myocardial infarction); 2- cardiogenic shock; 3-arrhythmic cause; 4-sudden cardiac arrest; 5-Other cardiovascular cause, which included deaths resulting from cardiovascular procedures, stroke, aneurysms, pulmonary emboli, cardiac rupture, peripheral or renovascular disease.

Follow up: The 30 days follow up was conducted by hospital visits and by cellular phone. Five patients were lost to follow up. The details concerning cause of death, major cardiac events (readmission for post myocardial infarction angina, recurrent myocardial infarction, heart failure, revascularization procedure and other complication) and functional class from date of discharge and for 30 days were documented.

Statistical analysis: Categorical variables are presented as number of cases and percentages and compared by the chi-square test. Time intervals are presented as median times. Other continuous variables are presented as mean \pm standard deviation or as median.

RESULTS

More than a third of patients were younger than 50 years. Table -1- shows the age distribution of the patients.

(Table-1) Age Distribution of Men & Women

Age (yrs)	Men (no=55) %		Women (no=13)	
<50	20	29.4	4	5.9
50-59	19	27.9	2	2.9
60-69	9	13.2	6	8.8
70-79	6	8.8	1	1.5
>80	1	1.5	0	

(Table-2) Presenting Symptoms

Presenting symptom	(n=68)	%
Typical chest pain	35	51.5
Heart failure	24	35.3
Syncope	2	2.9
Arrhythmia	4	5.9
Conduction defect	3	4.4
Killip class :		
1	41	60.3
2	16	23.5
3	3	4.4
4	8	11.8

In Table 2 shows the presenting symptoms of studied population. Assessment of left ventricular

ejection fraction, regional wall motion abnormality, presence or absence of pericardial effusion was done in 60 (88.2%) patient. Quantitative and/or qualitative cardiac biomarkers were assessed in 57(83.8%) of patients. Angiography was done in 5 (7.4%) patients within (5-14) days from onset of chest pain.

Table -3 shows the baseline characteristics of the patients. Of these consecutive patients with AMI, 30(44.1%) had presented directly to or had their myocardial infarction in our hospital and 38(55.9%) had been transferred from another hospital. Most of the patients were either overweight or obese and diabetics constituted 41% of them. In half of patients the index myocardial infarction was preceded by chest pain episode of less than 30 days duration. Half of the patients presented within 6 hours of onset of chest pain. The majority of patients had there MI in the anterior location, a quarter of them had inferior MI and one patient had true right ventricular infarction. Two patients had new left bundle branch block (LBBB).

Risk factor: The male gender, age group above 50, a body mass index above 25 kg/m², active smoking, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and history of ischemic heart disease before myocardial infarction are significant risk present in large percentage of patients in our study(table-3).

Pharmacological therapy: The in hospital medication was analyzed as shown in table-4. Thrombolytic therapy in the form of tenecteplase was given in 30 patients (44%). Thirty eight patients did not receive thrombolytic therapy, half of them because of delay in presentation to the hospital, 26.3%(no.10) because the drug was not available in previous hospital, 18.5%(no.7) were excluded by the treating physician for no obvious reason, and in 5.2%(no.2) because of contraindication due to 4 months history of ocular surgery in one patient and a one year history of hemorrhagic stroke in another. Patients' medications are reported in Table 4.

Diagnostic coronary angiography was done in 5 patients and no patient was subjected to revascularization either through percutaneous intervention or surgery. Intraortic balloon pump was needed in 6 patients, mechanical ventilation in 5 and temporary pacemaker in 4. No patient was assessed by pre-discharge stress test.

In hospital course: Complications occurred during hospital stay are shown in table-6. Table -5 shows the discharge medications and indicates that most patients received beta-blockers, aspirin and statins

Table -3 Baseline patients characteristics

Baseline characteristics	No=68	%
Gender: Male	55	80.9
Female	13	19.1
Body mass index		
18.5-24.9	6	8.8
25-29.9	33	48.5
30-34.9	16	23.5
>35	11	16.2
Family history of IHD	6	8.8
History of IHD	24	35.3
Previous infarction	4	5.9
Prodromal angina	34	50
>48hours rest angina	28	41.2
<48hours rest angina	6	8.8
Prior stroke	1	1.5
Prior PCI	2	2.9
Prior CABG	2	2.9
Hypertension	27	39.7
Diabetes mellitus		
Insulin dependent	2	2.9
Non-insulin dependent	26	38.2
Smoking: Active	31	45.6
Pastive	9	13.2
Hours between onset of pain & presentation		
0-3	18	26.5
4-6	16	23.5
7-24	9	13.2
>24	25	36.8
Location of infarction		
Anterior	27	39.7
Anterior & Inferior	8	11.8
Anterior & Lateral	11	16.2
Antero-lateral & posterior	1	1.5
Inferior	17	25
Lateral	1	1.5
RV infarction	1	1.5
LBBB	2	2.9

IHD: ischemic heart disease. PCI: percutaneous coronary intervention. CABG: coronary artery bypass grafting. LBBB: left bundle branch block.

Table-4 In-hospital medical therapy

Medical therapy	No =68	%
Tenecteplase	30	44.1
Aspirin 100mg	67	98.5
Clopedogril75mg	62	91.2
Heparin	65	95.6
LMWH	2	2.9
Glycoprotein 2b/3a blockers (tirofiban)	6	8.8
iv- metoprolol	3	4.4
Po-Beta blockers	56	82.4
ACE I	<24hrs=21 >24hrs=24	33.8 35.3
Oral nitrates	45	66.2
iv-Nitroglycerin	21	30.9
iv-Inotropics	12	17.6
Digoxin	5	7.4
Diuretics	24	35.3
Insulin	29	42.6
Oral hypoglycemic drugs	6	8.8
Lidocaine	2	2.9

Amiodaron	4	5.9
Statins	65	95.6
LMWH: Low molecular weight heparin, ACE I: Angiotensin converting Enzyme inhibitors, ARBs: Angiotensin 2 Receptor Blockers		

Table-5 medical therapy at discharge for survivals

Medication	No=59	%
Beta-blockers	49	83
ACE I	30	51
Aspirin	54	91.5
Clopidogrel	44	74.5
Oral nitrates	40	67.7
Diuretics	15	25.4
Digoxin	3	5
Warfarin	3	5
Amiodaron	3	5
Insulin	15	25.4
OHA	8	14
Statins	56	95
ACE I: Angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitor, OHA: Oral Hypoglycemic Agents		

Table-6 in-hospital complications

In-hospital complication	No=68	%
In-hospital mortality	9	13.2
Heart failure	24	35.3
Cardiogenic shock	8	11.8
Mechanical		
Free wall rupture	0	0
Ventricular septal defect	3	4.4
Mitral regurgitation	12	17.6
Arrhythmia		
Asystole	4	5.9
VT/VF	7	10.3
Atrial fibrillation	1	1.5
2 nd and 3 rd degree heart block	5	7.4
Stroke	1	1.5
Major bleeding	1	1.5
Minor bleeding	2	2.9
TTP	1	1.5
Pericarditis	2	2.9
Dressler syndrome	0	0
TTP: thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura, VT: Ventricular tachycardia, VF: Ventricular tachycardia		

bleeding and two had minor bleeding in the form of gingival bleeding and ecchymosis. Gangrene of the left lower limb developed in one patient as a complication of intraaortic balloon pump. Thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura (TTP) developed in one patient as a side effect of Clopidogrel. The overall mean hospital stay (days) was 6.03±4.25 ranging from 1-30 days with one patient had had extended hospital course for 30 days.

Tabl-7- Characteristics of in-hospital mortality

Baseline characteristic	No=9	%
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Gender : Male	5	55.6
Female	4	44.4
Age		
<60years	5	55.6
>60years	4	44.4
Body mass index kg/m2		
18.5-24.9	0	0
25-29.9	4	44.4
30-34.9	2	22.3
>35	3	33.3
Risk factors		
HTN	4	44.4
DM	4	44.4
Smoking	3	33.3
Myocardial location		
Anterior	5	55.6
Inferior	1	11.1
Anterolateral	1	11.1
Anteroinferior	1	11.1
LBBB	1	11.1
Cause of death		
Cardiogenic shock	3	33.3
Sudden cardiac arrest	4	44.4
Arrhythmia	2	22.3
Killip class		
1-2	1	11.1
3-4	8	88.9
Lv EF (%)		
>46%	1	11.1
30-44%	8	88.9
Thrombolytic		
YES	2	22.3
NO	7	77.7
VSD	3	33.3

30- Days follow- up

Five patients (7.4%) who discharged alive were lost to follow up. Thirty days follow up was completed to remaining 54 patients (79.4%) who were discharged alive. During this period one patient died because of TTP in a hospital for which he was referred for plasmapheresis. Another patient (1.5%) died because of recurrent myocardial infarction (table-8). One patient was readmitted for post MI angina and one for heart failure. Coronary angiography was done in 4.4% of patients. During 30 days follow up no patient subjected to percutaneous or surgical coronary revascularization.

DISCUSSION

The aim of this study was to provide a reliable picture of patients with AMI admitted to our hospital in order to identify areas of possible improvement and to design strategies for optimal care delivery. It is applied on patients consecutively admitted or referred to our hospital with ST elevation myocardial infarction, designed to study the whole clinical course, from symptoms onset to 1-month follow-up after discharge. It reflects the pattern of care applied in the management of AMI in our hospital. Most of the patients presented late and a few of them received thrombolytic therapy and the in-hospital mortality was high.

Table-8- Events from discharge to 30-days follow up

Events	No of pt	%
Death	2	2.9
Re-infarction	1	1.5
Re-admission for Post-MI angina	1	1.5
Hear failure	1	1.5
Coronary angiography	3	4.4
PCI	0	
CABG	0	

PCI: percutaneous coronary intervention, CABG: coronary artery bypass grafting

Risk factors: The traditional risk factors of IHD were present in our patient cohort such as being male (80.9%), high body mass index (88.2%), diabetes (41.1%), hypertension (39.7%) and 58.8% were either active or ex-smoker.

Pre-hospital delay: Reducing pre-hospital delay is one of the major tools for improving reperfusion therapy and hence morbidity and mortality in STEMI patients. In the present study, the mean delay between symptom onset and hospital admission in hours was about 36.42±47 in 44.1% of patients who admitted directly to our hospital and 8.16 ± 17.44 in 55.9% of patients who admitted to previous hospital and then referred to our hospital. This delay is longer than any delay observed world wide. In GRACE [4] study it was 139 min, in the PRAIS-UK registry [7] on unstable angina and NSTEMI (180 min), and in REACT [8], and in most thrombolysis trials [9, 10].

Timely administration of reperfusion therapy by primary angioplasty or thrombolysis is the recommended treatment for most patients with myocardial infarction and ST segment elevation [7, 8]. In the present study, pre-hospital thrombolysis has never been administered. Thrombolysis was the only reperfusion treatment in this study in our hospital and previous hospitals and administered to 44.1% of patients. Delay of presentation to the hospital was the main reason (50%) for not receiving thrombolytic treatment and unavailability was the second reason. Only one patient who developed myocardial infarction during hospital admission for unstable angina received thrombolysis within 30 min and no patient underwent primary PCI. Time delays usually considered as the gold standard of reperfusion treatments [13].

We believe that the reason for this delay is multi-factorial:

1. Being a tertiary center and lacking an emergency department is one of the reasons. Our hospital is not considered a general

hospital and usually takes care of patient referred from other hospitals and clinics.

2. Patient education and awareness of symptoms and the availability of corrective therapy in a timely fashion is important.
3. Poor infrastructures of the transporting system are another reason.
4. Finally the study was started at period were the security was bad, an important reason which halted some patients from presenting early especially those patients who had their symptoms started at afternoon and those who lived in hot zones.

Revascularization procedures: This survey shows that the use of cardiac catheterization and coronary revascularization in patients with acute myocardial infarction in our hospital is not aligned to the European average¹⁰, as coronary angiography was done for 7.4% of patients and no percutaneous or surgical coronary revascularization done for any patient during hospitalization and 30-day follow up. That is because there is no program for primary PCI in our hospital and also the study was conducted at times where resources were depleting.

In-hospital and discharge medical therapy: The present study confirms the very high rate in aspirin use during hospital stay and at discharge, consistent with the rates reported by other observational studies. In comparison with the most recent studies [4, 11] the rate of use of unfractionated heparin is still very high, compared to low molecular weight heparin (LMWH). In the present study, the use of glycoprotein IIb-IIIa inhibitors in STEMI was low (8.8%), lower than that observed in GRACE (20%) [4] and in the Euro Heart Survey (10%) [11] and higher to that observed in ENACT (6%)⁵. Beta-blockers are significantly more prescribed in our study compared to other studies, both during admission and at discharge 82.4% and 83% respectively [3, 4, 11]. Angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors were used, both during admission (69.1%) and at discharge (51%), identical to reported recent surveys[4,11,12]. Statins were prescribed in 95% of the patients during admission and at discharge, more than the overall rate observed in the ESC (54%), in RIKS-HIA (48%)[12]. in GRACE (47%)[4], and in Euroaspire II (43%).

In-hospital and 30-day outcome: The median of hospital stay in our study is 6 days which is short if it directly compared to Euro Heart Survey [11] and to GRACE Registry⁴ in which the median total length in STEMI was 8 days. During the 10 years of NRMI registry, the duration of hospital stays.

Of patients with myocardial infarction in the United States declined from a median of 8.3 days in

1990 to 4.3 days in 1999, independently of whether patients were treated with primary PCI or thrombolysis. A similar very short length of stay (median 5 days) for patients with MI was achieved in Sweden in year 2000 [12].

The in hospital mortality reported in our study (13.2%) is higher than that reported in GUSTO V (5.6%) [13] the main reason for that is that we are a tertiary center, usually receive complicated cases noting that three of the patients had ventricular septal rupture. The overall 30-day follow up mortality in our study was (2.9%) lower than that observed in BLITZ trial (9.2%) [14], in ASSENT trial (6.2%) [15], in GUSTO-V (6.4%) in (HERO-2) [16] (6.7% at 30-days). We think that the reason for this lower mortality is twofold. First, most of the complicated cases died during hospital stay (higher mortality) and secondly a better adherence to medication and adherence to the guidelines in this respect. However the number of the patients was small to draw strong conclusions.

STUDY LIMITATIONS

1. This study is not multicentre and the time for enrollment was short and the number of patients was small.
2. Restriction of the registry to patients who are admitted may have resulted in the lack of enrollment of patients who died early on arrival.

CONCLUSION

Many patients in this study did not receive thrombolytic therapy and the in-hospital mortality was high. Improving the outcome in AMI requires the collaboration of different institutions in the community and requires the development of our diagnostic, therapeutic and organizational tools.

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Clinical implications of additional heads of biceps brachii muscle

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Abstract

Background: Biceps brachii is a superficial muscle of the flexor compartment of arm. It is a strong flexor and a supinator of forearm. It is one of the most variable muscles in terms of number of its heads of origin, so the present study proposes to dissect North Indian cadavers to see the frequency of occurrence of more than two heads of biceps brachii and discusses its clinical implications.

Objective: To determine the prevalence of accessory heads of biceps brachii, their innervation and any anomalous course of neurovascular bundle in the front of arm.

Materials and Methods: Number of heads of biceps brachii muscle were studied in 77 adult human cadavers (n=154). Presence of additional heads of biceps brachii and any variation in the course of neurovascular bundle in the front of arm were noted.

Results: It was observed that the left upper limb of only one middle aged male cadaver had four heads of origin of biceps brachii i.e. the long head from supraglenoid tubercle of scapula, short head from tip of coracoid process of scapula and the two accessory heads from the anteromedial surface of the humerus between the insertion of coracobrachialis and the origin of brachialis. The musculocutaneous nerve took origin from the lateral cord normally and pierced through coracobrachialis to enter the flexor compartment of forearm. Then it passed between the two accessory heads before supplying brachialis and continued as lateral cutaneous nerve of forearm. Each head of biceps brachii was individually innervated by fibers from musculocutaneous nerve. No other anomalies in the neurovascular bundle were observed.

Conclusion: Awareness of the different course of musculocutaneous nerve and origin of supernumerary heads of biceps brachii is of importance to academicians, surgeons, traumatologists, orthopaedicians and plastic.

Keywords: *Biceps brachii, Soft ball, Shoulder, Elbow Musculocutaneous nerve, Variation.*

INTRODUCTION

Classically biceps brachii is a muscle of flexor compartment of arm having two heads, a long head and a short head. The long head arises from supraglenoid tubercle of scapula and the short head from the coracoid process of the scapula. Both the heads commonly get inserted onto the radial tuberosity and the bicipital aponeurosis [1].

Biceps brachii is a strong flexor and a powerful supinator of the forearm. It is a triarticulate muscle i.e. it acts on shoulder joint, elbow joint and proximal radioulnar joint. Its action at these three joints makes it suitable for softball windmill pitching [2].

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Repetitive eccentric contraction of biceps brachii in windmill pitching explains the high incidence of anterior pain in windmill pitchers [3]. Therefore the clinicians should know the variations of biceps brachii for correct diagnosis of pain in the shoulder region or front of arm.

Presence of supernumerary heads of biceps brachii is relatively frequent [4, 5, 6]. If the supernumerary heads are relatively large they provide additional strength to biceps brachii [7]. Though the presence of supernumerary heads is frequent but according to the available literature the passage of musculocutaneous nerve between the accessory heads of biceps brachii has not been reported. The knowledge of this variation is important not only to

the clinicians but also to the traumatologists, surgeons, academicians and plastic surgeons of hand.

METHODS

Both the upper limbs of 77 adult human cadavers of both sexes were dissected. Any variation in the origin of biceps brachii was looked for. Presence of supernumerary heads, the course of the neurovascular bundle and the innervation of the accessory heads was recorded and photographed. Any other variation in the whole cadaver was also looked for.

RESULTS

Out of 154 upper limbs dissected, 153 upper limbs exhibited a consistent pattern i.e. the thickness of the short head was in the range of 1.12 ± 0.22 cm and thickness of long head was 0.99 ± 0.15 cm, the reference point being 12.2 cm below the tip of the shoulder. The short head and the long head merged with each other 14.5 ± 2.0 cm below the tip of shoulder and were commonly inserted into radial tuberosity 2.7 ± 0.5 cm distal to elbow joint. It was observed that the biceps brachii of the left upper limb of only one middle aged male cadaver had four heads of origin. The short head arose from the tip of coracoid process of scapula along with coracobrachialis. The long head had an intracapsular origin from supraglenoid tubercle of scapula. The thickness of short head was 1.10 cm and long head was 0.6 cm.

The third and the fourth head, the supernumerary heads, arose from the anteromedial surface of humerus between the origin of brachialis and the insertion of coracobrachialis (Figure-1)

The third head was 0.15 cm and the fourth head was 0.6 cm in thickness, all measured 12.2 cm below the tip of the shoulder. All the heads ultimately united to form a common tendon 14 cm below the tip of the shoulder which was inserted into the radial tuberosity 2.1 cm distal

to elbow joint and took part in the formation of bicipital aponeurosis. A branch from musculocutaneous nerve was separately innervating each head of biceps brachii.

Figure (1): Photograph of the muscle, Biceps Brachii, showing the origin of the third (t) and the fourth (f) head from the anteromedial surface of humerus between the insertion of Coracobrachialis (c) and the origin of Brachialis (b).

The musculocutaneous nerve passed through the coracobrachialis and then between the third and the fourth head of biceps brachii before innervating brachialis (Figure-2) .No other variation was observed in this cadaver.

Anterior shoulder pain has been clinically observed in windmill pitchers [3]. Biceps brachii taking origin from the supraglenoid tubercle and tip of coracoid process of scapula can explain such a type of pain. It is one of the most variable muscles in terms of number of heads [8]. The most common variation is a third head [9, 10] though even seven heads have been reported [11, 12, 13].

In the present study, out of 154 upper limbs dissected only one left upper limb of a male cadaver showed the presence of four heads of biceps brachii.

DISCUSSION

On gross examination, the third and the fourth head of biceps brachii gave an insignificant contribution to the total mass of the muscle but relatively large supernumerary heads of biceps brachii provide additional strength to it [7].

Figure (2): Photograph of the muscle, Biceps Brachii, of the left upper limb of male cadaver. Note the Musculocutaneous nerve (mcn) passing between the third (t) and the fourth (f) head of Biceps Brachii and innervating all the heads of Biceps Branch separately.

The accessory heads took origin from the anteromedial surface between the insertion of coracobrachialis and the origin of brachialis muscles. Proximal attachment of the accessory heads of biceps brachii to the anteromedial surface of the humerus was referred to as inferomedial head by some researchers [14]. Biceps brachii can give rise to pain not only in the anterior shoulder in softball pitching but also towards the medial aspect of arm as the accessory heads of biceps brachii taking origin from the anteromedial surface of the humerus may be present. Repetitive overhead throwing exerts significant mechanical stress on the shoulder and elbow joint which may lead to development of anatomical changes in young throwers [15]. As the accessory heads of biceps brachii are attached to the anteromedial surface of the humerus, anatomical changes can take place at the anteromedial surface of the humerus also.

Individual heads of the biceps brachii were innervated by a separate branch from the musculocutaneous nerve which originated normally from lateral cord of the brachial plexus and pierced through coracobrachialis to reach the front of arm. It then passed between the accessory heads of biceps brachii before supplying brachialis. Compression of the musculocutaneous nerve between the two accessory heads can interfere with the action of brachialis which is a strong flexor of the elbow

joint. Loss of sensations on the lateral side of forearm can also occur.

Understanding such anomalies would not only interest academicians but will also help doctors dealing with sports medicine, surgeons, clinicians, orthopaedicians and plastic surgeons of hand in diagnosing pain in the shoulder region and anteromedial surface of arm. It will also facilitate them to make an accurate diagnosis of weakness in flexion at elbow joint and supination at proximal radioulnar joint.

CONCLUSION

Knowledge of the presence of accessory heads of biceps brachii will help the academicians and doctors dealing with sports medicine, surgeons, clinicians, orthopaedicians and plastic surgeons of hand to correctly diagnose and treat pain in the shoulder region and front of arm. Awareness of variation in the course of musculocutaneous nerve can assist in finding a solution to weakness of flexion at elbow joint and supination at radioulnar joint.

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Drug Induced Hypokalemia: A Retrospective Study

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Abstract

Objectives: To study the association between the use of diuretics, steroids, or their combination and hypokalemia.

Patients and Methods: One hundred fifty patients receiving diuretics, steroids, or both as a treatment for different medical problems (none of them was receiving potassium supplement) at Al-Hussain hospital in Karbala city, Iraq. were categorized into 3 groups according to the medication used whether it was diuretics, steroids, or combination of both. After detailed medical history and careful physical examination to detect any clinical feature of hypokalemia, electrocardiography and serum potassium estimation was done for every patient. Hypokalemia was considered when the serum potassium was less than 3.5 mm/l.

Results: The mean serum potassium for the study subjects was 3.9 ± 0.61 mmol/l, and 26.7% were found to have hypokalemia. Mild hypokalemia was present in 22% in patients receiving diuretics, and 14% in patients receiving steroids; and 36% in patients receiving combination of them. Moderate hypokalemia was found in 8% of patients receiving diuretics and steroids combination. Only 12% of patients in this study showed symptoms suggestive of hypokalemia (muscle weakness, fatigue, cramps), the majority being in patients receiving combination of diuretics and steroids. No physical signs of hypokalemia were detected in any patient of the study subjects. The study showed an association between decreased serum potassium concentrations with increasing duration of treatment. Electrocardiographic changes of hypokalemia were present in 6% of our patients.

Conclusion: Hypokalemia is a common electrolyte disturbance associated with the use of diuretics and/ or steroids which should be looked after in order to avoid its serious consequences.

Keywords: Diuretics Steroid, Serum potassium, Hypokalemia

INTRODUCTION

Hypokalemia, a serum potassium level of less than 3.5 mmol/l [1], is the most common electrolyte disturbance encountered in medical practice and poses a common diagnostic challenge with many potential associations. Multiple factors may contribute to this electrolyte disturbance, it may be caused by redistribution of potassium into the cells due to factors that increase cellular potassium uptake, in addition to total body depletion of potassium due to renal, gastrointestinal, or sweat losses [2]. Although diuretics (loop diuretics, thiazides) are the most common causes of a potassium deficit, other drugs, abnormalities of the pituitary-adrenal axis, renal disorders including

tumors, and a variety of less well-defined entities should be considered [3]. Hypokalemia is graded as: mild, moderate, and severe, and different limits for these grades were used by different studies [4, 5, 6].

Diuretics are commonly used in medical practice especially for hypertension, congestive heart failure, and edema of various causes [7, 8]. In practice the most common adverse events associated with diuretic administration are electrolyte abnormalities including hypokalemia [9]. The most common cause of hypokalemia being the use of potassium losing diuretics such as frusemide and thiazides [10, 11, 12]. The risk of hypokalemia secondary to diuresis increases when large doses of diuretics are used, when they are used in severe cirrhosis, when diuresis is brisk, and during

concomitant use of corticosteroids or adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) [1, 13].

Steroids are also widely used for various medical situations, especially collagen vascular diseases, asthma, organ transplantation, and as an anti-inflammatory agent [14, 15, 16]. They increase the absorption of sodium and chloride and the excretion of potassium and magnesium by the renal tubules [17, 18]. Sodium retention with potassium loss by urinary excretion may result in hypokalemic alkalosis in patients receiving glucocorticoids [19, 20]. Sodium retention will aggravate muscle weakness caused by hypokalemia [21]. Hypokalemia caused by concomitant use of diuretics and corticosteroids may be worse when there is diminished dietary potassium, alcohol consumption, malnutrition, anorexia nervosa, chronic illness, chronic diarrhea or vomiting, profuse sweating, or receiving intravenous fluid free of potassium, or in patients using certain drugs like salbutamol, theophylline, or insulin [10,22].

Hypokalemia may be asymptomatic and when symptomatic the symptoms and signs of hypokalemia depend on the level of serum potassium. In mild and moderate cases muscle weakness, fatigue, and cramps occur. In severe cases flaccid paralysis and hyporeflexia may occur [23]. The electrocardiographic changes in hypokalemia include flattening of the T wave, prominent U wave, ST depression, or atrial or ventricular ectopic beats [17, 24, 25, and 26].

The aim of this research was to study the association between the use of diuretics, steroids, or their combination, and hypokalemia.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This study was conducted on 150 inpatients in Al Hussain hospital medical ward from 2nd Jan. 2006 to 1st Apr. 2007. They were receiving diuretics, steroids, or both for different medical problems (none of them was receiving potassium supplement). None of them were readmitted during the study period.

Data collected include age, sex, detailed medical history, including the presence of symptoms of hypokalemia (fatigability, muscle weakness, and muscle cramps), and details of treatment including the dose and duration of medications given, and physical examination to elicit features of the clinical condition and signs of hypokalemia (flaccid paralysis, hyporeflexia, tetany) was done.

Electrocardiography was done for every patient to look for ECG changes of hypokalemia including flattening of the T wave, ST depression, prominent U wave, or dysrhythmias.

Venous blood sample was aspirated and serum potassium estimation using Corning-EEL flame photometer for every patient on admission was done (Hemolyzed samples were excluded).

The study subjects were categorized into 3 groups according to their medication. Group I consists of 50 patients treated by diuretics, group II consists of 50 patients treated by steroids, and group III consists of 50 patients treated by combination of both. Hypokalemia was in this study graded as: mild (grade 1: 3.0-3.4 mmol/L), moderate (grade 2: 2.5-2.9 mmol/L) and severe (grade 3: <2.5 mmol/L).

The effect of the different variables on the serum potassium level for the different study groups were statistically analyzed using statistical software (SPSS version 11). Anova test was performed and level of significance was set to be < .05.

RESULTS

The study subjects were 73 males and 77 females, their age ranges from 10 to 70 years with a mean of $44.7 \pm SD 15.5$ years, and the duration of treatment ranges from 3 to 36 months with a mean of $13.38 \pm SD 8.27$ months. The distribution of patients according to gender, mean age, and mean duration of treatment within each of the study groups is shown in Table 1.

Table (1): The gender, the mean age and the duration of treatment of the study groups (P > .05).

Study Group	N	Gender		Mean Age (years)	Treatment duration (Mean \pm SD)*
		M	F		
Group I	50	24	26	57.8 \pm 7.2	15.42 \pm 5.86
Group II	50	25	25	34.7 \pm 10.8	9.98 \pm 8.99
Group III	50	24	26	41.4 \pm 16.6	14.76 \pm 8.67
Total	150	73	77	44.7 \pm 15.5	13.38 \pm 8.27

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to their medical conditions

Group	N	Disease	No
I	50	Hypertension	26
		Heart Failure	20
		Liver Cirrhosis	4
II	50	Asthma	28
		Rheumatoid Arthritis	7
		Kidney Transplantation	4
		SLE	3
		Poor appetite	3
		Behcet Disease	2
		Pemphigus	2
		Allergic Disease	1
III	50	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease	16
		Glomerulonephritis	11
		Heart Failure with asthma	10
		Hypertension + asthma	9
		Kidney Transplantation + hypertension	4

Table (3): The mean serum potassium concentration and the distribution of patients according to the type of medication and the severity of hypokalemia (P< 0.001).

Medication	No	Mean S.K+ (mmol/l)*	Normokalemia	Hypokalemia	
				Mild	Moderate
Thiazide	15	3.97±0.63	39 (78%)	11 (22%)	0
Frusemide	13				
Thiazide+ amelrioride	22				
Prednisolone	39	4.12±0.55	43 (86%)	7 (14%)	0
Dexamethasone	11				
Frusemide + prednisolone	31	3.62±0.53	28 (56%)	18 (36%)	4 (8%)
Thiazide + predniolone	3				
Frusemide with dexamethasone	1				
Thiazide + ameloride + prednisolone	15				
	150	3.90±0.61	110 (73.3%)	36 (24%)	4 (2.7%)

Table (4): The distribution of patients according to the presence of symptoms of hypokalemia

Group	N	Patients with Symptoms (%)
1	50	3 (6%)
2	50	1 (2%)
3	50	14 (28%)
Total	150	18 (12%)

Table (5): Serum potassium according to duration of treatment (P< 0.001)

Duration (months)	No.	Serum potassium (mmol/L)
< 11	63	4.16±0.51
11-20	55	3.84±0.65
21-30	25	3.53±0.49
>30	7	3.33±0.24

Table (6): The distribution of patients according to the presence of electrocardiographic changes

Group	N	Patients with ECG changes
1	50	1 (2%)
2	50	0 (0%)
3	50	8 (16%)
Total	150	9 (6%)

Table (7): Serum potassium level according to the type of diuretic used P< 0.001

Type of diuretic	No of patients	S.K+ (mmol/l)
Frusemide	45	3.68±0.59
Thiazides	18	3.52±0.56
Thiazide+ potassium sparing diuretic	37	4.06±0.55
None	50	4.12±0.55
Total	150	3.90±0.61

The distribution of patients according to the medical conditions for which the patients were receiving the medications in the three studied groups is illustrated in Table 2. Distribution of patients according to the different type of medications they were using is illustrated in Table 3.

In group 3 mild hypokalemia was present in 18(36%) patients and 4(8%) had moderate hypokalemia. Only 18 patients (12%) in this study showed symptoms of hypokalemia, the largest number being in patients in group 3. The distribution of those patients among the study groups is shown in table 4. No physical signs of hypokalemia were detected in any patient of the study subjects.

The study showed decreased serum potassium concentration with increasing duration of treatment as shown in table-5.

The serum potassium level in the study subjects ranges from 2.7 to 5.6 mmol/l with a mean serum potassium of 3.9±0.61mEq/l. Forty patients (26.7%) were found to have hypokalemia. The mean level in each group and the distribution of patients within the studied groups according to the severity of hypokalemia is shown in Table 3. In group 1 mild hypokalemia was present in 11(22%) patients and none had moderate or severe hypokalemia. Nine of those with hypokalemia were receiving thiazides, one frusemide, and one combination. In group 2 mild hypokalemia was present in 7(14%) patients and none had moderate or severe hypokalemia. All the patients with hypokalemia in group 2 were receiving prednisolone.

Electrocardiographic changes of hypokalemia were present in 9 patients (6%), 8 of them were in group 3. The distribution of those patients among the study groups is shown in table- 6.

A significantly higher level of Serum potassium (P< 0.001) was found in patients receiving thiazide and potassium sparing diuretic as

compared to those receiving potassium losing diuretics (table-7).

DISCUSSION

The mean age in group 2 was 34.7 years which is significantly lower than that of the other two groups, which might be attributed to the fact that 56% of them (28 patients) were asthmatic, it was significantly lower than that in group 1 which was 57.84 years as 46 of the patients (92%) were hypertensive or had heart failure. A comparable mean age of patients with asthma was reported by Vondra V et al (1993) , Halasz A et al (2008) , and A Navarro et al (2001) [27, 28, 29, 30].

The mean serum potassium of patients in group 1 was significantly lower than that of those in group 2 that indicates that diuretics cause more severe hypokalemia than steroids ($p < 0.001$), and the mean serum potassium of patients in group 3 was significantly lower than that of those in group 1 and in group 2, that indicates that the use of diuretics and steroids in combination causes more severe hypokalemia than either when given individually ($p < 0.001$), keeping in mind that the mean duration of treatment was not significantly different between the study groups, and there was no available data about the mean serum potassium of the study subjects before starting the treatment,

It was also found that the incidence of hypokalemia was higher in patients receiving diuretics as compared to those who receiving steroids and it was highest in patients receiving combinations of them. This is consistent with the results of Widmer P, Maibach R, and Kunzi UP study conducted in 1994 in Switzerland [31] which was the only study we could find that had studied hypokalemia caused by the use of combination of diuretics and steroids.

All patients who had mild hypokalemia except 4 had moderate hypokalemia in group 3 and none had severe hypokalemia.

Symptoms of hypokalemia are subjective and vague and in addition they can be caused by other diseases e.g., heart failure, drugs (e.g. salbutamol) used for treatment of asthma, or other electrolyte disturbances e.g. sodium retention. Therefore symptoms of hypokalemia were more common in group 3 in which hypokalemia was more common (28%) than in group 1(6%) or group 2 (2%). Of the 38 patients with hypokalemia 18(47%) had symptoms of hypokalemia and that is because most our patients had mild hypokalemia. In comparison with a study conducted 1980 by Lemieux G and Beauchemin M none of their patients had symptoms of hypokalemia [32].

In this study it was found that the longer the duration of treatment the more the incidence of hypokalemia ($p < 0.001$) and this is consistent with the results in the study conducted by Omer SB in Saudi Arabia in 2001[33].

Electrocardiographic changes were absent in group 2 while it was present in one patient in group 1, and in 8 patients in group 3. The larger number of patients who had electrocardiographic changes in group 3 was partially due to patients who had moderate hypokalemia.

Patients in group 1 and 3 were using diuretics. The mean serum potassium in those patients using thiazides diuretic was 3.52, while it was 3.68 in patients using frusemide, and 4.06 in patients using potassium sparing diuretic in combination with thiazides or frusemide. Our results is consistent with results in other studies which shows thiazides diuretics cause more potassium loss than frusemide and that potassium sparing diuretics are effective in preventing hypokalemia induced by diuretic use [11,34,35].

CONCLUSION

Hypokalemia is a common electrolyte disturbance encountered in patients using diuretics and steroids and is more common in patients receiving combination of them.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Because of the serious consequences of hypokalemia, serum potassium level should be monitored in all patients who are at risk of developing it.

Serum potassium level is to be followed in every patient receiving loop diuretics or thiazides without a potassium sparing diuretic or potassium supplement and in patients receiving a combination of diuretics and steroids.

A prospective study, assigning the serum potassium before starting the medications for proper assessment of the possible consequent hypokalemia is recommended.

LIMITATIONS

The difficulty in assessing the effect of the other factors that might contribute in the etiology of hypokalemia like inadequate intake of potassium or the use of other drugs like salbutamol used by our asthmatic patients.

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Etiology and Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern of Otitis Media in Children at Princess Rhamah Hospital in Jordan

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Abstract

Background: Otitis media is one of the most common infections in children. Recently it was noticed that there is a marked increase in relapse of otitis media in children. Therefore, this study conducted to investigate microorganisms causing otitis media in children and to assess their sensitivity to various groups of antimicrobial.

Patients and Methods: A retrospective study was conducted on positive cultures taken from 173 children aged below 15 years, who attended as outpatient or inpatient at Princess Rahmah Hospital between January and December/2008. The obtained data were analyzed and the results were tabulated.

Results: A total of 173 isolates were recovered from cultures obtained from children patients. The male and female isolates ratio was (1.24:1.0). The most frequent pathogen found was *S. aureus* (68.2%), followed by *Streptococcus spp.* (12.1%), *H. influenzae* (9.3%), *Pseudomonas spp* (6.9%) and *Klebsiella spp.* (3.9%). The susceptibility rate of *S. aureus* was recorded the highest (95.9%) for vancomycin, and the lowest susceptibility rate (31.8%) was recorded for oxacillin.

Conclusion: *S. aureus* was the main isolate of otitis media in children, which almost all isolates were susceptible to cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin and vancomycin. Overall oxacillin resistance was near 67%. This information should be considered when empirical therapy is recommended or prescribed for children with otitis media.

Keywords: Otitis media, Antimicrobial, Infection, Bacterial resistance

INTRODUCTION

Otitis media (OM) is an inflammation of the middle ear, and is very common infection in childhood, almost always accompanied by a viral upper respiratory infection (URI), with a peak incidence between 4-7 years of age [1]. The reason for the higher frequency in these populations is due to anatomic differences of skull base and Eustachian tube and biologic susceptibility [2]. Several risk factors have been associated with OM such as previous acute otitis media, hereditary, parental smoking, attending day care centers, bottle feeding and autumn season [3, 4]. The incidence rate is higher in male than female [5].

The most common bacterial pathogens in OM are *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, and *Moraxella catarrhalis* [6, 7]. Other

pathogens responsible for OM are *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella sp.*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Proteus sp* [8]. The type of OM pathogen is depending on the geographical area. [9] In a study done on 917 children with OM in the US, Israel, and Eastern Europe, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, and *Moraxella catarrhalis* recovered in 18%, 5%, 1% of the patients respectively showing variable incidence of those microorganisms according to geographical area [9]. In an Iranian study, the most frequently isolated microorganisms were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Proteus sp* [10].

Many antimicrobials have been used for the treatment of OM infection includes: penicillin, cephalosporins, vancomycin, and macrolides (clindamycin, clarithromycin, and azithromycin) [11]. Bacterial resistance to antimicrobial agents has become an increasing problem in the treatment of

otitis media [12]. A multicentre surveillance study, carried out in Asia and Europe, demonstrated a high prevalence of antimicrobial resistance among respiratory pathogens and important differences in antimicrobial resistance profiles between countries [13]. Pathogens that cause acute otitis media become resistant to common used antibiotics [14, 15]. The increasing rates of antibiotic resistance are due to repeated exposure of these bacteria to antibiotics and geographic spread of resistant strains [16, 17].

The rapid emergence of multidrug resistant otitis media in developing countries is a new potential threat to the survival of newborn babies. Little information about etiology and antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of otitis media is available in Jordan. Therefore, this study was conducted to assess the causative organisms and antimicrobials susceptibility pattern of otitis media pathogens isolated from children during the year of 2008 (from Jan to Dec. 2008) at Princess Rahmah Hospital in Irbid, Jordan. The importance of this study is to aid clinicians to facilitate the empiric treatment and management of children with symptoms of otitis media. Moreover, the data would also help authorities to formulate antibacterial prescription policies.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This retrospective study was conducted on 173 children patients (≤ 15 years of age) who attended as outpatient or inpatient diagnosed with otitis media at the Princess Rahmah Hospital in Irbid, Jordan between January and December 2008. This protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of the ministry of health in Jordan (MOH, REC, MBA, 6838).

Data of microorganisms and antibacterial susceptibility were obtained from the records of clinical microbiology laboratory which filled in a prepared data sheet. Ear discharging for culture was collected from the external auditory canal using a sterile cotton swap. Bacteriological specimens were processed and identified with standard cultures. All isolates were tested for their susceptibilities to at least 8 out of 15 antimicrobials using antimicrobials diffusion discs [18]. Bacterial sensitivity was tested for the following antimicrobials: amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ampicillin, cefaclor, cefixime, clindamycin, cephalothin, cotrimoxazole, ciprofloxacin, cefotaxime, erythromycin, gentamicin, oxacillin, penicillin, tobramycin and vancomycin. Data were analyzed statistically using SPSS (version 15 for Windows) program calculating the frequencies and cross tables.

RESULTS

Through a 12 month duration (January to December 2008), a total of 173 child below 15 years of age (96 male and 77 female) that gave a positive culturing reaction were studied. Results showed that the majority of pathogens isolate were *Staphylococcus aureus* (68.2%), followed by *Streptococcus spp.* (12.1%), *H. influenzae* (9.3%), *Pseudomonas spp* (6.9%) and *Klebsiella spp.* (3.9%), Table-1.

The antimicrobial susceptibility of otitis media isolates for 15 selected antimicrobial agents used in this study are summarized in Table-2.

Of fifteen antimicrobial were tested, both Cefotaxime and Ciprofloxacin had the highest susceptibility rate (92.7%) for all the isolates tested, followed by Vancomycin (88.8%) and Cephalothin (87.8%). Whereas Oxacillin showed the lowest susceptibility rate (33.3%) for all the isolates tested, Table-3.

DISCUSSION

The incidence rate of otitis media in this study was higher in male than female (96 male vs. 77 female), which was in agreement with other finding elsewhere [5].

This current study provides information regarding the main etiological agent *S. aureus* that causes otitis media in children and its antimicrobial susceptibility patterns. These results are in agreement with other studies that reported *S. aureus* as the most common bacteria isolated from children with otitis media [10, 20]. While, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* was the predominant agent of otitis media followed by other microorganisms [6, 7, 9].

The most effective antimicrobial agent against *Staphylococcus aureus* was vancomycin (95.9%), followed by Cefotaxime (94.2%), Cephalothin (92.1%), tobramycin (90.6%), and ciprofloxacin (90.3%). While *Staphylococcus aureus* was found to be low susceptible to erythromycin,

Table (1): Bacterial isolates from children with Otitis Media

Bacteria	Sex		Total	(%)
	M	F		
Staph. Aurous	64	54	118	68.2
Streptococcus	13	8	21	12.1
H. influenza	12	4	16	9.3
Pseudomonas	5	7	12	6.9
Klebsiella sp	2	4	6	3.5
Total	96	77	173	100.0

Table (2): Susceptibility of otitis media bacterial isolates to antimicrobial agents.

Drug	Staph. Aurous		Streptococcus		H. influenza		Pseudomonas		Klebsiella	
	n = 118		n = 21		n = 16		n = 12		n = 6	
	N	S %	N	S %	N	S %	N	S %	N	%
AMC	86	79.0	18	94.4	14	85.7	10	0	5	40.0
AMP	56	48.2	14	71.4	8	50.0	5	0	3	0
CEC	62	74.1	16	56.2	8	62.5	5	0	5	0.0
CF	62	32.2	16	56.2	7	71.4	8	0	4	5.0
CLN	80	86.2	8	85.7	12	83.3	8	75.5	1	50.0
CLT	64	92.1	4	50.0	6	83.3	6	83.3	2	50.0
COT	77	45.4	9	0	8	87.5	8	62.5	5	60.0
CPR	52	90.3	6	100.0	4	100.0	4	100.0	3	100.0
CTX	69	94.2	10	100.0	8	87.5	8	75.0	2	100.0
ERY	59	42.3	2	100.0	6	66.7	5	40.0	2	50.0
GEN	112	83.9	20	65.0	16	81.2	11	72.7	5	80.0
OXC	91	31.8	11	27.2	10	50.0	6	66.7	5	0
PEN	70	40.0	8	62.5	12	41.6	8	50.0	4	25.0
TOB	32	90.6	10	40.0	8	62.5	5	100.0	1	100.0
VAN	98	95.9	14	85.7	10	70.0	9	55.5	3	33.3

Number of isolates(N), Sensitive (S), Amoxicillin-Clavulanic acid (AMC), Ampicillin (AMP), Cefaclor (CEC), Cefixime (CF), Clindamycin (CLN), Cephalothin (CLT), Cotrimoxazole (COT), Ciprofloxacin (CPR), Cefotaxime (CTX), Erythromycin (ERY), Gentamicin (GEN), Oxacillin (OXC), Penicillin (PEN), Tobramycin (TOB), Vancomycin (VAN).

Table (3): Susceptibility of different otitis media bacterial isolates to antimicrobial Agents

Drug	Bacteria		
	N	S	%
CTX	97	90	92.7
CPR	69	64	92.7
VAN	134	119	88.8
CLT	82	72	87.8
CLN	110	92	83.6
GEN	164	132	80.4
TOB	56	44	78.5
AMC	133	99	74.4
CEC	96	62	64.5
AMP	86	41	47.6
COT	107	50	46.7
ERY	74	34	45.9
PEN	102	43	42.1
CF	97	37	38.1
OXC	123	41	33.3

Number of isolates (N), Sensitive (S), Cefotaxime(CTX), Ciprofloxacin (CPR), Vancomycin (VAN), Cephalothin (CLT), Clindamycin (CLN), Gentamicin (GEN), Tobramycin (TOB), Amoxicillin-Clavulanic acid (AMC), Cefaclor (CEC), Ampicillin (AMP), Cotrimoxazole (COT), Erythromycin (ERY), Penicillin (PEN), Cefixime (CF), Oxacillin (OXC).

penicillin, oxacillin and cefixime. Similar finding was reported for susceptibility pattern of otitis media *S. aureus* isolates [10].In this study, majority of isolated showed low susceptibility rates (42.1%, 38.1%, and 33.3%) to penicillin, oxacillin and cefixime respectively. Whereas Cefotaxime and ciprofloxacin showed the highest susceptibility rates of 92.7% followed by vancomycin (88.8%) and

cephalothin (87.8%). These finding for ciprofloxacin suggest that the behavior of these pathogens in our setting is the same as that reported in the international literature [19]. Medical literature has shown an increase in the incidence of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains. Several cofactors have been implicated, among which the frequent use of antimicrobial agents is highlighted [20].

CONCLUSION

Otitis media in children is mainly caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* organisms, which develop resistance to commonly used antimicrobials. This emergence of multiple drug resistance call for judicious antibiotic use to

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Measles Epidemic In Diwaniya

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Abstract

Background: Measles is a disease of infants and children older than 10-12 months as young infants are traditionally protected by maternally acquired passive immunity.

Objectives: to determine the frequency of measles in young infants less than 9 months during an outbreak of the disease in Diwaniya.

Patients and Methods: during the period from December 20, 2008 to February 20, 2009; 260 cases with clinical diagnosis of measles were admitted to the maternity and children teaching hospital in Diwaniya.

Results: twenty nine percent of cases were in infants younger than 9 months, 19% in those between 9-15 months. Forty four percent of those older than 9 months were vaccinated, 27% of the mothers received the measles vaccine and 41% of them had history of measles

Conclusion: These results emphasize the importance of intensification of measles immunization coverage in Diwaniya together with strengthening of campaigns with large coverage is likely to be a key in preventing further measles outbreaks in Diwaniya.

Keywords: Measles, Diwaniya ,Iraq

INTRODUCTION

Measles is a highly infectious viral disease for which humans are the only reservoir [1]. Measles was described by Rhazes (a famous Arabian philosopher and physician in the 10 century AD), he was the first to diagnose small pox and differentiated it from measles, and he edited a famous book on these two diseases Figure-1.

Measles virus is a member of the genus Morbillivirus in the family Paramyxoviridae, the virus was isolated by Enders and Peebles in 1954, measles viruses are spherical, enveloped single stranded RNA viruses. Measles is transmitted primarily from person to person by large respiratory droplets (1) and by the airborne route as aerosolized droplets [4-9].

The incubation period of measles is 10-12 days, the prodromal period then begins with fever, malaise, conjunctivitis, coryza and tracheobronchitis. Koplik spots appear on the buccal

mucosa 1 to 2 days before rash onset and may be noted for an additional 1 to 2 days after rash onset [10, 11]. The most common complications of measles are otitis media, pneumonia, postinfectious encephalitis, subacute sclerosing panencephalitis .The risks of complications and death is increased in young infants and adults [1]. By the end of the 1950s , Enders and colleague had developed the Edmonston B strain of live attenuated measles vaccine [12].By the mid to late 1960, new strains of measles vaccine had been developed in many countries by further attenuation of Edmonston as: Alk-C , Schwarz , Edmonston-Zagrab, Moraten, CAM-70, Leningrad-16,SSI,etc.

The level of antibody induced by immunization with attenuated measles virus vaccine vary with an approximately log-normal distribution , and reach lower peak levels than those induced by wild virus[13].The rate of antibody decline is faster among persons who attain the highest antibody levels post immunization[14]. The maternal antibody profiles of infants vary between geographic regions, the rate of loss of maternal antibodies has

been found to correlate inversely with socioeconomic status [15]. The reasons for earlier loss of maternal antibodies in the developing countries include : (16)

1. Lower antibody level among mothers.
2. Decreased efficiency of transplacental transfer of measles immunoglobulin G₁.
3. Increased catabolism of passive antibodies because of frequent infections in infancy.
4. Loss of antibodies in the intestinal lumen during diarrheal illness.

Low level of maternal antibodies has inhibited successful seroconversion after immunization [17, 18]; seroconversion is related to the level of maternal antibodies [19, 20]. The EPI (Expanded programme on immunization) WHO didn't recommend vaccination in infants less than 9 months except in high risk situations such as refugee camps, hospital outbreaks and for HIV infected children [21].

Figure (1): On-line publication of AL-Razes Kitab fi ALJadri wal Hasba. Website of American University of Beirut

protection afforded by maternal antibodies may be bridged with that induced by the vaccine [24]. The measles immunization schedule in Iraq recommends measles vaccine for infants at nine months of age and MMR (measles, mumps, and rubella) at the age of fifteen months. booster dose of Measles vaccine is also given at school entry (5-6 years).

During late Summer 2008, an observation was made in the maternity and children teaching hospital in Diwaniya (180 km south of Baghdad), Department of pediatrics , that the frequency of cases of measles is increasing particularly in infants less than 9 months old and so this study was conducted to address this problem. The aim of the study is to determine the frequency of measles cases in infants less than 9 months of age in addition to measles vaccination coverage in our patients and their mothers and some clinical and epidemiological aspects of the disease.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

During the period from December 20, 2008 to February 20, 2009, cases of measles admitted to the maternity and children teaching hospital in Diwaniya were addressed; the diagnosis of measles was made on clinical basis [8]. Information was collected on each patient considering the following: age, sex, residence, immunization status, maternal measles status (had the disease in the past, recent disease, immunized, not immunized, unknown), complications of the disease, duration of hospitalization and the frequency of death and its cause.

RESULTS

During the study period, 260 cases of measles were admitted to the maternity and children teaching hospital in Diwaniya. One hundred and sixty seven were males (64%) and 93 were female (36%). Seventy five patients were below the age of 9 months (29%), 50 were between 9-15 months (19%), 26 patients were older than six years (10%). The age and sex distribution is shown in figure -1.

Table (1): The ages and causes of death in the study group

Causes of death	Age (Ms)	No	%
Encephalitis	5, 7	2	40%
Pneumonia	8, 13	2	40%*
Diarrhea	3	1	20%**

*One patient with Pneumonia had also Kala-azar.
 ** The patient with Diarrhea was a case of Down syndrome

Few recent reports conclude that in low income areas, outbreaks of measles may be curtailed by measles vaccination as early as 4.5 months [22, 23]. Strategies for some vaccines under development are aiming to vaccinate younger infants and the

Figure (1): Age and Sex distribution of cases

The majority of the patients were from rural areas, 162 (62%) versus 98 (38%) from urban areas. Forty four percent of infants older than 9 months were vaccinated (82 patients) and 100 patients were not vaccinated (55%), the immunization status was unknown in 3 patients, a good proportion of the vaccinated infants and children received only one vaccine (either measles vaccine or MMR (measles, mumps, rubella vaccine), accurate estimate of the Percentage of full vaccination or partial vaccination

cannot be achieved because most families didn't keep the vaccination record of their children. History of maternal measles was obtained in 80 mothers (31%), recent measles disease during this outbreak was found in 25 mothers (10%), measles or MMR vaccination was traced in 70 mothers (27%). Maternal measles status, maternal immunization and immunization status of our patients is summarized in figure-2, 3. Diarrhea was the most common complication in our patients occurring in 165 patients (63%), followed by pneumonia in 144 patients (55%), encephalitis occurred in 2 patients (0.8%). Most patients required hospitalization for 1-5 days, 205 (79%); 50 patients stayed for 5-10 days (19%) and 5 patients were admitted for more than 10 days (2%). The majority of our patients were discharged well from the hospital, 255 (98%); unfortunately 5 patients died during the study period (2%), the ages and causes of death of those patients is shown in table 1.

Figure (2): Mother immunization and maternal measles status

Figure (3): Vaccination status of children according to the age group

Figure (4): The frequency of measles cases in Diwaniya in comparison with other places.

Figure (5): Vaccination coverage in our patient compared with that in other areas.

Figure (6): Age distribution of infants younger than 9 months

Figure (7): Percentage of IgG-positive infants according to age for measles [Adapted from Ref-29]

DISCUSSION

Measles is an endemic disease in Diwaniya, Iraq and many other countries including the developed ones with variable outbreaks every 2-3 years. More than half of the population had measles by the time they were six years old and 90% had the disease by the time they were 15 years old, it was considered as an expected life event and this was true prior to 1963[2] (discovery and use of the vaccine).more than 2 million cases of measles are reported annually with 345000 deaths in 2005(25). In the UK, 499 confirmed cases were reported to the end of May 2006 compared to 77 cases in 2005 [26].

From January 1st to July 31st 2008, The CDC (centre for disease control and prevention, USA) received 131 reports of confirmed measles cases and this was the highest over the last 15 years (27). This outbreak is also the largest in Diwaniya over the last 15 years. The frequency of measles cases in Diwaniya in comparison with other places is shown in figure -4. [26, 27, 28, 29].

The sex distribution of cases reflect the study sample , while more cases from rural areas reflects poor vaccination coverage as those patients live in a far scattered rural areas and most families wait for the NIDs (national immunization days) and measles is not a routine in these days like the polio vaccine [26]. Forty four percent of our children and 27% of

their mother are partially or fully vaccinated and these figures are relatively low. Vaccination coverage in our patients compared with that in other countries [30, 31, 32] is shown in figure -5.Twenty nine percent of cases were in infants below the age of 9 months; this figure is relatively high as those infants are supposed to be protected by passively acquired maternal antibodies against measles. Decay or loss of maternally acquired measles antibodies is a well known fact. The highest morbidity rate was also observed among children less than 9 months in Sri Lanka outbreak suggesting the waning passive immunity in infancy [33, 34] figure- 7.

In addition to the various causes of loss of maternal antibodies in the developing countries [16], another possible reason for this high frequency of measles cases in this age group is that, most of the mothers of those babies were born during the years 1990-1992, during this time the country was under economic sanctions and there was inadequate vaccination coverage and the problem of the cold chain. This figure of 29% frequency in those less than 9 months is relatively higher than the range between 13-26% reported in Africa (Kenya, Rwanda, Uganda, and Guinea-Bissau) and USA [27, 35]. The insignificant difference in the occurrence of measles cases among those who were vaccinated and who were not, could be partially due to vaccine failure which occurs in approximately 5-15% of vaccine recipients after a single dose of vaccine. Waning immunity after immunization may also be a factor (36, 37). The occurrence of measles cases among mothers reflects the inadequate coverage when they

were infants due to the economic sanctions on this country during the 1990s.

The frequency of complications in our patients is relatively higher than that in the developed countries (28) where the frequency of pneumonia range between 1-6% and diarrhea 8%.The death rate in our patients of 2% is less than that reported elsewhere (Laos 2-5%(29), 3-10% [37], but is definitely higher than that in the developed countries (1/5000 (UK) [26]. Most of our patients were admitted for 1-5 days indicate that the disease is mild and not severe.

CONCLUSION

Measles in Diwaniya is not different from that in other parts of the developing countries, i.e. it is an endemic disease with variable outbreaks every now and then. There is a little increase in the disease frequency in young infants less than 9 months. The vaccination coverage in our patients lags behind that in other parts of the world. Intensification of measles immunization coverage in this city is probably the best measure in preventing further measles outbreaks in Diwaniya. Vaccination of infants younger than 9 months needs to be discussed with WHO regional office/EPI.

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Spirometry Findings of Pulmonary Abnormalities in Sickle Cell Disease

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Abstract

Background: People with sickle cell disease (SCD) may develop sickle chronic lung disease (SCLD). The sickled cells occlude vessels causing vascular injury, especially to organs with sluggish circulation and in atelectatic areas of the lung. Approximately 4% of SCD patients develop SCLD which is responsible for 20% of deaths in SCD population.

Materials and Methods: Thirty one patients with a diagnosis of sickle cell disease enrolled in this study & offered pulmonary function test (PFT) via spirometry after exclusion of concurrent history of smoking or acute chest syndrome (ACS) or asthma. The results of forced vital capacity (FVC), forced expiratory volume in first second (FEV1), and FEV1/FVC ratio were reported to classify the abnormality according to American Thoracic Society criteria of PFT abnormalities.

Results: Abnormal PFT values found in 80.65%, and restrictive changes (70.97%) being the most predominant abnormality. The effect of frequent ACS attacks was not of clinical significance ($p < 0.10$).

There is association between the severity of sickling phenotype & the presence of restrictive lung disease as more severe anemia in steady level through out the course of the illness ($p = 0.08$) found to be of no statistical significance in comparison with lower measured hematocrit at acute sickling presentation ($p = 0.05$) when compared with sickled patient with normal PFT.

Conclusion: Abnormal pulmonary function is not consist with clinical awareness of shortness of breath ,therefore; this test may be considered as the first objective sign of chronic sickle cell lung complications & it may be a good clinical guide in management strategy. Sickle lung complication is indicator of more severe sickling disease and needs early therapeutic intervention.

Keywords: Sickle cell disease, Acute chest syndrome, Chronic lung complications, Lung function alterations.

INTRODUCTION

People with sickle cell disease (SCD) may develop sickle chronic lung disease (SCLD)[1,2] When deoxygenated sickled hemoglobin(HbS) undergoes conformational changes , crystallized Hb S molecules form a viscous solution within erythrocytes, "stiffening" them and changing them from their normal biconcave shape to sickle shape which is less deformable and subject to hemolysis. The sickled cells occlude vessels causing vascular injury, especially to organs with sluggish circulation and in atelectatic areas of the lung. Cells that have sickled repeatedly become irreversibly sickled. deoxygenation is maximal in the venous

circulation and the sickle cells can cause extensive and progressive damage to the pulmonary vascular bed. Approximately 4% of SCD patients develop SCLD leading to end stage respiratory failure, characterized by hypoxemia, restrictive lung disease, cor- pulmonale and diffuse lung abnormality on chest radiograph. These complications are secondary to repeated episodes of pulmonary vaso-occlusion (like acute chest syndrome) and chronic hemolysis which may account for 20% of deaths in SCD population [1, 3, 4].

Dyspnea is a frequent complaint among sickle patients with a multi-factorial underlying etiology and therefore; clinician finds that pulmonary function tests (PFT) may be useful to

document the severity of lung complications in SCD[5,6].The pulmonary function tests of each subject can be classified into one of the 4 categories based on American Thoracic Society criteria [7]

1. Normal: (FVC) forced vital capacity, (FEV1) forced expiratory volume and (TLC) total lung capacity within normal range (at least 80%of predicted) with FEV1/FVC at least 70%.
2. Obstructive: FEV1/FVC ratio less than 70% associated with decreased FEV1 and FVC (less than 80%) while TLC either normal or elevated.
3. Restrictive: I. FEV1, FVC and TLC decreased (no more than 80% predicted) with normal FEV1/FVC ratio (at least 70%) or II. TLC decreased (no more than 80%predicted) with normal FEV1, FVC and FEV1/FVC ratio suggestive of low lung volumes.
4. Mixed: both obstructive and restrictive pictures as FEV1/FVC ratio reduced suggestive of obstructive disease with reduced TLC as a feature suggestive of restrictive disease.

In order to determine which pulmonary dysfunction pattern is predominantly occurred with SCD, this study designed.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

Thirty one patients with sickle cell disease (SCD) Hb SS- homozygous were enrolled during the period from April 2007 to February 2008 in Al-kadhimiya Teaching hospital hematology clinic. Evaluation included history and examination.

Patients with acute chest syndrome attacks (as new episodic chest pain or pleuritic chest pain or unexplained attacks of shortness of breath or new X ray infiltrate) were deferred from the study until 1 month elapsed from the last ACS attack as well as those with combined genotype (sickle/ thalassemia) were excluded, as well as those having history of bronchial asthma or even family history of asthma .All of them were not smokers

Each subject underwent PFT for two times to ensure reproducibility as the differences between the 2 tests must be <20% for each sickled patient who is in clinically steady state (1 month from the last vasoocclusive crisis). Spirometry was the tool used to evaluate pulmonary function abnormality and included the following measures; (FVC) forced vital capacity, (FEV1) forced expiratory volume in first second, and FEV1/FVC ratio. Unfortunately the (TLC) total lung capacity and diffusion capacity for carbon monoxide (DL co) were not available in the used machine currently, and therefore did not include in our assessment. The predicted values in

the spirometry machine for the above measures were calculated on the basis of algorithms that accounted for sex, age, weight and height [8].The data are presented as percent predicted values

The results were analyzed according to American Thoracic Society criteria [7].Statistical analysis includes presentation of all parameters as mean ±SD while PFT data are presented as mean ±SD, according to their percent predicted values. T-test was used to identify significance difference at p<0.05.

RESULTS

Total 31 adolescence and adult homozygous sickled patient were eligible for this study. The average age was 20.23±3.56 yr (range 15-31yr).41% were male. eight patients (25.8%) were complaining from progressive shortness of breath. ACS was common as 41.93% (13/31) reporting history of frequent ACS attacks through out their life while another 32.25% (10/31) reporting incidental episodes during the follow up period.

All patients were reflecting a state of Hb SS phenotype proved by their previous records of hemoglobin electrophoresis. At the time of enrollment in the study, they were anemic as the mean Hb level was 82.5 ±14.4 g/l, with leucocytes and mild thrombocytosis (11.75 ±2.64 x10⁹ /l, 410.96 ±113.46 x10⁹/ l) respectively. Biochemical assessment showed that they were jaundiced as total serum bilirubin was 3.62±2.13 mg/dl with normal liver function tests and renal function tests Tabl-1.

Table 1: patient's parameters

Clinical Parameters	Parameter	Value
	Age (year)	20.23±3.56
	Male gender	41 %
	Shortness of Breath	25.8 %
	ACS history %	74.193 %
Laboratory Parameters	Hb g/l	82.5 +14.4
	Hematocrit	24.76±3.91 %
	WBC x10 ⁹ /l	11.75 ±2.64
	Platelets x10 ⁹ /l	410.96 ±113.46
	Bilirubin mg/dl	3.62±2.13

The finding of spirometry for each patients demonstrated abnormal PFT values in 80.65% (25/31).The overall picture characterized by restrictive changes in 70.97% (22/31) of patients. Although the spirometry was technically within normal range ,the means for FEV1(83.03±16.06%

predicted) and FVC (84.37±16.01% predicted) were considered to be low-normal measures with high FEV1/FVC ratio of 98.36±9.15%. The most common PFT abnormalities observed were restrictive finding 70.97% (22/31) while obstructive finding, either alone or in conjunction with restrictive finding was relatively uncommon, occurring in 9.67% (3/31) of the patients who are already do not have any history of asthma previously or in their family. (tab.2) The effect of ACS attacks on the results of PFT was not of clinical significance as the pattern of PFT abnormalities observed in those with ACS history were similar to those without such history (restrictive pattern). 23 out of 31 (74.19%) had at least one episode of ACS before obtaining PFT in one month period or more (p<0.1).

There is association between the severity of Hb SS phenotype and the presence of restrictive lung disease as the more severe phenotype characterized by more severe anemia in steady level, through out the course of the illness (Hb 83 vs. 87 g/l) (p=0.08) which is of no statistical significance in comparison with lower measured hematocrit at acute sickling presentation (24.7 vs. 26.2%) (p=0.05) and leucocytosis (11.93 vs. 10.95 x10⁹ cell/l) (p=0.06) in comparison with sickled patient with normal PFT.

Table 2: PFT results

Spirometry findings	Test	Value (%)	
	FEV1-mean±SD	83.03±16.06	
	FVC -mean±SD	84.37±16.01	
	FEV1/FVC-mean±SD	98.36±9.15	
Classification of findings	NORMAL	No. (31)	%
		6	19.354
	RESTRICTIVE	22	70.967
	OBSTRUCTIVE	1	3.225
	MIXED	2	6.451

DISCUSSION

Pulmonary complications in adult sickled patients are responsible for 20-30% of the mortality observed (2, 3, 9) Although pulmonary hypertension can occur in about third of SCD patients (10) but it is not the only etiology of shortness of breath observed in SCD. Here in this study it is found that 80.65 % of studied patients have abnormal PFT which is not consistent with clinical awareness of shortness of breath that reported in only 25.8% of the studied patients.

Prior studies have suggested that abnormal PFT is the first objective sign of chronic sickle cell

lung complications which may be a good clinical guide in management strategy [3].

Multiple previous studies have demonstrated a spectrum of PFT abnormalities in adult sickle cell diseases including restrictive lung changes, decreased DL co factor only, hypoxemia & /or obstructive diseases [3,5,6,11,12].

Similar to results of Elizabeth S. et al. & Sylvester K P et al., it is found that abnormal PFT was demonstrated in large proportion of the studied patient (80.65% (25/31)), despite little are complaining from distressing shortness of breath & this may attract attention for earlier assessment of lung abnormality as well as may indicate more severe underlying sickling process as suggested by Elizabeth S et al. who found that 71.3% sickle patient with at least one episode of ACS had a lower TLC in comparison with those have no history of ACS (69.17 vs. 72.83%; p=0.06). This fact unfortunately could not be proved in our study due to lack of body plethmography that designed to define TLC.

The most common PFT abnormality observed in this study is restrictive pattern which agreed with both Elizabeth S. et al.[13] and Sylvester K. P. et al. [3], although it is best demonstrated by measurement of TLC as some of early restrictive changes can be defined by normal FEV1 and FVC with low TLC <80% [13].

In Hb SS, it appears that spirometry alone is not sufficient to predict the diagnosis of restrictive lung diseases especially with out using DL co factor essay or plethysmography where some cases may presented with just low TLC or low DL co alone, in addition to the contribution of other possible factors on the results of PFT like occupational exposure or smoking or co incidental infection how ever it is worth to say that sickle lung complication is directly related to more clinically severe sickling process with sudden drop in hematocrit level (p=0.05) rather than more severe anemia in steady state level (p=0.08), leucocytosis and thrombocytosis.

It is mentioned that prevention of compromised pulmonary function due to recurrent "silent" chest sickling crises may improve the life of those sicklers even if they are in clinical stable disease with well tolerated steady state anemia. Silent acute chest syndrome may be expected whenever there is sudden drop in hematocrit concentration and increase in the number of leucocytes or platelets [14].

Incentive spirometry with use of maximal inspirations exercises(15), early control of respiratory tract infection & hyper reactive airway diseases(16), chronic transfusion therapy[17], or even the use of hydrxyurea are advisable interventions to be considered in management of

Iraqi patients aiming to reduce the chance of lung parenchyma complications.

CONCLUSION

Abnormal pulmonary function is not consist with clinical awareness of shortness of breath ,therefore; this test may be considered as the first objective sign of chronic sickle cell lung complications and it may be a good clinical guide in management strategy. Sickle lung complication is indicator of more severe sickling disease and needs early therapeutic intervention.

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The role of preoperative ultrasound in predicting difficulties encountered during laparoscopic cholecystectomy

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Abstract

Background: Pre-operative prediction of difficulties which may occur during laparoscopic cholecystectomy can help in reduction of operative and postoperative complications. The aim of our study was to study the value of preoperative ultrasound findings for predicting difficulties encountered during LC and to assess the usefulness of these findings to identify patients at high risk of conversion from laparoscopic to OC.

Patients and Methods: A prospective study of 200 consecutive patients who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy for symptomatic cholelithiasis in the period between October 2005 and March 2007 in Rizgary Teaching and Howler Private Hospitals in Erbil, Kurdistan, Iraq. Abdominal ultrasound was done pre-operatively, the diagnosis of gall stones was made and the presence of ancillary findings was recorded. Five ancillary ultrasound findings were assessed. These included; thickened gall bladder wall more than 4mm, presence of pericholecystic fluid, severely contracted gall bladder, empyema, and ^{gall} bladder filled with stones.

Ultrasound findings were compared with the operative findings.

Results: In 36 patients who had one or more of these findings laparoscopic

Cholecystectomy was difficult in 22(61.1%) of them. The statistical analysis showed that thick wall gall bladder > 4mm has the highest sensitivity (69%) and the presence of pericholecystic fluid has the highest specificity (100%) in predicting difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy and the presence of more than 2 ancillary findings yielded an accuracy rate of (100%). Conversion to open cholecystectomy was needed in 13.9% of these patients. The rates of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy and conversion to laparotomy were much lower in those patients who had no ancillary findings (4.3%) and (1.2%) respectively.

Conclusion: Preoperative ultrasound findings are of value for predicting difficulties encountered during laparoscopic cholecystectomy which may require conversion to open cholecystectomy.

Keywords: Laparoscopic surgery, cholecystectomy, ultrasound, ancillary ultrasound findings.

Introduction

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) is now considered the gold standard procedure for symptomatic gallstone disease [1] and one

of the most frequently performed procedures in surgery. LC has substituted traditional cholecystectomy due to a more comfortable postoperative period than the open approach [2]. The increasing experience with LC has led to an expansion of the indications for this procedure, a reduction in contraindications of the procedure, and more complex cases being operated laparoscopically. The definition of difficult LC is inconsistent. The term *difficult cholecystectomy* refers to multiple technical intra-operative difficulties that increase the risk for complications and significantly prolong the operating time[3,4] Although most patients will also benefit from the laparoscopic approach, difficult cases are at a higher risk for conversion and the resulting complications that may overshadow all advantages of the laparoscopic procedure, making this approach unsafe, uneconomic, inefficient, and hence possibly inferior to traditional open cholecystectomy (OP)[5,6]. Reliable predictive factors for difficult procedures and hence conversion of LC would be extremely useful in the preparation and planning of management for patients with symptomatic cholelithiasis [7, 9].

Patients and Methods

This is a prospective study of 200 consecutive patients who underwent LC for symptomatic gall bladder stones during the period from October 2005 to March 2007 in Rizgary Teaching and Hawler Private Hospitals in Erbil by one surgeon. Exclusion criteria included patients with unstable ASA III or IV classification and patients with suspicion of choledocholithiasis. Preoperative workup included a complete history and physical examination and a routine laboratory and radiological tests for all patients. Ultrasound examination for all patients was carried out in Erbil Teaching Hospital by one sonography expert on day before operation, using a

high resolution ultrasound machine (3.5MHz, curvilinear probe, G 50 Semens). The patients fasted for 6 hours before the examination. The initial scan was performed in the right subcostal region during suspended inspiration. Scans were performed both along the long axis and at right angles to the long axis of the gallbladder. When necessary right lateral intercostal scans were performed along the length of the intercostal spaces. A further alternative approach was to lay the patients completely on their left side and to perform anterior subcostal scans. Care was taken to ensure that the entire volume of the organ is examined and that even a tiny calculus not missed. A special care was given to record any ancillary finding including; thick gall bladder wall, contracted gall bladder, presence of pericholecystic fluid, gall bladder filled with gall stones, and finally if the clinical and ultrasound findings would suggest empyema of the gall bladder. The study approved by local research ethics committee. Informed consent was taken from the patients. The procedure of LC and the risk of conversion were explained to them, with a special emphasis for those patients with a higher risk of conversion. All patients received 1 gm Cefotaxime i.v. at time of induction of anesthesia and another 2 doses at 8 and 16 hours postoperatively. All operations performed under general anesthesia by standard North American laparoscopic technique.

Intra-operative cholangiography was not carried out in any of the procedures. A closed drain was used when indicated. The preoperative ultrasound findings compared with intra-operative findings. The operations which were not converted to OC, graded as difficult or

easy operations according to the period between insertion of the ports and clipping of the cystic duct and artery. When this period is less than 30 minutes the operation regarded as easy otherwise it regarded as difficult. The data analyzed statistically by SPSS 15.

Results

The study was comprised 200 patients. The age ranged between 16 to 79 years (mean was 35). One hundred sixty one patients were women and 39 were men. The male to female ratio was (1:4). There was no mortality in the study. All patients had surgically proven gall stones, thus sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy of ultrasound in diagnosis of gall stones were 100%. Thirty six patients (18%) had additional ultrasound findings that presumed to be of significance in predicting difficult LC and conversion to OC. These ancillary findings shown in table -1.

Ancillary findings	No.
Thickened gall bladder wall more than 4mm.	26
Presence of pericholecystic fluid.	8
Severely contracted gall bladder	2
Empyema.	2
Gall bladder filled with stones.	8

Table (1): Ancillary ultrasound findings in 36 patients (some patients had more than one ancillary finding)

LC was easy in 164(82%) patients and difficult in 29(14.5%) patients, while in 7(3.5%) patients the procedure had to be converted to OC.

In patients who didn't have ultrasound ancillary findings, the procedure was easy in 155(94.5%), difficult in only 7(4.3%) cases, the reasons of difficulty were; severe adhesions (n=3), morbid

obesity (n=2), liver cirrhosis (n=1) and uncontrolled intra-operative bleeding (n=1), while conversion rate was 1.2% i.e. only in two patients and it was because of severe adhesions (Figure- 1).

Figure (1): A- Laparoscopic photo of a patient who had severe adhesions. B- The preoperative ultrasound of the same patient showed neither, ancillary findings nor any indication of a difficult procedure.

In patients who had ancillary ultrasound findings, the rate of difficult LC was 61.1% and conversion rate was 13.9%. These results were much higher and statistically significant when compared with the results of patients who had no ancillary ultrasound findings ($P > 0.05$) (Table -2).

Gall bladder wall thickness was an important predicting factor of difficult LC. Fifteen of 26 patients with wall

	Patients with no ancillary ultrasound findings	Patients with ancillary ultrasound findings	Total
Total	164 (82%)	36 (18%)	200 (100%)
Easy LC	155 (94.5%)	9 (25%)	164 (82%)
Difficult LC	7 (4.3%)	22 (61.1)%	29 (14.5%)
Conversion to OC	2 (1.2%)	5 (13.9%)	7 (3.5%)

Table (2): Rates of difficulty of Laparoscopic cholecystectomy and conversion to open cholecystectomy.

thickness greater than 4mm had difficult operation (Figure-2), thus the sensitivity of wall thickness greater than 4mm in predicting difficulty was 69%, and specificity 96.5% (Table -3).

Figure (2): (a. and b.) Ultrasound and laparoscopic photo of a patient who had acute cholecystitis with a thick wall gall bladder

Presence of fluid in the pericholecystic area resulted in even more difficult

laparoscopic procedure (Figure- 3). In all of 8 patients with pericholecystic fluid collection the operation was difficult: sensitivity of pericholecystic fluid for surgical difficulties during LC was 10.3%, and specificity 100% (Table- 3).

Figure (3): Ultrasound and laparoscopic photo of a patient who had acute cholecystitis with pericholecystic fluid.

Procedure	Ultrasound Predictors				
	Wall thickness >4 mm	Pericholecystic fluid collection	Contracted gall bladder	Gallbladder filled with stones	Empyema
Total	26	8	2	8	2
Easy LC	6	0	0	3	0
Difficult LC	15	3	2	5	1
Conversion to laparotomy	5	5	0	0	1
Sensitivity (%)	69.0	10.3	6.9	17.2	3.4
Specificity (%)	96.5	100.0	100.0	98.2	99.4
Positive predictive value (%)	76.9	100.0	100.0	62.5	50.0
Negative predictive value (%)	94.8	86.8	86.4	87.5	85.9
Accuracy (%)	92.5	92.5	86.5	86.5	85.5

Table (3): Value of Ultrasound findings in predicting difficult Laparoscopic cholecystectomy

	Ultrasound predictors				
	One	Two	Three	Ancillary	No ancillary
Total	28	6	2	36	164
Easy LC	9	0	0	9	155
Difficult LC	19	2	1	22	7
Conversion to laparotomy	0	4	1	5	2
Sensitivity (%)	90.1	79.9	78.3	94.5	25.0
Specificity (%)	67.9	100.0	100.0	75.0	5.5
Positive predictive value (%)	94.5	100.0	100.0	94.5	5.5
Negative predictive value (%)	52.8	13.3	4.4	75.0	25.0
Accuracy (%)	87.0	80.5	78.5	91.0	9.0

Table (4): Value of the number of ancillary ultrasound findings in predicting difficult Laparoscopic cholecystectomy

Other ancillary ultrasound findings apart from gall stones indicating difficult surgical preparation namely contracted gall bladder and empyema were also observed (Table 3). When the gall bladder was filled with stones (n=8), difficulty was encountered in 5 patients, making its sensitivity 17.2%, its specificity 98.2% (Table 3). In patients with more than one ancillary finding by

ultrasound, LC was never easy i.e. specificity and positive predictive value were 100% (Table 4). LC was converted to OC whenever it was deemed necessary to avoid exposing patients to unnecessary risks. Conversion rate was higher when there was more than one ancillary ultrasound findings (Table 4).

Discussion

The first account of gall stones was given in 1420 by a pathologist Antonio Benevieni, in a woman who died with abdominal pain. With the passage of time, first OC and then, LC were established as the standard treatment of gall stones [10].

Ultrasound is noninvasive and cost effective, involves no ionizing radiation, and has a reported specificity of 99% for the detection of gall stones [11, 12]. In our study its specificity was 100%. It is the cornerstone imaging modality for the diagnosis of gall bladder stones, and it is unlikely to be replaced by other examination methods [13]. It is generally accepted as the modality of first choice for the diagnosis of acute cholecystitis [14-16]. It has relevance for decision taking, and is an indispensable procedure in the emergency setting [17].

In the early years of LC, acute cholecystitis was considered a relative contraindication, especially in severe attacks or if the gall bladder wall thickness was more than 4mm [18]. Since then, many reports worldwide documented the safety of the procedure in acute cholecystitis [18-21] and the operation is recommended as the treatment of choice for acute cholecystitis [5, 22].

The definition of a difficult LC relative and it is linked to the experience of the surgical team [3]. In the present study, difficult LC occurred in 14.5% of total surgical procedures. We evaluated preoperative ultrasound's capacity of predicting technical challenges in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. When there were ancillary ultrasound findings, where difficulty was anticipated, the

percentage of difficult LC increased significantly to 61%.

Our findings suggest that patients with thickened gall bladder wall tend to have technical difficulties during LC. Similar findings have been reported by many authors [23-26], in fact it was the most sensitive ultrasound findings that predict a difficult LC.

Pericholecystic fluid is another predictor of difficult LC. In our study eight patients had pericholecystic fluid and the surgical procedure was difficult in all of them, making the presence of pericholecystic fluid more specific than gall bladder thickness in predicting difficult LC.

When there were more than 2 ultrasound findings suggesting acute cholecystitis, the specificity of ultrasound in predicting technical difficulty mounted to 100%. Difficult LC needs longer time to finish and the preoperative prediction of long operation when patients are listed for LC may have several practical applications. In addition to allowing better planning of the operating sessions, both in terms of service provision and training of junior doctors, it may allow a more efficient selection of patients for ambulatory LC. Moreover, additional anesthetic measures may be taken to minimize postoperative emesis and dizziness [8].

In a large study involving 6,380 patients Kuldip & Ohri reported an overall conversion rate of 0.42% and a rate of 1.86% in difficult cholecystectomies [10], while Livingston & Rege reported conversion rates ranging on average between 5% and 10% in a nationwide study in the USA [27]. Others reported conversion rates of 2.9-10% for elective

LC and 6-35% for acute cholecystitis [5, 19, 22, 28]. In our study the conversion rates were 1.2% in patients without ancillary ultrasound findings, 13.9% in patients with ancillary ultrasound findings, and an overall conversion rate of 3.5%.

The quest for predicting the probability of conversion of LC in unselected patients with calculus gall bladder disease has been extensive [5,29,30,32]. Many authors have reached conclusions that preoperative ultrasound examination is useful in selecting patients who are likely to have difficulty and may require conversion from laparoscopic to open surgery. Thickened gall bladder wall [38, 41], and the presence of pericholecystic fluid [42] being the most strong association with conversion, as seen also in your study.

In our study, the conversion rate in patients with no ancillary findings was 1.2%, but it was significantly higher (13.9%) when ultrasound showed findings that might predict conversion from laparoscopic to open approach. Conversion rate was higher when there was more than one ancillary finding.

Five patients from those with no ancillary ultrasound findings had difficult LC and in two of them the procedure was converted to laparotomy. Ultrasound could not predict difficulty, mostly because the reason for difficulty and conversion was severe adhesions around the gall bladder which is a finding the preoperative ultrasound can not show, but rather it is an intraoperative finding [43]. On the other hand 25% of our patients with ancillary ultrasound findings, LC was easy, this can be explained partially by the fact that some of these procedures were done at

later stages of the study i.e. later stage of the learning curve of the surgeon, and partially by the fact there are other factors which may contribute to the degree of difficulty, like age, sex and obesity [44, 45].

Conclusion: preoperative ultrasound is able to furnish valuable data in predicting laparoscopic cholecystectomy challenges. On the other hand, a relevant number of cases still exist wherein the concordance between the preoperative ultrasound findings and the surgical findings is unsatisfactory. In this group of patients the surgeon cannot safely rely on ultrasound examination alone and factors with a higher predictive value are obtained only during LC. The need to convert can only be assessed during an attempt at LC.

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Placenta accreta: Is there a place for over sewing of placental site?

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Abstract

Background: Placenta accreta is a cause of life threatening hemorrhage. Hysterectomy is the traditional treatment. Over sewing placental site were introduced to preserve fertility but its place is not clear.

Patients and Methods: 25 patients with placenta accreta had been treated, during period of 12 month, in Medical City. Over sewing of the placental site were tried in ten cases.

Results: Six women out of ten preserve their reproductive function with over sewing sutures.

Conclusion: Over sewing of placental site showed some effect in some patients who had focal placenta accreta.

Keywords: *Placenta accreta, Over sewing of placental site.*

INTRODUCTION

Placenta accreta (PA) is a condition in which part of the placenta is adherent to the uterine wall because of invasion of myometrium by chorionic villi [1]. This invasion could be [accreta] superficial just attach to myometrium (75-80%), [incretta] deep to myometrium (15-17%) or extensive [percreta] involving organs outside the uterus like urinary bladder (5-7%) [1]. The invasion could involve all cotyledons (total), several cotyledons (partial) or only one cotyledon (focal) [2].

The incidence of (PA) reported to be 1/30000 in 1930, 1/19000 in 1960 [3] while present incidence in USA and UK is between 1/800 and 1/200 [4], this possibly is due to rising rate of caesarean section. The rate of (PA) has a direct relationship to the rate of placenta previa and the number of prior caesarean sections [5].

PA is associated with 9.5% maternal mortality rate, in addition to high morbidity rate in form of massive blood transfusions, infection, ureteral damage and fistula formation [6]. Traditionally, hysterectomy has been the treatment of choice in cases of (PA) [7] conservative management is being

described in some cases and uterine preservation was successful [8] Over sewing of the placental site (OSPS) is one of these conservative methods. It can be done by placing multiple(3-4) deep square suture over area of maximum bleeding of placental bed as described by James et al(1). In this study we tried to evaluate the success to preserve the uterus, if OSPS was used in selected cases of PA.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This is a prospective observation study carried out in the department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Medical City –Baghdad. During the period of 12 months (1st March 2006 – 28 Feb 2007), 4661 babies were born, 25 mothers had placenta accreta (1/200). We considered the diagnosis of placenta accreta on clinically, during caesarean section by delayed spontaneous separation of placenta and difficulty in establishing a cleavage plane during manual removal of the placenta. Over sewing of placental site by placing multiple 3-4 square sutures over the area of maximum bleeding using chromic cat gut NO 1 was done in ten cases who were haemodynamically stable, the placental invasion was superficial (clinically) and limited to

one cotyledon of the placental bed (focal placenta accreta). Additional surgical procedure (bilateral internal iliac arteries ligation or secondary hysterectomy) was needed when OSPS failed to control the hemorrhage. Five women out of ten (treated primarily by OSPS) continued to bleed and internal iliac arteries ligation was performed to stop placental hemorrhage in one case, while secondary hysterectomy was needed to control hemorrhage in another four cases. Postoperative histopathological examination of hysterectomy specimens confirmed placenta increta diagnosis rather than placenta accreta as suspected on clinical ground at the time of Caesarean section. Fifteen women treated primarily by hysterectomy were excluded from this study and their abnormal adherence of the placenta was confirmed later by histopathological examination to be partial accreta in (nine cases), increta in (four cases) and percreta in another (two patients).

RESULTS

There was no significant difference between two groups of patients, in their age, gravidity, parity or gestational age as shown in table - 1.

Two of our patients delivered vaginally, ten by elective caesarean section and thirteen women had emergency abdominal delivery as appear in table - 2.

Three of our patients who had hysterectomy as first choice, required internal iliac arteries ligation later to control their hemorrhage while another five women were continued to bleed after

(OSPS) and secondary hysterectomy (4 cases) and internal iliac arteries ligation (one case) were needed to control hemorrhage, as shown in table - 3 and 4. Significant difference was found between both groups of patients in their successful outcome. There was no significant difference in final maternal morbidity between two groups of patients; there was only one maternal mortality was recorded after primary hysterectomy as appear in table - 5.

The average incidence of PA has been estimated to be 1/2500 birth [1]. The incidence in our hospital was higher (1/200); this is due to the fact that our hospital is the main tertiary center in Iraq and many cases of antenatal suspected or diagnosed PA were referred to us.

Both hysterectomy and (OSPS) group had similar features as shown in table - 1, these findings are comparable to Kayem et al [9] and Brettelle et al [10]. Most of our patients (91%) have been delivered abdominally with only 2 cases vaginally (table - 2) in agreement with Brettelle et al [10].

Thirteen patients (57%) were treated as an emergency case, eleven abdominal plus two vaginal deliveries as appear in table - 2. For many years, hysterectomy is the treatment of choice in cases of placenta accreta, as PA was considered a serious complication of pregnancy. Hysterectomy was associated with loss of fertility with high morbidity rate. Conservative management of PA, aimed to preserve fertility and reduce morbidity. The American college of obstetricians and gynecologists (ACOG) clinical guide line [11] support the use of conservative measures in focal placenta.

Table (1): Patients' characteristic of women with placenta accreta

	Primary hysterectomy	Conservative management	p	
Age in years (mean+/-SD)	31.07(5.13)	30.00(5.22)	0.61	NS
Gravidity (mean+/-SD)	5.69(2.89)	4.75(3.36)	0.46	NS
Parity (mean+/-SD)	3.50(1.56)	2.90(1.67)	0.35	NS
Gestational age in weeks at delivery (mean+/- SD)	34.07(3.37)	35.08(5.59)	0.35	NS

NS=not significance at P =0.05

Table: (2):Type of delivery in women with placenta accreta and their primary management

Type of delivery	Primary hysterectomy	Conservative management	Total (%)
Vaginal delivery	0	2	2(9%)
Elective caesarean section	5	5	10(43%)
Emergency caesarean section	8	3	11(48%)
Total	13	10	23(100%)

Table (3): Outcome of Placenta Accreta First Line Treatment

	Over Sewing	Primary Hysterectomy	Total (%)
Success Outcome	5	10	15 (65)
Failure Outcome	5	3	8 (35)
	10	13	23 (100)

Table (4): The Second Line Treatment of Placenta Accreta

	Secondary hysterectomy	Internal iliac arteries ligation	Total
Failure of primary hysterectomy	0	3	3
Failure of conservative management(over sewing)	4	1	5
Total	4	4	8

Table (5): The postoperative morbidity in patients with placenta accreta according their primary treatment.

	Primary hysterectomy	Conservative management
Blood unit (mean+/-SD)	5.53(3.30)	3.33(2.80)
Fresh frozen plasma units(mean+/-SD)	5.92(6.00)	5.00(5.22)
Admission to intensive care unit (%)	2/13 (15.3%)	0/10
Bladder injury (%)	4/13	1/10
Vesico-vaginal fistula	1/13	0/10
Infection	2/13	1/10

DISCUSSION

The average incidence of PA has been estimated to be 1/2500 birth[1]The incidence in our hospital was higher(1/200); this is due to the fact that our hospital is the main tertiary center in Iraq and many cases of antenatal suspected or diagnosed PA were referred to us.

Although hysterectomy is the standard procedure in cases of placenta accreta we can still preserve the uterus by using simple surgical technique before the decision is taken for hysterectomy as suggested by The American college of obstetricians and gynecologists (ACOG) clinical guide line [9]. By applying over sewing technique (described above) we were successful to preserve (6/10) uteruses, five as primary outcome of over sewing of placental site and another one saved after additional bilateral internal iliac arteries ligation Reviewing the histopathological examination of their uteri removed after failure of (OSPS) proved that the placentae were (deeply invading) rather than (superficial invading) the myometrium, in discrepancy with our intra-operative assessment. This is mostly due to difficulty in estimating the depth of invasion [1]. Over sewing placental bed used in haemodynamically stable patients as a primary procedure taking few minutes, according to our own observation it caused no relevant delay, no more morbidity and preserved fertility. Six out of 10(OSPS patients) preserve their reproductive ability.

CONCLUSION

Over sewing of placental site showed some effect in some patient who believed had minor degree of placenta accrete

Over sewing of placental site in selective cases of placenta accreta associated with higher failure rate to control bleeding, but even though such failure not increased the morbidity and the fertility can be preserved and it is worthy tried.

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The Pattern of Brain Metastases :Three centers report

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Abstract

Background: Brain metastases are neoplasms that originate in tissues outside the brain and spread secondarily to involve the brain.

Methods: 54 patients (61% males and 39% females) with metastatic brain tumors were admitted to 3 neurosurgical centers in Baghdad (the Neurosurgical Ward in Hospital for surgical specialties, the Neurosurgical Hospital, and the University Hospital in AL-Kadhimiya) during the period between from January 1997 to December 2003. The patients included in this study were those who had an operation for the intracranial lesion and had a histopathological proof to be a metastatic tumor, or those who had no operation to the intracranial lesion, but have a histopathological proof of the primary lesion.

Results: The most common primary cancer to metastasize to the brain in our study was from the lung accounting for 35.18% of the patients.

It is more common in males. Headache is the most common presenting symptom followed by focal weakness and seizures. The most common primary site is the lung, next is the breast, and third is the lymphatic system. 29.62 % of the patients have unknown primary tumors which is a high percentage in comparison with the developed countries. Surgery for the metastatic brain tumors was done for 42.6% of the patients, and the frequency of surgery was more with single lesions. Radiotherapy is still the main treatment modality used for patients with metastatic brain tumors in our country either postoperatively or without surgery. 90.74% of our cases receive radiotherapy. Adenocarcinoma is the most common histopathological diagnosis of the brain metastases; next is the undifferentiated carcinoma and the third is Squamous cell carcinoma.

Conclusion: Metastatic brain tumors are common in Iraq, but the incidence is still less than reported in the developed countries.

Keywords: Metastatic brain tumors, Iraq

INTRODUCTION

Brain metastases are neoplasms that originate in tissues outside the brain and spread secondarily to involve the brain. This may result either from direct local extension of the primary growth, or from blood borne metastases. The incidence of brain metastases is difficult to determine with precision. Previous reports suggested that metastases made up 5-20 % of the total number of intracranial tumor, and a prevalence of 20-40 % among cancer patients is estimated to be Gender also plays a role in certain instances: males have a higher incidence of metastases from lung

cancer and melanoma whereas women have a higher incidence of breast primary cancer [1, 2, 3, 4]. Approximately 80-85% of brain metastases are located in the cerebral hemispheres, 10-15% in the cerebellum, and 3-5% in the brain stem. The highest incidence of parenchymal metastases is posterior to the Sylvian fissure near the junction of temporal, parietal and occipital lobes (presumably due to embolic spread to terminal middle cerebral branches). They are more often parietal (67%) than frontal (33%) [4-9]. CT scan data indicated that brain metastases are multiple in about 45-50% of cases. More recent experience with MRI indicates that the incidence of multiple metastases is higher than was previously believed; occurring in 2/3 to

3/4 of patients with brain metastases [5, 10, 11, and 12].MRI is currently the diagnostic test of choice for brain metastases. Contrast (gadolinium) enhanced T1-weighted images are shown to be more sensitive and specific than any other imaging technique in determining the location, number, and presence or absence of metastases particularly those located in the posterior fosse. The contrast-enhanced MRI is also the preferred method of assessing the presence of leptomeningeal metastases. A characteristic nodular pattern of enhancement is often seen within the basal cisterns, Sylvian fissure, and cortical sulci and along the tentorium [10, 11, 12].

PATIENTS AND METHODS

54 patients (61% males and 39% females) with metastatic brain tumors were admitted to 3 neurosurgical centers in Baghdad (the Neurosurgical Ward in Hospital for surgical specialties, the Neurosurgical Hospital, and the University Hospital in AL-Kadhimiya) during the period between from January 1997 to December 2003.The patients included in this study were those who had an operation for the intracranial lesion and had a histopathological proof to be a metastatic tumor, or those who had no operation to the intracranial lesion, but have a histopathological proof of the primary lesion. Figure-1 shows the age distribution.52% of the patients were from Baghdad. 21 patients (38.89%) were private workers, 17 patients (31.48%) were housewives, 6 patients (11.11%) officials, 6 patients (11.11%) retired, 1 patient(1.85%) engineer, 1 patient (1.85%)teacher, 1patient(1.85%) driver, 1 patient (1.85%) student.

All the patients received dexamethasone 4 mg 6 hourly IV after the CT diagnosis even for those who had no operation for the intracranial lesion. Carbamazepine in a dose of 200 mg 2-4 times daily was used in 27 patients, 17 of them had seizure at time of presentation, and the other 11 were given the Carbamazepine prophylactically in the preoperative period. Surgery was done for 23 patients. The type of the operative intervention was determined according to the site, size of the tumor, age of the patients, and his medical and general conditions regarding fitness for surgery and anesthesia. The management of the primary lesion also played a role in the management of the intracranial metastasis.

All the 23 patients were operated under the general anesthesia (GA). The surgery was burr-hole biopsy, craniotomy, or a posterior fossa craniectomy. The last two were either with total removal of the tumor (macroscopically completely removed), or subtotal removal (significant part left because it was inaccessible or invading important structures). The cystic component of the tumor was

aspirated in those tumors that are not removed totally to achieve a better decompression. The pathological specimens were preserved and send for the histopathological study to confirm the diagnosis of the metastasis. All of the patients in this study received radiotherapy (except 4 patients died after proving the diagnosis) for the intracranial lesion after histopathological diagnosis of the secondary lesion by operation in 23 patients, or by radiological diagnosis in-patients with a known primary lesion. The radiation was in the form of whole brain radiotherapy (WBRT) in a dose ranging from 2000-4000 rads in 2-4 week. Unfortunately, the hospital records of those patients did not have data about the post-radiation follow up and survival, so we could not include this information in this study.

Figure (1): The age distribution of the patients.

RESULTS

The most common primary cancer to metastasize to the brain in our study was from the lung accounting for 35.18% of the patients. It is more common in males .Headache is the most common presenting symptom followed by focal weakness and seizures. The most common primary site is the lung, next is the breast, and third is the lymphatic system. 29.62 % of the patients have unknown primary tumors which is a high percentage in comparison with the developed countries. The metastatic tumors of the breast origin are increasing on the expense of those from lung origin, but still the latter are higher. Motor deficit is the most common sign & occurred in 48.15%. Papilloedema occurred in 44.44% of cases and was more common with single brain metastasis and with tumors in the infratentorial region. Facial palsy is the third. Metastatic brain tumors are multiple in 53.7% and single in 46.3% of the cases. 60% of the metastatic tumors are in and around the parietal lobe of the brain. The second common origin is the cerebellum 12%. Most of the metastases from lung origin are multiple 63.15%, &most of the metastases from breast origin are single 72.7%. Metastatic brain

tumors are cystic in 16.67% of the cases, & most of the unknown primary cases 68.7 % are multiple. Clinical improvement is seen after steroid administration in most of the patients. Surgery for the metastatic brain tumors was done for 42.6% of the patients, and the frequency of surgery was more with single lesions. Radiotherapy is still the main treatment modality used for patients with metastatic brain tumors in our country either postoperatively or without surgery. 90.74% of our cases receive radiotherapy. Adenocarcinoma is the most common Histopathological diagnosis of the brain metastases; next is the undifferentiated carcinoma and the third is Squamous cell carcinoma.

Table (1): Origin of metastatic brain tumors

Primary site	No. (%)
Lung	19(35.18%)
Breast	11 (20.37%)
Bladder	2(3.7%)
Lymphatic system	3 (5.55%)
Renal	1 (1.85%)
Colon	1 (1.85%)
Skin	1(1.85%)
Unknown	16 (29.62%)

The most common primary cancer to metastasize to the brain in our study was from the lung accounting for 35.18% of the patients. Table-1 shows the origin of metastatic brain tumors.

Table (2): The main presenting symptoms.

Symptoms	No	%
Headache	42	77.78
Focal weakness	29	53.7
Nausea/vomiting	2	40.74
Seizures	13	24.1
Disturbed consciousness	13	24.1
Unsteady gait	10	18.52
Blurred vision	9	16.67
Speech difficulty	6	11.11
Behavioral changes	4	7.41
Dysphasia	3	5.56
Double vision	2	3.7
Numbness	2	3.7
Hoarseness	1	1.85
Hemiparesis	26	48.15
Papilloedema	24	44.44
Facial palsy	11	20.37
Ataxia	8	14.81
Dysphasia	6	11.11
6th nerve palsy	3	5.56
Visual field defect	3	5.56

Headache was the presenting symptoms in 40.74% of the cases. It was markedly severe in 22.7 % of those patients and this could be related to the rapid growth of the metastases.

Table-2 shows the main presenting symptoms. Figure (2): Duration of presenting symptoms.

Focal weakness was the presenting symptoms in 29.63%of the cases, which was usually a localizing, sign of the lesion. Fit was the presenting symptoms in 14.81% of the cases which was generalized in 75% of them, and 62.5% of those patients presented with fit have multiple brain metastases. This shows that the more the number of the intracranial lesions, the more liability of the patient to present with fit. Of 38 patients with known primary tumor. , 22 patients had a previous operation for the removal of the tumor from the primary as shown in table-3. Table (4): The location of the metastasis in the brain. Table -5 shows the number of metastatic lesion.

Figure (2): Duration of presenting symptoms

Table (3): Number of the patients requiring operation according to the primary lesion

Primary site	Surgical Treatment	Non-surgical Treatment
Lung	4	15
Breast	11	0
Bladder	2	0
Lymphatic	3	0
Colon	1	0
Renal	1	0
Skin	0	1

Pathological studies: The specimens taken during the operation of the 23 patients who had operations for the intracranial metastases were preserved in formalin and sent for histological studies to have paraffin sections. Gross pathology. The tumor color was grayish-pink in 15 patients and yellowish-white in 8 patients. The texture was soft in 16 patients and

firm in 7 patients. No calcification could be identified in any patient. Dural attachment of the tumor was noticed in 3 patients, 2 of them were of breast carcinoma origin and one patient of unknown primary. The tumor was vascular in 9 patients, and of mild to moderate vascularity in 5 patients. Necrotic tissue was noticed in 6 patients and cystic component of the tumor was aspirated in 7 patients. The fluid was xanthochromic.

Table (4): The location of the metastasis in the brain

Location	No.	%
Parietal	8	32
Fronto parietal	4	16
Parieto -occipital	3	12
Cerebellum (hemisphere)	3	12
Brain stem	2	8
Frontal	2	8
Occipital	1	4
Thalamic	1	4
Cerebellum (vermis)	1	4

Histopathology Adenocarcinoma was the diagnosis in 13 patients (56.52%), of moderate differentiation and show papillary formation in 2 patients. The Histopathological diagnosis in 7 patients (30.43%) was undifferentiated carcinoma. Squamous cell carcinoma was the diagnosis in 3 patients (13.04%).

Table (5): The number of metastatic lesion

Site of primary	No. of metastatic lesion		Total
	Single	Multiple	
Lung	7	12	19
Breast	8	3	11
Bladder	2	0	2
Lymphatic system	3	0	3
Colon	0	1	1
Skin	0	1	1
Renal	1	0	1
Unknown	5	11	16

Radiotherapy 26 patients (48.14%) who have a Histopathological diagnosis of the primary tumor with a clinical and radiological evidence of the metastatic brain tumor were sent directly for radiotherapy without surgery for the intracranial lesion.

DISCUSSION

70.36% of the patients had age range between 30-59 years compared to 75% of patients between 40-60 years in previous studied[3]. The patients in this study are somewhat younger. Headache was the

presenting symptoms in 40.74% while 50% in other series [24]. Most of the patients with headache responded to medical treatment with steroids indicating that it is due to brain edema. Deterioration in the level of consciousness was the presenting symptoms in 9.26% of the cases that was progressive in 80% of them and 80% of them have a single metastatic brain tumor and supratentorial in all of those patients.

The Duration of the presenting symptoms was less than 1 month, which is regarded to be sudden. In 50% compared to 18.5% of patients presented within 1 month [3]. This may show the rapid and aggressive growth and behavior of the metastatic brain tumors in this study.

The most common **primary cancer** to metastasize to the brain in this study was from the lung accounting for 35.18% of the patients which is lower than previous reports, 38.1% in Simionescu study[26], 44% in the Sloan-Kettering Cancer Center study[23] and 45% in Chevalier TL et al study[29]. The metastases from breast cancer in this study were found in 20.37% of the patients and this is slightly less than 22.6% in Simionescu[26] but is more than the 10% recorded in the Sloan-Kettering Cancer Center study[23], and 5% recorded by Chevalier TL et al study[29]. The metastatic tumors of unknown primary were found in 29.62% of patients which is higher than 11.8% recorded by the Simionescu study[26] and 10% recorded by the Sloan-Kettering Cancer Center study[23].

Ct scan of the brain showed that 53.7% of patients have multiple brain metastases which is comparable to the 51% recorded by Delattre JY et al study[5], but still lower than that reported by studies that depend on the autopsies of the died cancer patients that record the multiplicity in 60-85% of the patients[9]. This percentage will also be higher by the more use of other sophisticated investigations such as MRI, PET and MRS. In comparing the distribution of the metastases in the brain of our study and Delattre JY et al study [5].

In this study about 60% of the metastatic lesions are in and around the parietal lobe compared to 48% in the Delattre JY et al study [5] and this is due to the fact that most of the metastatic emboli reach the brain through the middle cerebral artery and its branches. The CT scan results of our study showed that 63.15% of the metastases from lung origin were multiple; while for the metastases of breast origin 72.7% were single the same results were obtained by the Delattre JY et al study [5].

42.6% of the patients were treated surgically for the metastatic brain lesion, which less than that reported

by the Simionescu MD [26]. **Radiotherapy** is still the treatment of choice for many patients with brain metastases[1]. In this study 48.14% of the patients were sent for radiotherapy depending on the Histopathological diagnosis of the primary tumor and the radiological evidence of brain metastasis. In addition, all the patients who had surgery for the intracranial metastasis were also sent for radiotherapy

Histopathological results of the patients who had an operation for the intracranial lesion in our study were: Adenocarcinoma 56.52%, undifferentiated carcinoma 30.43%, and Squamous cell carcinoma 13.04%. These results are somewhat comparable with those of the Chevalier TL et al [29]. Study of 120 patients in which the histological diagnosis was obtained in 86 patients 71.7% and the results were: Adenocarcinoma 44.1%, undifferentiated or small cell carcinoma 30.3%, Squamous cell carcinoma 11.6%, indeterminate malignancy 9.2%, and melanoma 4.6%

CONCLUSION

Metastatic brain tumors are common in Iraq, but the incidence is still less than reported in the developed countries.

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Do early ischemic changes on computed tomography predict the stroke severity and functional outcome in patients with acute ischemic stroke?

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Abstract

Background: Computed Tomography (CT) is available in all stroke centers and can be interpreted by all radiologists and even by trained neurologists. The study aim was to test the association of early ischemic changes (EICs) on initial CT with different variables especially the stroke severity and the functional outcome.

Patients and Methods: Retrospective analysis of 118 patients [aged 70.2 ± 11.9 years (mean \pm SD); 45 % females] with middle cerebral artery (MCA)-stroke treated with intravenous recombinant tissue plasminogen activator (rtPA) at the neurology department of our university hospital May 2004–May 2008.

Results: Out of 118 patients, 52 (44.1 %) showed EICs. Of 52 with EICs: 50 (96 %) developed MCA infarction ($P < 0.001$), 11 (21 %) had altered consciousness ($P = 0.032$), and 20 (38 %) were institutionalized three months after stroke ($P = 0.024$). Similarly patients with EICs sustained larger infarcts (infarct volume 79 cm^3) than patients with no EIC (infarct volume 22 cm^3); $P < 0.001$. The total time between the stroke onset and initiation of thrombolysis therapy was shorter in patients with EICs than in those with no EICs (109 vs. 124 minutes); $P = 0.016$. Excluding the hyperdense middle cerebral artery sign (HMCAS), the difference in the functional outcome in patients with other

EICs was not statistically significant compared with that in patients with no EICs ($P = 0.214$). However, patients with EICs other than HMCAS showed to have more severe stroke (mean NIHSS on admission: 14.5) than those with no EICs (mean NIHSS on admission: 11.5), $P = 0.036$. The difference between the NIHSS at 24 hours' control was also statistically significant when comparing the two groups (11.3 in patients with EICs vs. 6.8 in patients with no EICs), $P = 0.025$.

Conclusion: EIC showed to be associated with severe stroke and poor functional outcome. Excluding HMCAS, other EICs are only associated with development of severe stroke.

Keywords: HMCAS, NIHSS, Outcome, mRS, Thrombolysis, Infarct volume.

INTRODUCTION

Acute ischemic stroke is one of the major causes of mortality, morbidity and functional disability. Intravenous recombinant tissue plasminogen activator (rtPA) is an evidence based therapy of the acute ischemic stroke [1] with therapeutic window which has recently been lengthened to 4.5 hours from the onset of the stroke symptoms [2]. However, thrombolysis therapy is associated with increased risk of symptomatic intracranial hemorrhage which amount to 6.4% within 36 hours after the onset of stroke according

to the National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS) study [1]. Higher rates of intracranial hemorrhage were reported when treatment with tPA were more liberal than the initial recommendations according to NINDS protocol [3].

Computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) play a central role in the management of the stroke. Diffusion weighted images (DWI) and perfusion weighted images (PWI) can further help to identify patients suitable for treatment with rtPA. However, MRI is less available than CT and often means logistic difficulties to handle severely sick stroke patients. Because of

better availability, ease and short examination time, CT is still and is likely to remain the method of choice in the initial workup of stroke with the primary task to exclude intracranial hemorrhage. Early signs of ischemic stroke on CT were systematically reviewed [4] and to be looked for also in the baseline CT. Among these signs are loss of insular ribbon, sulcal effacement, obscuration of lentiform nucleus, loss of gray and white matter differentiation and focal parenchymal hypoattenuation, Figure 1.

Figure (1): (A-D) Axial CT-images of four patients with MCA-stroke showing HMCAS (black arrow head, A), loss of insular ribbon (white arrow, B), Sulcal effacement compared with contralateral side (white arrow heads, A), and parenchymal hypoattenuation (black arrows C, D).

HMCAS is another important sign to be looked for in the initial CT in the acute ischemic stroke. HMCAS has been shown to correlate with poor functional outcome [5].

The aim of this study was to test the association of the EICs with the age, gender, National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) before and after treatment with rtPA, state of consciousness on admission, the occurrence of cerebral infarction and intracerebral hemorrhage, infarct volume, the functional outcome, mortality, and the need for institutionalization following acute ischemic stroke.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This is a retrospective analysis of 118 patients with middle cerebral artery (MCA)-stroke treated with intravenous recombinant tissue plasminogen activator (rtPA) at the specialized stroke unit in the neurology department of our university hospital between May 2004 and May 2008. The mean value

for patient's age was 70.2 ± 11.9 years (mean \pm SD) and range of 30-87 years. 45 % were females.

The following variables have been recorded:

1. Stroke score according to National Institute of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) [6, 7] recorded by a stroke neurologist in all patients at admission and 24 hours following treatment with rtPA. The NIHSS is a 15-item neurologic examination stroke scale used to evaluate the effect of acute cerebral infarction on the levels of consciousness, language, neglect, visual-field loss, extraocular movement, motor strength, ataxia, dysarthria, and sensory loss.
2. The level of consciousness was also reported as reaction level scale (RLS) [8]. For the purpose of analysis of this study the patients were categorized into 2 groups with regard to their level of consciousness: (a) fully conscious (RLS=1), or (b) altered consciousness (RLS \geq 2).
3. All patients were examined with a plain CT of the brain on admission using a multislice CT (SOMATOM Sensation 16, Siemens AG, and Forchheim, Germany). The baseline CT's were evaluated by two readers at two different occasions (one at the time of admission and one at the time of analysis of this study) without knowledge of stroke symptoms or the side affected. Images were evaluated with regard to the occurrence of the following early ischemic changes (EICs): (a) Hyperdense middle cerebral artery sign (HMCAS), (b) insular ribbon sign (c) sulcal effacement, (d) parenchymal hypoattenuation, and (e) obscured white- and the grey matter discrimination.
4. All patients were examined with plain CT 24 hours after treatment with rtPA and evaluated with regard to (a) the occurrence of: cerebral infarction, (b) the occurrence of parenchymal hemorrhage, and (c) measurement of infarct volume. The latter was performed using the "Volume" application at a Leonardo workstation. The evaluating neuroradiologist was blinded to the clinical outcome and the NIHSS score before and after treatment.
5. The functional outcome at 3 months was evaluated by a stroke neurologist according to the modified Rankin Scale (mRS) [9, 10], Table 1.
6. The neurologist who did the evaluation was blinded to the occurrence of EICs at the initial CT and the infarct size on CT 24 hours after treatment. The mRS was given as an absolute value (0-6) for every individual patient. For the purpose of the analysis of this study patients were categorized according to their outcome

into (a) favorable functional outcome (independence) with mRS 0–2, and (b) unfavorable functional outcome; (dependence or death) with mRS 3–6 [11].

7. The patients’ accommodation at three months control was also recorded and categorized into (a) living at home with or without municipal help, or (b) institutionalized.
8. The time between onset of stroke symptom and admission to the emergency room as well as the total time between the onset of stroke symptom and the start of rtPA were recorded for every individual patient.

Statistical analysis: Statistical analysis was performed by means of SPSS 17. Fisher's exact test and/or chi-square test was performed to test the association between EICs and the categorical variables whereas (gender, level of consciousness, posttreatment hemorrhage, death, outcome categories, and need for institutionalization). Mann-Whitney U tests was performed to test the association between EICs and the continuous variables (age, NIHSS, infarct volume, mRS). The statistical significance was set to a P value of ≤0.05.

RESULTS

Out of 118 patients included in the study, 52 (44.1 %) had EICs. Of 52 patients with EICs: 39 showed HMCAS (of which 9 had also other EICs) and 22 had other EICs but no HMCAS, Table 2. The incidence of other variables analyzed in this study is shown in Table 2. HMCAS was the most common EIC found on the plain CT on admission (33.1 %). Among other EICs a combination of more than sign was the most common EIC. The distribution of EICs including HMCAS is shown in Table 3. In total, 88 patients (74.6 %) developed infarction despite treatment with thrombolysis.

Table 1: Modified Rankin Scale (mRS).

Score	
0	No symptoms at all.
1	No significant disability despite symptoms; able to carry out all usual duties and activities.
2	Slight disability; unable to carry out all previous activities, but able to look after own affairs without assistance.
3	Moderate disability; requiring some help, but able to walk without assistance
4	Moderately severe disability; unable to walk without assistance and unable to attend to own bodily needs without assistance.
5	Severe disability; bedridden, incontinent and requiring constant nursing care and attention.
6	Dead

Table (2): shows the incidence of different variables included in this study

	Mean ± SD
Age (years)	70.2 ± 11.9
NIHSS on admission	12.2 ± 5.9
NIHSS 24 at hours control	7.7 ± 7.2
Time to hospital (minutes)	56 ± 30
Time to treatment (minutes)	118 ± 38
Infarct volume (cm ³)	47 ± 68
Functional outcome (mRS)	2.6 ± 1.9
	N (%)
Gender: Females	53 (44.9 %)
Altered consciousness	16 (13.6 %)
EICS, Total	52 (44.1 %)
HMCAS	39 (33.1 %)
Other EICs but no HMCAS	22 (18.6 %)
Infarction at 24 hours CT	88 (74.6 %)
Hemorrhage at 24 hours CT	15 (12.7 %)
Death	11 (9.3)
Favorable prognosis	57 (48.3 %)
Living at home	85 (72 %)
SD : Standard deviation, N: number, (%): percentage among patients of the whole study cohort	

Table 3: shows the incidence of different EICs and the functional outcome in each sign

EIC:	No	Unfavorable outcome
HMCAS	39	27 (69 %)
Insular ribbon sign	3	2 (67 %)
Sulcal effacement	2	2 (100 %)
Parenchymal hypoattenuation	7	4 (57 %)
Obscured white- and the grey discrimination.	4	3 (75 %)
More than 1 EIC	6	3 (50 %)

Of 66 patients whose baseline CT did not show EICs, 38 (58 %) developed infarction within the MCA territory, whereas all but two patients (50 out of 52) with EICs developed MCA infarction (P<0.001), Table 4. Of 52 patients with EICs, 11 (21 %) had altered consciousness compared with 5 patients (8 %) out of 66 patients with no EICs (P=0.032). There was also significant association between EICs and the need for institutionalization after stroke. Of 52 patients with EICs, 20 (38 %) were institutionalized three months after stroke compared with only 13 of 66 patients (20 %) with no EICs (P=0.024), Table 4.

Patients with EICs showed higher NIHSS on admission and at 24 hours control than patients with no EICs (15 on admission and 11 at 24 hours control for patients with EICs compared with 10 and 5, respectively for patients with no EIC); P<0.001, Table 5. Similarly patients with EICs sustained larger infarcts (infarct volume 79 cm³) than patients with no EIC (infarct volume 22 cm³); P<0.001, Table 5. Patients with EICs reached the hospital more rapidly

than patients with no EIC (51 vs. 60 minutes). However, this difference was not statistically significant with P=0.057. The total time between the stroke onset and initiation of thrombolysis therapy was also shorter in patients with EICs than in those with no EICs (109 vs. 124 minutes). This difference was statistically significant with P=0.016, Table 4. 65 % of patients with EICs had unfavorable outcome compared with 41 % of patients with no EICs (P=0.008), Table 4.

Table 4: shows the results of testing the association between EICs and different categorical variables. P-values of the statistically significant differences are written in bold.

	EIC (-)	EIC (+)	P-value
Gender			
Female	33 (50 %)	20 (38 %)	
Male	33 (40 %)	32 (62 %)	0.211
Level of Consciousness			
RLS 1	61 (92 %)	41 (79 %)	
RLS ≥ 2	5 (8 %)	11 (21 %)	0.032
Occurrence of cerebral infarction			
No	28 (42 %)	2 (4 %)	
Yes	38 (58 %)	50 (96 %)	<0.001
Occurrence of parenchymal hemorrhage			
No	64 (97 %)	48 (92 %)	
Yes	2 (3 %)	4 (8 %)	0.403
Outcome			
Favorable	39 (59 %)	18 (35 %)	
Unfavorable	27 (41 %)	34 (65 %)	0.008
Death			
No	60 (91 %)	47 (90 %)	
Yes	6 (9 %)	5 (10 %)	0.992
Post stroke accommodation			
Living home	53 (80 %)	32 (62 %)	
Institutionalized	13 (20 %)	20 (38 %)	0.024

Excluding the HMCAS, the difference in the functional outcome in patients with other EICs was not statistically significant compared with that in patients with no EICs (P=0.214). However, patients with EICs other than HMCAS developed more severe stroke (mean NIHSS on admission: 14.5) than those with no EICs (mean NIHSS on admission: 11.5), P=0.036. The difference between the NIHSS at 24 hours' control was also statistically significant when comparing the two groups (11.3 in patients with EICs vs. 6.8 in patients with no EICs), P=0.025; Figure 2. The occurrence of EIC was not correlated with age or gender (P=0.153, and 0.211, respectively). There was no statistically significant difference in the occurrence of posttreatment cerebral hemorrhage or mortality between patients with EICs and those with no EICs, Table 4 and 5.

Table 5: shows the results of testing the association between the EICs and different continuous variables. P-values of the statistically significant differences are written in bold. CI=Confidence interval.

	Mean (95 % CI)	Median	P-value
Age			
No EIC	72 (70-74)	75	
EIC	68 (64-72)	71	0.153
NIHSS on admission			
No EIC	10 (9-11)	9	
EIC	15 (13-16)	15	<0.001
NIHSS at 24 hours' control			
No EIC	5 (4-6)	3	
EIC	11 (9-13)	12	<0.001
Infarct volume (cm³)			
No EIC	22 (11-32)	3.4	
EIC	79 (57-101)	47.8	<0.001
Time to hospital (minutes)			
No EIC	60 (53-68)	55	
EIC	51 (43-59)	45	0.057
Time to treatment (minutes)			
No EIC	124 (115-133)	118	
EIC	109 (98-120)	100	0.016

Figure 2: Descriptive statistics with box plots showing the NIHSS on admission (below), and NIHSS at 24 hours' control (above) among patients with EICs to the right (labeled: Yes), and among patients with no EICs to the left (labeled: No) of each box plot.

DISCUSSION

This study has shown that patients whose initial pretreatment plain CT showed EICs developed infarction more frequently than those without EICs

despite the fact that patients with EICs reached hospital and received treatment more rapidly than those whose initial CT did not show EICs. These patients sustained larger infarcts, exhibited poor functional outcome and needed institutionalization more frequently. However, the impact of the EICs on the functional outcome after excluding HMCAS was not statistically significant.

The reliability of EIC and their predictive value has been studied thoroughly [4, 5, 12-14]. In our study, the possible association of EICs with a wide range of variables has been comprehensively analyzed in contrast to other published reports studying the association of EICs with single or couple of variables. Some previous reports has shown that EICs were not associated with 3-months outcome [13], while others showed that EICs were associated with stroke severity but not the functional outcome [15]. The prognostic role of EICs has been shown to increase by using semiquantitative estimation of EICs according to ASPECTS [16] or by addition of further imaging modality e.g. Perfusion CT [17] or CT-angiography. The fact that patients with EICs reached hospital earlier than patients with no EICs and had shorter time to the initiation of thrombolysis therapy indicates that the cause of their poor outcome was not dependent on delay in the treatment instigation.

CONCLUSION

EICs are important signs to be looked for on the initial CT of brain of patients with acute ischemic stroke before thrombolysis therapy. It has been shown to be associated with the severity of the stroke and the functional outcome.

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Radiological and Endoscopic Findings of Middle Ear Effusion in Adults

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Abstract

Background: Middle ear effusion in adults, characterized by presence of thin (serous) non purulent fluid in the middle ear space.

Aim: To evaluate the radiological and nasal endoscopic findings of adults with middle ear effusion before and after treatment.

Patients and methods: A prospective study of 54 selected patients with unilateral or bilateral serous otitis media, aged 21-60 years. Clinical assessment was done for all patients, an endoscope examination of the nose and postnasal space, and plain radiographs (of paranasal sinuses and mastoid X-ray). Medical treatment used for 10-14 days. Patient who did not respond to medical treatment, myringotomy and aspiration of middle ear fluid was done. The response to treatment (medical or myringotomy) was evaluated after 2 months by using the same assessment methods.

Results: Rigid endoscope revealed no abnormal signs in the nasal cavities and postnasal space in 46 patients (85%). Occipitontental X-ray views for paranasal sinuses were taken. In the majority of patients (50 patients – 92.5%) there were no abnormalities found. Oblique lateral mastoid X-ray views were taken. 35 patients (65%) had decreased pneumatization of the mastoid air cell system. Thirty nine patients (72 %) did not improved symptomatically following medical treatment alone , 32 patients (82%) of them had decreased pneumatization of the mastoid air cell system while in the 15 patients (28%) who were improved symptomatically following medical treatment alone, 3 patients (20%) of them had decreased pneumatization ($p<0.001$).

Conclusion: Endoscope of the postnasal space is recommended to exclude post nasal space tumors in adults. Mastoid pneumatization was an important screening tool for adult patients with middle ear effusion with some correlation with the severity and extent of affection.

Keywords: Nasal endoscopy, Radiography, Middle ear effusion

INTRODUCTION

Radiographic examination of the mastoid bones in patients with middle ear effusion made by Schullers projections [1] may sometimes reveal occlusion of air cells. Long term regular inflation reduces the amount of effusion in the mastoid [2]. Imaging of nose and paranasal sinuses can be done by plain radiography or CT scan. CT scan is superior to plain radiography for demonstration of detailed anatomy of nose and paranasal sinuses, but the limiting factors for their routine use instead of plain radiographs are the availability of scanning and cost [3]. Nasal endoscopy is now the gold standard by which other visual examinations are judged. Not every patient

require nasal endoscopy, but when the history suggests possible sinusitis endoscopic assessment is recommended even if there is an obvious anatomical abnormality such as a deviated septum. Eustachian dysfunction is one of the conditions where the endoscopy contributes to diagnosis and management. [3].

PATIENTS AND METHODS

A prospective study of 54 patients aged 21-60 years with symptoms of unilateral or bilateral aural fullness and/or pressure, an ear being plugged, or decreased hearing, reports of pain are rare. Clinical assessment was done for all patients included a

history, ENT examination, rigid endoscope examination of the nose and postnasal space, and plain radiographs of paranasal sinuses and mastoid air cells (which were read by same radiologist). Medical treatment used for 10-14 days (oral antibiotic, oral antihistamine, topical nasal decongestant and given advice to auto inflate by using Valsalva's maneuver). Patient who did not respond to medical treatment were subjected to myringotomy and aspiration of middle ear fluid. The response to treatment (medical or myringotomy) was evaluated after 2 months by using the same above mentioned assessment methods.

RESULTS

Naso-endoscopic examination findings: Rigid endoscope of nasal cavities and postnasal space was performed for our 54 patients, no abnormal signs were revealed in 46 patients (85%), while in 8 patients (15%) abnormal signs are revealed ,[6] patients) had septal deviations which were not severe in any case and were of various configurations. The remaining two patients had signs of allergic rhinitis and unilateral sinusitis on the opposite side of serous otitis media, respectively. No patient was found to have abnormal signs in the postnasal space (see figure 1).

Sinus X-ray: Occipitontental X-ray of paranasal sinuses were performed in all 54 patients at presentation. In the majority of patients (50 patients - 92.5%) there were no abnormalities found. In 4

patients (7.5%) abnormal findings were detected. (See figure 2).

Mastoid X-Ray: Oblique lateral mastoid X-ray views were taken for all our 54 patients at presentation. 35 patients (65%) had decreased pneumatization of the mastoid air cell system, while 19 patients (35%) had normal pneumatization of the mastoid air cell system. Decreased pneumatization of mastoid air cell system was correlated with the side of serous otitis media. The majority of the 35 patients with abnormal mastoid X-ray (31 of 32 patients—97%) had bilateral serous otitis media, while the majority of the 19 patients with normal mastoid X-ray (18 of 22 patients—82%) had unilateral serous otitis media.

Chi square = 39.57 p< 0.001 so the difference is significant. (See figure3)

Effects of medical treatment versus mastoid X-ray findings: thirty nine patients (72 %) did not improved symptomatically following medical treatment alone, 32 patients (82%) of them had decreased pneumatization of the mastoid air cell system on their mastoid X-ray, while in the 15 patients who were improved symptomatically following medical treatment alone, 3 patients (20%) of them had decreased pneumatization .chi square=23.5 p< 0.001. so the difference is significant (See figure 4).

Figure 1: Nasoendoscopic findings

Figure 2: Occipitontal X ray Findings

Figure 3: mastoid X ray Findings

Figure 4: Effects of medical therapy on versus Mastoid X ray

DISCUSSION

In this study endoscopic examination of the nose and postnasal space revealed no predisposing factor in these anatomical areas.

The role of sinus pathology in the pathogenesis of secretory otitis media in adults is frequently emphasized but there exists no

unanimous opinion on this issue [4]. Fiklelestein et al, [5] and Chao WY et al [6] were convinced that sinusitis was the main cause of adult serous otitis media in the majority of patients or the main cause of recurrence.

Fiklelestein et, al, [5] concluded that the lymphoid vegetation at the torus tuberosus and the salpingopharyngeal folds lead to obstruction or at least dysfunction of the Eustachian tube and the development of middle ear effusion and they

strongly suggested that every patient presenting with middle ear effusion should be evaluated for sinusitis and visa versa.

In our study we did not find any significant role of sinusitis in causation of serous otitis media in adults. Differences between our results and those of the above studies may be explained by including of pediatric age groups in these studies, as the lymphoid system of the children is more reactive and might contributed to an overestimated role of these factors in the etiology of middle ear effusion.

Dempstev J H and Simpson D C [7] found that biopsy of the nasopharynx in patients without any other evidence of nasopharyngeal malignancy revealed tumor in only 0.4% of patients, They said that if no additional findings are detected on a careful history and clinical examination, and if good view of the nasopharynx can be achieved with mirror or endoscopic examination, then examination and biopsy under general anesthesia is likely to produce a low yield of additional information and the cost effectiveness of the procedure should be seriously questioned.

Gaze M N et al, [8] found that the prevalence of malignancy in patients with serous otitis media with no other suspicious signs was 1.4%. They concluded that examination under general anesthesia and biopsy of the nasopharynx is a cost-effective investigation which continues to be indicated in adult patients with deafness due to serous otitis media.

In this study, the majority of patients (92.5%) had no abnormalities on their sinus X-ray views.

P.M.Robinson [9] had found that 11% of adult patients with serous otitis media had both clinical and radiological evidences of sinusitis and the diagnosis is confirmed by proof puncture of the maxillary antra.

In this study, 65% of patients had decreased pneumatization of the mastoid air cell system with some correlation of the side distribution of this finding with the side of the serous otitis media.

The importance of the mastoid pneumatization had been widely analyzed and proved [10].

Sade and Fuchs [1] found that persons with mastoid pneumatization level of $\leq 6 \text{ cm}^2$ were 18 times more prone to acquire secretory otitis media.

Eugenijus and Lesinskas et, al, [10] found that in adult patients with secretory otitis media, compared with healthy individuals, the mastoid pneumatization level was lower, while in case of unilateral secretory otitis media the pneumatization

of the healthy ears was almost always better (in 92% of cases).

Warren F. Diven et, al, in their study (Hydrolase Activity in Middle Ear Effusions, Effect of Antibiotic Therapy) show that sterilization of the middle ear cleft and elimination of the hydrolytic enzyme activity may be benefits of antimicrobial therapy and prerequisite to the healing of the inflamed mucosa. [11]

In this study, the majority of those patients who did not improve following medical treatment alone (82%) had decreased mastoid pneumatization in reverse to the minority of patients that not improved following medical treatment alone (20%) had decreased mastoid pneumatization ($p < 0.001$). Eugenijus Lesinskas et al, [10] found that though the results of conservative treatment of secretory otitis media in adults were satisfactory, recovery was achieved only in 30.8% of the treated ears with low mastoid pneumatization level and that the mastoid pneumatization level was an important prognostic criteria [1]. We concluded that decreased mastoid pneumatization was a clue to poor outcome of medical treatment, with a cumulative impact with that of the bilateral affection.

CONCLUSION

1. Endoscopy of the post nasal space is recommended to exclude post nasal space tumors in adults.
2. Mastoid pneumatization was an important screening tool for adult patients with middle ear effusion with some correlation with the severity and extent of affection.

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Current Stem Cell Clinical Trials and Research Progress

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Abstract

During the last 15-10 years, the interest in stem cells has been growing exponentially because of their self-renewal abilities and high plasticity. The physiologic function of adult stem cells (ASCs) is maintaining tissue homeostasis through cellular damaged or aged turn over, while embryonic stem cells (ESCs) generate all committed cell type of organism. Researchers try to exploit these properties to treat degenerative pathologies, as neurological disorder (Parkinson, Alzheimer, Ataxias, multiple sclerosis...), musculoskeletal disorder (arthrosis, dystrophy, heart failure...), diabetes, eyes disorder (optical nerve or corneal degeneration...), autoimmune disease, renal failure and cancer. Although initial enthusiasm for them potentiality, SCs therapy tire to develop for several reasons. Firstly, self renewal and plasticity are also properties of cancer cells and the possibility to lose control on transplanted SCs could become the worst side effect obtainable.

Secondly, in case of allergenic graft will avoid immunorejection by the recipient. Finally, to have ESCs is necessary to manipulate and to sacrifice embryos and scientific, but above all catholic, world identify in this stage of develop a human with same rights of a born man. In this review, we report on recent advances on the clinical trial about stem cells (SCs) therapy. Ours intention is to show all stem cells types disposable and them rational employment in medicine, with focus on treatment benefits and side effects.

To give an ethical imprint at the work, we resume the more common clinical practice guidelines in a work track.

Keywords: *Stem cell, Research , Therapies, Progress*

Stem cells

Stem cells are the basic building blocks of the body. SCs are undifferentiated cells capable of self-renewal and differentiation into diverse mature progenies.

Table-1 summarizes stem cell cardinal characteristics [1-12]. SCs play a central role in tissue genesis, regeneration and homeostasis by providing new elements to increase tissue mass during pre- and post-natal growth, and replacing cell loss due to senescence or damage [8, 9].

Natural stem cells

Stem cell begins with the most primitive totipotent stem cell, the zygote, which is the result of the fusion of two germ cells (oocyte and sperm) during the process of fertilization. As a totipotent stem cell, the zygote is able to give rise to both the embryo and the placenta. The “artificial” counterpart of the totipotent zygote is referred to as a clonote and can be created in the laboratory with an experimental approach known as somatic nuclear transfer, involving removal of the nucleus from a somatic cell and its insertion/transfer into an enucleated oocyte [13]. The first blastomers that derive from the first division of the zygote or clonote are still totipotent stem cells. In support of this is the well-known fact that the first blastomers, if separated from each other, can give rise

to two independent embryos [14], as seen in the case of monozygotic siblings. When the blastomers have divided into the 32-cell stage, the embryo is known as a morula. Cells which form the morula have already lost their totipotency and are now pluripotent. The pluripotent stem cell (PSC) is defined as being able to contribute to the development of the embryo but has lost the capacity to form the trophoblast (which gives rise to the placenta). Thus the term PSC refers to the stem cells that contribute to all three germ layers, mesoderm, ectoderm and endoderm, but not to the trophoblast.

During early embryogenesis, the growing morula develops a central cavity and becomes the blastocyst [15]. A fully developed blastocyst contains cells that are precursors for extra-embryonic tissues and a distinct group of cells called the inner cell mass (ICM) [16]. The cells of the ICM are also pluripotent and can give rise to all three germ layers of the developing embryo [17].

Stem cell types

Exist an huge variety of stem cells: from pluripotent ESCs, isolated from inner cell masses (ICMs) of blastocysts, and multipotent umbilical cord stem cells (UCSCs), which appear to derive from amniotic membrane epithelium, to ASCs, localized in specific niches or tissue compartment as bone marrow (BM), brain, skin, eyes, hearth, kidneys, lungs, gastrointestinal tract, pancreas, liver, breast, ovaries, prostate and testis. However, the two basic types of stem cells are: embryonic stem cells that are isolated from the inner cell mass of blastocysts, and adult somatic stem cells that are found in adult tissues [18-20].

Embryonic stem cell lines (ES cell lines) are cultures of cells derived from the epiblast tissue of the inner cell mass (ICM) of a blastocyst or earlier morula stage embryos. A blastocyst is an early stage embryo—approximately four to five days old in humans and consisting of 50–150 cells. Blastocysts are pre-implantation stage embryos approximately 1 week in age depending on species. From the ICMs develop the organism, whereas the surrounding trophectoderm contribute to the placental chorion. ES cells are pluripotent and give rise during development to all derivatives of the three primary germ layers: ectoderm, endoderm and mesoderm. In other words, they can develop into each of the more than 200 cell types of the adult body when given sufficient and necessary stimulation for a specific cell type. They do not contribute to the extra-embryonic membranes or the placenta. Fetal stem cells are primitive cell types found in the organs of fetuses ESCs could be isolated

using physical microdissection or through compliment-mediated immunodissection. The ICM cells are difficult to maintain in culture. To obtain continuous culture derived from ICM cells needs of feeder layer of primary fibroblast cells that synthesize factor able to maintain undifferentiated ESCs. This method requires pretreatment to block replication of feeder layer cells and continuous supply of sustaining cells. ESCs could be maintained in culture for prolonged time (1-2 years), in undifferentiated phenotype and this is an advantage for therapeutic and research applications [12, 21].

Adult stem cells ASCs are cells localized in specific organism niches and help in maintaining homeostasis of the tissue/organs. At the end of embryogenesis, each tissue contains a heterogeneous population of cells at different stages of maturation, including relatively undifferentiated, self-renewing cells, termed adult SCs (ASCs). ASCs have a limited differentiation potential and are responsible for turnover and repair within the tissue of origin. ASCs have been identified in several organs, such as bone marrow (BM), gastrointestinal epithelium, skin, brain, muscle, and liver [11, 22, 23]. The term adult stem cell refers to any cell which is found in a developed organism that has two properties: the ability to divide and create another cell like itself and also divide and create a cell more differentiated than itself. Also known as somatic stem cells and germ line (giving rise to gametes) stem cells, they can be found in children, as well as adults [24, 25]. In adult organisms, stem cells and progenitor cells act as a repair system for the body, replenishing specialized cells, but also maintain the normal turnover of regenerative organs, such as blood, skin, or intestinal tissues. The reciprocal interactions between SCs and their niche influence SC behavior: a complex network of developing signals regulates the balance between quiescence and the dividing state, leading ASCs toward self-renewal or differentiation [26-29].

Researchers found ASCs in BM, heart, kidney, brain, skin, eyes, gastrointestinal tract, breast, ovaries, prostate and testis. ASCs originate during ontogeny and remain in specific area where they stay in quiescent state for variable time. They have a restricted differentiation potential, originating a limited number of distinct cell progenitors. In niches microenvironment reciprocal cell interaction and chemical dialogue between stem cells and stromal cell regulate ASCs self-renewal and differentiation.

Between ASCs different type, more interesting attention have had BMCs, HSCs, adipose tissue-derived

stromal cells (ADSCs) and derived MSCs. MSCs are adult stem cells derived from bone marrow, liver, umbilical cord, placenta, adipose tissue, synovial membrane, amniotic fluid and teeth. They are generally restricted to forming only mesoderm-specific cell types such as adipocytes, osteoblasts, myocytes and chondrocytes, but several MSCs are able to form all three embryonic germ layers. Adipose tissue contain a particular type of MSCs. ASCs display a similar gene expression profile and surface antigen phenotype to bone marrow-derived MSCs, such as CD34 and CD44, acquire a similar fibroblast morphology. Nevertheless, ASCs express also non BM specific marker, such as VCAM-1 and NGFR. Furthermore, ASCs differentiate primarily to mesoderm tissue in vitro and in vivo could repair bone tissue and reconstitute immune system, but also are able to differentiate in endothelial cell and contribute to revascularization of ischemic tissue. HSCs derived prevalently from BM, in particular near endosteal bone surface and sinusoidal endothelium, and in a little part circulate in peripheral blood. The interest for these SCs depends to relatively easy extraction of BM from the donor or less invasive, but less efficacy, stimulation of releasing in peripheral blood after treatment with granulocyte-colony stimulating factor (G-CSF). Identification and isolation of HSCs is possible with antibody anti-CD34, a surface protein that distinguishes SCs from other hematopoietic cells [11, 29].

According to the hierarchical model, long-term SCs (true SCs, extremely rare, with high differentiation potential and proliferative capacity) can give rise to short-term SCs (transit-amplifying or committed progenitors), which in turn are able to differentiate into mature elements providing tissue-specific functions [8,30]. Despite the paradigm of unidirectional cell determination, recent studies have shown that ASCs are endowed with an unexpected plasticity, as circulating adult progenitor cells can differentiate into mature cells of other tissue types [21, 26, 31]. A particularly high degree of plasticity is shown by bone marrow SCs (BM-SCs), which in vivo and in vitro studies have proved to be able to differentiate into a wide range of non-hematopoietic phenotypes [32-35]. It has also been demonstrated that BM-SCs normally circulate in the peripheral blood, and that the number of circulating SCs committed toward neuronal and hepatic differentiation increases following treatment with mobilizing agents [36]. This phenomenon has led to speculation about the existence of BM-derived pluripotent SCs, which could migrate from the peripheral blood into various tissues and contribute to

normal turnover and repair following injury [8, 28, 37]. Several types of stem cells recently identified in adult tissues, mainly bone marrow (BM) or cord blood (CB). These cells possess differentiation potential into cells from more than one germ layer. These cells were described as MSC - mesenchymal stem cells, MAPC - multipotent adult progenitor cells, MIAMI - marrow isolated adult multi-lineage inducible cells or MASC- Multipotent Adult non-hematopoietic stem cells that were detected by different investigators using different experimental strategies.

Umbilical cord stem cells UCSCs are multipotent cells that might generate diverse differentiated cell types, localized in umbilical cord epithelium (UCE, derived from amniotic membrane epithelium) and umbilical cord blood (UCB). If cultured on fibroblast-populated collagen gel, UCE cells can differentiate in keratinocyte-like cells and to generate stratified epithelial structure when grafted onto the back of nude mice. UCB, instead, contains primitive subpopulation of CD34⁺ hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs) and mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), able to differentiate into multiple lineages.

Stem cell research

Although the concept of stem cells was introduced nearly a century ago by Alexander Maximow [38], Modern stem-cell research began in 1963 when Canadian scientists James E Till, Ernest A McCullough and Lou Siminovitch established assays to detect hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs) [2]. Those scientists found HSCs in the bone marrow of mice. In a series of experiments they demonstrated that cells from the bone marrow could reconstitute hematopoietic and hence rescue lethally irradiated animals. Using serial transplantations, they established the self-renewal ability of the original bone marrow cells. When cells from splenic colonies in the first recipients of bone marrow transplants were further transplanted into other animals that had received a lethal dose of irradiation, colonies of white and red blood corpuscles were found in the secondary recipients. On the basis of these experiments, they defined HSCs as cells that have "the abilities of unrestricted self-renewal as well as multi-lineage differentiation" [2]. This discovery marked the beginning of modern-day stem-cell research. Only in recent years have other somatic stem cells been identified in tissues with more limited regenerative capacity [18, 23].

Table (1):Stem cell characteristics	
<p>1-Self-renewal through mitotic cell division. The ability to go through numerous cycles of cell division while maintaining the undifferentiated state. SCs are thought to alternate symmetric and asymmetric divisions, hence maintaining the property of self-renewal [10].</p> <p>2-SCs possess a hierarchy of potentialities: from the totipotency of the zygote and its immediate progeny, to the pluripotency of embryonic SCs (ESCs), and the multi/unipotency of adult SCs (ASCs) [8, 11, 12].</p> <p>Potency - the capacity to differentiate into a diverse range of specialized cell types. Stem cells to be either totipotent or pluripotent.</p> <p>A-Totipotent (omnipotent) stem cells can differentiate into embryonic and extra-embryonic cell types and form complete organism.</p> <p>B-Pluripotent stem cells can differentiate into nearly all cells i.e. cells derived from any of the three germ layers.</p> <p>Multipotent stem cells can differentiate into a number of cells, but only those of a closely related family of cells.</p> <p>Oligopotent stem cells can differentiate into only a few cells, such as lymphoid or myeloid stem cells.</p> <p>Unipotent cells can produce only one cell type, their own, but have the property of self-renewal which distinguishes them from non-stem cells (e.g. muscle stem cells)[1-7].</p>	
In Vitro characteristics	
<p>1-Able in vitro cultures to give rise to more differentiated stem cells committed to cells from all three germ layers.</p> <p>2 Pluripotentiality which is in vivo contribution to blastocyst development. Accordingly, PSC if injected/aggregated with cells from inner cell mass of the blastocyst should be able to give rise to cells from all three germ layers (meso-, endo-, and ecto-derm) including gametes.</p> <p>3- Tetraploid complementation potential: PSC could give rise to a whole embryo. For example if PSC is transduced with gene encoding with green fluorescence protein (GFP) it will give rise to GFP+ chimera (blastocyst complementation) or GFP+ mouse (Tetraploid complementation).</p>	

Disorder	Trials summary
Rheumatoid arthritis (RA)	Snowden et al [54] treated 76 patients with severe RA resistant to conventional therapies with AHST. Treatment in the majority obviated the need for antirheumatic drugs sensitivity. One patient submitted to graft purification and immunosuppression died.
Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is associated with marked reduction of number and proliferative capability of HSCs. CD34+ present an elevate apoptosis rate. AHST reduced the number of apoptotic CD34+ pre-treatment.	50 patients with SLE refractory to standard immunosuppressive therapies and have either organ or life threatening visceral involvement were treated with AHST and were followed for 5 years. About 50% of patients experienced disease-free survive. HSCinfusion ameliorate disease activity, improved serologic marker and either stabilize or reverse organ dysfunction, but is associated to a high relapse rate and mortality remained high (23%)[55]. Traynor et al [56] conducted a single centre trial on AHST transplant in 15 patients with SLE. General outcome was better and only 2 subjects had recurrence of symptoms
Multiple sclerosis (MS) Mezey et al hypothesize that HSC-derived cells could replace damage neurons [60]	76 patients with MS not responding to conventional therapies were treated with AHST. Better results were obtained in patients with secondary progressive MS (SPMS) and less than 40 years old. Cell therapy reduced inflammation in the CNS, 8 cases experienced neurological deterioration during the treatment, 5 patients died of post-operative infections or localized toxicity [57]. Poor effectiveness of AHST was observed on 26 patients with primary progressive MS (PPMS); only one had clinical improvement, 13 subjects remained stable and in 7 patients there was deterioration. 4 subjects showed at MRI new lesions [59].
Systemic sclerosis (SSc) AHST may improve skin flexibility& stabilize pulmonary involvement [61-71]. However, disease progression & treatment complication) are associated to high mortality rates (27%) [72].	57 patients with SSc were treated with HSTC & followed up for more than 6 months. 14 patients achieved complete remission and 32 achieved partial remission, for a period of over 3 years. Some patients were in better clinical condition than before treatment. In a multi-center study on 11 patients, 5 patients showed reactivation of SSc after AHST, but the treatment extended the short life expectancy of patients with severe SS [73]
Crohn's disease	Severe refractory Crohn's disease were treated with cyclophosphamide (CY) and G-CSF and then with AHST. All patients didn't show serious infection toxicity at 2-30 months of follow-up; even they clinically remitted with disappearance of diarrhea, reduction of abdominal pain and activity [74, 75].
Autoimmune thrombocytopenic purpura (AITP)	AITP cases are responsive to high doses of immunosuppressors with myelosuppression risks. HSTC demonstrates to accelerate reestablishment of the hematological parameters while reduce the number of autoimmune cells in the body 12 cases of AITP were treated with AHST. The responses varying from transient response to continuous remission or even death related to transplantation [76]. 14 patients with chronic refractory AITP treated with CY and AHST, 8 obtain a durable response, suggesting that SC accelerated hematological reestablishment [77].
Autoimmune hemolytic anemia (AIHA)	AHST treatment as associated with immunosuppressive therapy could be an effective treatment for AIHA [78, 79].

Disorder	Trials Summary
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<p>Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) . At present, all treatment designed doesn't restore neural cells. Stem cell therapy can be a promising strategy could combine neuroprotection with recover neuromotor function.</p>	<p>Intrathecal injection of selected HSC into spinal zone in 3 patients with severe ALS afforded partial improvement on neurological function, without complication [80]. 7 patients with severe impairment of the lower limb without respiratory complication were treated with spinal injection (T7-T9 level) of ex vivo expanded AHSC extracted from BM. Most of the patients experienced slight and reversible effects, as intercostals pain or dysesthesia, persisting after 2 years follow up. General deceleration in loss of muscular strength in the legs (marked in 4 patients and slight in 2) and in decline of respiratory function (4 patients) were observed [81]. 61 patients with ALS at different stages received SCs extracted from 4- 8 week embryos. Improvement of neurological function was observed in 34% after 2 months mostly in early stage disease cases [82].</p>
<p>Diabetes Mellitus (DM) Type I diabetes SC transplantation could rehabilitate pancreatic islets and reintroduce physiological secretion of human insulin. Allogenic islet transplantation (AIT) has also been tried [85].</p>	<p>15 patients with newly diagnosed type 1 DM (aged 14-31 years) were treated with AHST. Culture-negative bilateral pneumonia was observed in 1 patient and late endocrine dysfunction in 2 others). AHST improved β-cells function in all but 1 patient and induced prolonged (18.8 months) mean insulin independence in the majority of the subjects [83]. 1 month after single transplantation of pancreatic islets from non-heart-beating donors or a living donor, 6 patients with DM showed metabolic stability, sufficient to avoid life-threatening severe hypoglycemia and prevent or delay the progress of secondary complication of diabetes [84]. An interesting study transplant a combination of different stem cell type in insulinopenic DM patients. 5 subjects were submitted to allotropic human adipose-tissue-derived, insulin-making mesenchymal stem cells (h-AD-MSC) transfusion with unfractionated cultured bone marrow. In all patients, insulin requirements decreased (from 30% to 50%) and serum c-peptide levels increased (from 4- to 26-fold) with a mean follow up of 2.9 months. The practice was safety and no side effects appear during follow up [86].</p>
<p>Spinal cord lesions</p>	<p>In a Korean phase I/II clinical trial, 35 complete spinal cord injury patients were divided in 2 groups to compare the effects of autologous BMC transplantation after GM-CSF stimulation. Furthermore, to evaluate if efficacy of transplantation correlated with time of injection after the trauma, BMCs-treating group was distributed in three subgroups: acute (<2weeks), subacute (2-8weeks) and chronic (>8 weeks). No significant neuropathic pain was observed. About 30% of acute and subacute treatment groups showed neurological improvements passing to ASIA A score to B or C [96].</p>

Disorder	Trails Summary
<p>Parkinson's disease (PD) characterized by the selective and gradual loss of nigrostriatal dopamine-containing neurons loss of pigmented dopamine-secreting (dopaminergic) cells in the pars compacta region of the substantia nigra. [87, 88].</p>	<p>6 patients with PD received implants of human embryonic mesencephalic tissue unilaterally in the striatum. Every patient was previously engrafted with tissue from 4 to 8 donors into the putamen (4 patients) or the putamen plus the caudate nucleus (1 patient) on the other side. Dopa level increased after 12-18 months. After the second graft, 2 patients exhibited marked improvements, as virtual disappear of 'on-off' fluctuations, increase speed movement and L-dopa reduction. The improvement in 1 patient was moderate. 2 patients experienced worsening [89]. 6 patients with advanced PD were treated with bilateral fetal nigral transplantation from donors aged 6.5 to 9 weeks after conception. Surgery complications were mild and transient. Treatment was safe & associated with significant improvements of daily living activities and motor function [90]. 5 patients with PD were transplanted bilaterally into the putamen and caudate nucleus with human embryonic mesencephalic tissue from donors. In the second postoperative year, mean daily L-dopa uptake was decreased by 54% and UPDRS score in 'off' phase was decreased by a mean of 40%. Dopa detection with PET showed a mean 61% increase in the putamen, and 24% increase in the caudate nucleus, compared with preoperative values [91]. A double-blind randomly trial compared transplant of cultured mesencephalic tissue derived from embryos with sham surgery. In 17 of the 20 patients fiber outgrowth from the implanted neurons, as indicated by an increase in F-fluorodopa uptake on PET or postmortem examination. However improvements of first year, dystonia and dyskinesias recurred in 15% of the patients who received transplants [92]. An American double-blind trial compared fetal nigral transplantation with placebo. 34 patients with PD were treated and followed for 24 month. There was no significant treatment effect. Although striatal fluorodopa uptake increased, 56% of transplanted patients developed dyskinesia that persisted after dopaminergic medication [93].</p>
<p>Spinal cord lesions There is no cure for spinal trauma. However, interesting results were obtained with stem cells transplantation [87].</p>	<p>7 patients with spinal cord injury (American Spinal Injury Association [ASIA] class A) transplanted with olfactory mucosa autograft of stem-like progenitor cells for neural repair. After grafts, MRI showed partial to moderate filling of lesion sites. 2 patients restored sensation in their bladder, and one of these regained voluntary contraction of anal sphincter. 100% of patients had improvement in ASIA motor scores: mean of 6.3 in upper extremities for 3 tetraplegic subjects and mean of 3.9 in lower extremities for 4 paraplegic subjects. The side effects included transient pain relieved with medication and sensory decrease in one patient, probably caused by difficulty in locating the lesion [94]. Autologous transplantation of olfactory ensheathing cells (OECs) was performed into the spinal cord in 6 patients with complete, thoracic paraplegia, followed for 3 years. 1 patient showed an improvement over 3 segments in light touch and pin prick sensitivity bilaterally, anteriorly and posteriorly [96].</p>

Table-3	
Huntington's disease (HD) Associated with death of projection neurons in the caudate-putamen (striatum) [97].	A patient with HD died 18 months after transplantation of human fetal striatal tissue from cardiovascular disease. Postmortem histological analysis revealed surviving transplanted cells with typical morphology of the developing striatum. No histological evidence of rejection was observed. Fetal neural cells without mutant HD may be able to replace damaged host neurons and reconstitute damaged neuronal connections [98].
Brain Stroke	10 stroke patients received a subarachnoidal injection of cell suspension containing immature nervous and hematopoietic tissue. 6 months after engraftment, functional activity significantly increased in contrast to the control group. No serious side effects were observed [99]. Bang et al randomly allocated 30 patients with infarcts within the middle cerebral arterial territory and neurological deficits into 1 of 3 groups: the MSC group (5 patients) received intravenous infusion of 1×10^8 autologous MSCs, whereas the control group (25 patients) did not receive MSCs. The patients were followed up for 1 year. Outcomes improved in MSC-treated group compared with control group: Barthel index, to evaluate neurological deficits, ($p=0.011, 0.017$ and 0.115 at 3, 6 and 12 months, respectively) and modified Rankin score, to evaluate function, ($p=0.086, 0.171$ and 0.286 at 3, 6 and 12 months, respectively) of MSC patients improved consistently during the follow-up period. No adverse cell-related, serological or imaging-defined effects were observed [100].
Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD)	Autologous transplantation of muscle-derived CD133+ cells was used in in boys with DMD in a 7-month, double-blind trial. SC safety was tested by measuring muscle strength & evaluating muscle structures with MRI and histological analysis. Timed cardiac and pulmonary function tests were secondary outcome measures. No local or systemic side effects were observed in all treated DMD patients. Treated patients had an increased ratio of capillary per muscle fibers with a switch from slow to fast myosin-positive myofibers[101]. 10 boys with DMD & absent dystrophin (age 5-10 years) were implanted with 100 million myoblasts in the anterior tibial muscle of one leg and placebo in the other. Cyclosporine (5 mg/kg/day) was administered for 7 months. Pre and post-implantation (after 1 and 6 months) muscle biopsies were analyzed. Force generation (tetanic tension and maximum voluntary contraction) was measured monthly in a double-blind design. There was increased force generation in both legs of all boys. Using the polymerase chain reaction, evidence of myoblast survival and dystrophin mRNA expression was obtained in 3 patients after 1 month and in 1 patient after 6 months [104].
DMD)	Mendell et al injected 110 million muscle cells donated by fathers or brothers once a month for 6 months to the biceps brachii muscles of one arm of 12 boys with DMD. The opposite arms served as sham-injected controls. Strength was measured by quantitative isometric muscle testing. Six months after the final myoblast transfer, there was no significant difference in muscle strength between arms injected with myoblasts and sham-injected arms. In one patient, 10.3 percent of muscle fibers expressed donor-derived dystrophin after myoblast transfer. Three other patients also had a low level of donor dystrophin (< 1 percent); eight had none [105]. One biceps muscle of 8 patients with DMD was injected at 55 sites with 55 million normal myoblasts from fathers. The other biceps of each patient was injected with a placebo as a control. All patients received cyclophosphamide for immunosuppression for 6 or 12 months. No serious complications were observed. The overall therapeutic efficiency was poor [106]. 5 young boys with DMD were treated with injection of the biceps with myoblasts. At the same time, myoblasts were also injected in the left tibialis anterior (TA) of these patients. The strength developed during maximal static contractions of the elbow flexor and extensor muscles was measured with a Kin-Com dynamometer. No increase in static elbow flexion torque was measured at any time from 2 mo up to 18 mo after the transplantation[107].

Table(4):Cirrhosis trials summary	
9 alcoholic liver cirrhosis patients were treated with infusion of autologous BM derived CD34+ Treatment was well tolerated and no side effects were observed. Serum bilirubin significantly decreased ($p<0.05$) 4, 8, and 12 week post-infusion. Liver enzymes levels improved through the study. The Child-Pugh score (CP; used to assess the prognosis of chronic liver disease) improved in 7 out of 9 patient, while 5 patients had improvement in ascites in imaging[120].	
9 liver cirrhosis cases treated with autologous BM cell infusion Significantly improved Child-Pugh scores were seen at 4 and 24 weeks ($p<0.05$). Alpha-Fetoprotein& proliferating cell nuclear antigen (PCNA) expression in liver biopsy tissue was significantly elevated after ABMI therapy ($p < .05$). No major adverse effects were noted [121].	
10 patients with chronic liver disease received autologous BMCs infusion. All patients were discharged 48 h after BMC infusion. 2 patients developed mild pain at the BM needle puncture site. Bilirubin levels were lower at 1&4 months after treatment than baseline levels . Albumin levels 4 months after BMC infusion (3.73 ± 0.5) were higher than baseline levels (3.47 ± 0.5). International normalized ratio (INR) decreased from 1.48 (SD = 0.23) to 1.43 (SD = 0.23) one month after treatment[122].	
3 patients with large central liver malignancies were treated with intra-portal administration of autologous CD133(+) BMSCs. 2.5-fold increase in mean proliferation rates was noted compared with a 3 patients treated without application of BMSCs. Portovenous application of CD133(+) BMSCs could be a novel therapeutic approach of enhancing and accelerating hepatic regeneration [123].	

Malignancy	
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	Patients with renal cell carcinoma (RCC) treated with reduced intensity conditioning and peripheral blood stem cells and immunosuppression experienced chronic GVHD in 33%. Transplant-related mortality was 16% at one year. Complete (n = 4) or partial (n = 24) responses. Factors associated with survival included chronic GVHD. Patients (n = 17) with chronic GVHD and given DLI had a 2-year survival of 70% [124]. HSCT leads to durable responses in a minority of metastatic RCC patients. Appropriate patient selection is paramount. Anemia and decreased performance status may enable risk stratification [125,126]. Treatment of metastatic RCC with HSCT after conditioning with immunosuppression was associated with a graft-versus-tumor effect [127].
Breast cancer	The use of first-line high-dose chemotherapy (HDC) with AHCT have some effect on overall survival (OS), disease-free survival (DFS) and response rate in patients with metastatic breast cancer responding to induction therapy [128,129].
	Allogeneic SC transplantation (allo-SCT) can induce curative graft-versus-leukemia reactions for hematological malignancies through allogeneic immunity. As the gastrointestinal tract is a target of graft-versus host disease (GvHD), colorectal cancer has been suggested as a candidate for allo-SCT. [130]. Some studies described the feasibility of combination of chemotherapy and SCT for the treatment of ovarian malignancies. [131]

Therapeutic applications

The stem cells isolated from adult tissues are a non-controversial source of stem cells for therapy. They are “plastic” and thus could transdifferentiate into stem cells committed for various non-hematopoietic organs and tissues [39]. Several reports demonstrated the remarkable regenerative potential of hematopoietic stem cells (HSC) in animal models, for example, after heart infarct [40], stroke [41], spinal cord injury [42] and liver damage [43]. However since these first exciting and promising reports, the role of BM-derived HSC in the repair of damaged organs has become controversial [44, 45]. Further experiments with highly purified populations of HSC showed them not to be effective in regenerating damaged heart [46] or brain [47]. The degree of stem cell plasticity and the potential contribution of bone marrow (BM)-, mobilized peripheral blood (mPB)- or cord blood (CB-derived) stem cells to organ regeneration remain unknown as these tissues may contain heterogeneous populations of stem cells [44,48].

Mesenchymal Stem Cells (Multipotent Mesenchymal Stromal Cells)—MSC are

fibroblastic cells that are essential in forming the hematopoietic microenvironment in which HSC grow and differentiate [49]. These cells contribute to the regeneration of mesenchymal tissues (e.g., bone, cartilage, muscle, ligament, tendon, adipose and stroma) [50]. It is likely that MSC may be contaminated by other populations of primitive non-hematopoietic stem cells. This possibility should be considered whenever a “trans-dedifferentiation” of MSC into cells from other germ layers is demonstrated. Because various inconsistencies have come to light in the field of MSC research, the International Society for Cellular Therapy recently recommended avoiding the name of MSC stem cells and changing it to multipotent

mesenchymal stromal cells instead [51]. The phenotype of these cells.

Multipotent Adult Progenitor Cells (MAPC)—MAPC are isolated from BM as well from various adult organs as a population of CD45- GPA-A- adherent cells and they display a similar fibroblastic morphology to MSC. Interestingly MAPC are the only population of BM derived stem cells that, so far as is known, contribute to all three germ layers after injection into a developing blastocyst, indicating their pluripotency [25]. The contribution of MAPC to blastocyst development, however, requires confirmation by other, independent laboratories.

Marrow-isolated adult multi-lineage inducible (MIAMI) cells—This population of cells was isolated from human adult BM by culturing BM MNC in low oxygen tension conditions on fibronectin [52]. MIAMI cells were isolated from the BM of people ranging from 3- to 72-years old. Colonies derived from MIAMI cells expressed several markers for cells from all three germ layers, suggesting that, at least as determined by in vitro assays, they are endowed with pluripotency. However, these cells have not been tested so far for their ability to complete blastocyst development. The potential relationship of these cells to MSC and MAPC described above is not clear, although it is possible that these are overlapping populations of cells identified by slightly different isolation/expansion strategies.

Multipotent Adult Stem Cells (MACS)-These cells express pluripotent-state-specific

transcriptions factors (Oct-4, Nanog and Rex1) and were cloned from human liver, heart and BM-isolated mononuclear cells [53]. MACS display a high telomerase activity and exhibit a wide range of differentiation potential. Again the potential relationship of these cells to MSC, MAPC and MIAMI described above is not clear, although it is possible that these are overlapping populations of cells

identified by slightly different isolation/expansion strategies

STEM CELL CLINICAL TRIALS

Several trials have been conducted on treatment of **Autoimmune diseases and Neurological disorders**. with autologous HSCs transplantation (AHSCT) as summarized in Table-2 and implantation of embryonic and adult SCs as summarized in Table-3 [54-100]. Myoblast transfer has also been tried in muscle dystrophies [101-107]. Fassa set al noted the risk of development post-transplantation autoimmune disease. In 35 patients, one presented autoimmune thyroiditis 11 months

Patients with acute MI received an intracoronary infusion of progenitor cells derive from bone marrow showed at 4 months improvement in LVEF which was significantly greater than in the placebo group At 1 year, intracoronary infusion of BMCs was associated with a reduction in the pre-specified combined clinical endpoint of death, recurrence of Myocardial infarction, and any revascularization procedure (P=0.01) [109]. Patients with previous MI and ejection fraction (EF) $\leq 35\%$ received autologous skeletal myoblast transplantation and bypass surgery. New York Heart Association (NYHA) class improved from 2.5 to 1.8 at 1 month (p=0.004 versus baseline) and EF increased from 24.3 to 31 at M1 (p=0.001 versus baseline) and remained stable thereafter implantation [110]. Patients survived acute MI and underwent to coronary artery by-pass grafting were treated with the isolation of autologous myoblasts from biopsy and them injection, after amplification. LVEF increased from 25% to 40% before the procedure to 29% to 47% during the 4-month visit (p<0.05), and the effects was maintained throughout all the follow-up in some patients [111].

No obvious beneficial effect of and intracoronary transfer of autologous BMCs 4-8 days after percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) in patients with acute MI compared with patients received optimum post-infarction medical treatment. Left-ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) increased by 0.7 percentage points in the control group and 6.7 percentage points in the BMC group (p=0.0026). In transplanted group, enhanced left-ventricular systolic function primarily in myocardial segments adjacent to the infarcted

after transplant and another developed a refractory, acquired hemophilia A which resulted in death 28 months post-transplant [58].

Studies suggested that SC could improve heart function and repair cardiac tissue after myocardial infarction (MI). Patients with MI and left ventricular (LV) dysfunction indicated for coronary surgery treated with myoblast growth from skeletal muscle biopsy experienced no improvement in LV function compared with placebo. However, the high-dose SC treatment was associated with significant LV volumes compare with placebo. No significantly difference of major cardiac adverse events and ventricular arrhythmias was observed between treated groups ad placebo. [108].

area. No augmented risk of adverse clinical events, in-stent re-stenosis, or pro-arrhythmic effects [112].

Ocular surface disease are characterized by persistent epithelial defects, corneal vascularisation, chronic inflammation, scarring and conjunctivalisation, resulting in visual loss. This pathology is associated to limbal stem cell deficiency (LSCD), and consequently the lack of ability to produce new epithelial cells and to restore function. LSCD can be caused by a variety of hereditary or acquired disorders [113].

Treatment of patients with LSCD caused by burns with autologous limbal stem cell obtained by controlateral eye and cultured on fibrin were reported to be successful. Re-epithelialization occurred within the first week. Inflammation and vascularisation regressed within the first 3-4 weeks. By the first month, the corneal surface was covered by a transparent, normal-looking epithelium. At 12-27 months follow-up, corneal surfaces were clinically and cytologically stable. Successful endothelial rejection in central penetrating graft after simultaneous keratolimbal allograft transplantation (KLAT) and penetrating keratoplasty (PKP) using the same donor cornea has also been reported in few patients. Several patients with various ocular disorders Stevens-Johnson syndrome, ectodermal dysplasia, chemical injury, ocular cicatricial pemphigoid, and keratoconjunctivitis treated with limbal allograft transplantation experienced restoration of the corneal epithelium and decreased vascularisation. Corneal opacification was reduced eyes and visual improvement was achieved in several eyes. [114-119].

Cirrhosis is irreversible once it occurs, and treatment generally focuses on preventing progression and complications. In advanced stages of cirrhosis the only feasible option is a liver transplant. An alternative solution for end stage liver failure could be stem cell therapy Table-4 summarized trial results.

Malignancies

Allogenic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation is often used to treat hematological malignancies. The efficacy of this procedure is due to both myeloablative conditioning and graft-versus-leukemia (GVL). Allogenic transplantation has been developed to treat solid tumors, with the expectation that graft-versus-tumor (GVT), like GVL, will have a significant anti-tumor effect. This effect has been demonstrated in renal carcinomas, and with less evidence in breast cancers.

Five patients with malignant ovarian tumors resistant to chemotherapy underwent allogenic transplantation, four from bone marrow, and one from peripheral blood stem cells. All donors were HLA-identical siblings. One patient received a myeloablative conditioning regimen, while the other four received a non-myeloablative regimen. Two patients received donor lymphocyte infusions (DLI). Four of the patients presented with acute or chronic GVHD associated with tumor regression of at least 50%. These tumor regressions were measured by CA-125 levels and CT scans. The fifth patient died of rapid progression just after transplantation. Of the four transplantation survivors, three received a non-myeloablative regimen which did not seem to reduce treatment effectiveness. While it did reduce toxicity, one of these patients died of GVHD after 127 days. DLI was administered to two patients. These infusions seemed to promote GVHD which was able to control disease progression for one patient and had no apparent effect on the other. **Allograft of hematopoietic stem cells might be of interest in ovarian cancer.** The results in one patient also suggest that DLI may be an effective immunotherapy, although doses and timing need to be determined. The number of cases presented is small [132].

Since 1980, 75 patients with **small-cell lung cancer (SCLC)** have been enrolled in four consecutive studies of high-dose chemotherapy using autologous bone marrow transplantation (ABMT) to assist hematological recovery. In the

first study, 25 patients were treated with cyclophosphamide (160-200 mg/kg) as the sole chemotherapy; in the second (26 patients), the cycle of high-dose cyclophosphamide (with or without 800-1,200 mg/m² etoposide) was repeated as induction treatment. In the first study, response was high [14 complete responses (CR), 7 partial responses (PR)] but was not increased by repeating the cycle (15 CR, 8 PR), and survival was slightly worse in the second trial. In the third study, 15 patients were treated with doxorubicin, vincristine and etoposide for two cycles and then with 200 mg/kg cyclophosphamide. Although high-dose cyclophosphamide increased the complete response rate, the additional responses were short-lived. In the final study, an attempt was made to increase the initial CR rate by combination chemotherapy using carboplatin (400-600 mg/m²), etoposide (120 mg/m² x 4) and either high-dose cyclophosphamide (40 mg/kg x 4) or melphalan (140 mg/m²). Although all nine patients responded, none underwent a CR. The long-term survival (up to 7 years) does not appear to be different from that in comparably selected cases treated with conventional chemotherapy[133].

A multi-centric randomized prospective trial was conducted to test whether late intensification chemotherapy would increase the emission rate, the relapse-free survival, and the survival of small-cell lung cancer patients responding to induction chemotherapy. Autologous bone marrow transplantation was used as support to reduce the duration of the aplasia induced by very high-dose chemotherapy. As induction chemotherapy, 101 patients received, during a period of 5 months, a total dosage of 120 mg/m² methotrexate, 4.5 mg/m² vincristine, 1,800 mg/m² cyclophosphamide, 180 mg/m² doxorubicin, 160 mg/m² cisplatin, 750 mg/m² VP-16-213, and 30 Gy prophylactic cranial irradiation. Forty-five patients, selected for their sensitivity to this induction treatment, were randomized to a last cycle of chemotherapy that combined cyclophosphamide, BCNU, and VP-16-213 either at a conventional dosage of 750 mg/m² intravenously (IV), 60 mg/m² IV, and 600 mg/m² orally or alternatively at a very high dosage of 6 g/m² IV, 300 mg/m² IV, and 500 mg/m² IV, respectively. In the late intensification group, the complete remission rate increased from 39% before randomization to 79% after high-dose chemotherapy. Median relapse-free survivals after randomization for intensified and control chemotherapy groups were 28 and 10 weeks,

respectively ($P = .002$). Median overall survival after induction therapy was 68 weeks for the intensified group compared with 55 weeks for the conventional therapy group ($P = .13$). Four patients died during intensification. Patients in both groups relapsed at the primary site. It can thus be concluded that late intensification chemotherapy for sensitive small-cell lung cancer increases the complete remission rate and resulted in a statistically significant increase in the relapse-free survival. However, since relapse occurred at the primary site and toxicity was high, overall survival was not significantly improved[134].

To determine progression-free survival (PFS) and overall long-term survival for limited-stage small-cell lung cancer (SCLC) patients aged 60 years or younger who respond to first-line chemotherapy followed by high-dose combination alkylating agents (cyclophosphamide 5,625 mg/m², cisplatin 165 mg/m², and carmustine 480 mg/m²) with hematologic stem cell support and chest and prophylactic cranial radiotherapy. Patients were selected on the basis of their continued response to first-line therapy, their relative lack of significant co-morbidity, and their ability to obtain financial clearance. Of 36 patients with stage III SCLC, nine patients (25%) had achieved a complete response (CR), 20 had achieved a near-CR, and seven had achieved a partial response before undergoing high-dose therapy. Toxicity included three deaths (8%). For all patients, the median PFS was 21 months. The 2- and 5-year survival rates after dose intensification were 53% (95% confidence interval [CI], 39% to 72%), and 41% (95% CI, 28% to 61%). Of the 29 patients who were in or near CR before undergoing high-dose therapy, 14 remain continuously progression-free a median of 61 months (range, 40 to 139 months) after high-dose therapy. Actuarial 2- and 5-year PFS rates were 57% (95% CI, 41% to 79%) and 53% (95% CI, 38% to 76%). By multivariate analysis, short intensive induction chemotherapy was associated with favorable outcome ($P < .05$)[135].

Combined-modality treatment for limited-disease small cell lung cancer using conventional chemotherapy and chest irradiation achieves high response rates, but most patients relapse over a period of 12 to 16 months. To improve current results, we performed a phase II trial including high-dose chemotherapy and peripheral blood progenitor cell transplantation (PBPCT) as part of an early intensification strategy after two cycles of induction therapy. Moreover, to reduce the risk of local recurrence, the protocol

included surgical resection in stages I to IIIA patients as well as chest irradiation. Between January 1991 and July 1994, 16 consecutive patients (median age, 50 years; age range, 30 to 59 years) were treated in this single-center trial. The patients received two cycles of conventional chemotherapy consisting of etoposide 500 mg/m², ifosfamide 4 g/m², cisplatin 50 mg/m², and epirubicin 50 mg/m² plus granulocyte colony-stimulating factor 5 microg/kg at a 3-week interval, followed by PBPCT collection and subsequent high-dose etoposide 1,500 mg/m², ifosfamide 12 g/m², carboplatin 750 mg/m², and epirubicin 150 mg/m² with PBPCT. The duration of the entire chemotherapy program was 9 weeks. Six of 10 patients in stages I to IIIA and one of six patients in stage IIIB received adjuvant surgery before high-dose chemotherapy, followed by thoracic (50 Gy) and prophylactic (30 Gy) cranial irradiation. Hematopoietic reconstitution after high-dose chemotherapy occurred within 11 days (range, 9 to 17 days) for both neutrophils ($>0.5 \times 10^9/L$) and platelets ($>20 \times 10^9/L$). Oral mucositis (World Health Organization grade 2 to 4) was the predominant nonhematologic toxicity, which was observed in 12 of 16 patients. One patient developed neutropenic septicemia with fatal multi-organ failure. At a median follow-up of 44 months (range, 32 to 77 months) after PBPCT, nine patients are alive and well, resulting in a disease-free and overall survival rate of 56.3% \pm 12.4%. The median overall survival has not yet been achieved. None of the patients who had surgery relapsed or died after therapy. All relapses occurred within the first 12 months after PBPCT. Patients in stages I to IIIA (10 patients) had a 70% \pm 14% overall survival rate at 4 years, while patients in stage IIIB (six patients) had a 33% \pm 19% survival rate at 4 years, with a median survival of 17 months post transplant. These data demonstrate that a multi-modality treatment including early high-dose chemotherapy with PBPCT may lead to a prolonged disease-free survival in the majority of patients. A randomized phase III study has now been initiated to prospectively investigate the role of high-dose chemotherapy, surgery, and chest irradiation in the multidisciplinary approach to limited-disease small cell lung cancer[136].

A phase I-II trial assessed the feasibility and activity of a combination chemotherapy regimen with etoposide, ifosfamide, cisplatin or carboplatin, and epirubicin in limited-disease (LD, stages I-IIIB) and extensive-stage (ED, stage IV) small-cell lung cancer (SCLC). Standard-dose chemotherapy (SDC)

consisting of etoposide (500 mg/m²), ifosfamide (4000 mg/m²), cisplatin (50 mg/m²) and epirubicin (50 mg/m²) (VIP-E), followed by granulocyte colony-stimulating factor (G-CSF), was given to 100 patients with SCLC. Thirty patients with qualifying responses to VIP-E proceeded to high-dose chemotherapy (HDC) with autologous peripheral blood stem-cell transplantation (PBSCT) after etoposide (1,500 mg/m²), ifosfamide (12,000 mg/m²), carboplatin (750 mg/m²) and epirubicin (150 mg/m²) (VIC-E) conditioning. For standard-dose vip-e: ninety-seven patients were evaluable for response. The objective response rate was 81% in LD SCLC (33% CR, 48% PR; excluding patients in surgical CR) and 77% in ED SCLC (18% CR, 58% PR). The treatment-related mortality (TRM) of SDC was 2%. Two additional patients in CR from their SCLC developed secondary non-small-cell lung cancers (NSCLC), and both were cured by surgery. The median survival was 19 months in LD SCLC and 6 months in ED SCLC. The five-year survivals were 36% in LD and 0% in ED SCLC. For high-dose vic-e: HDC was feasible in 16% of ED-, and 58% of LD-patients. All HDC patients (n = 30) improved or maintained prior responses. Four patients died of early treatment-related complications (TRM 13%). Two additional patients in CR from their SCLC developed secondary malignancies (esophageal cancer, secondary chronic myelogenous leukemia). The median survivals were 26 months in LD SCLC, and 8 months in ED SCLC. The five-year survival was 50% in LD and 0% in ED SCLC[137].

To determine the feasibility and safety of multiple sequential courses of high-dose chemotherapy and peripheral-blood progenitor cells (PBPCs) administered in a multicenter setting to patients with small-cell lung cancer. Sixty-nine patients (limited disease, n = 30; extensive disease, n = 39) treated at 15 European centers were scheduled to receive three courses of high-dose chemotherapy with ifosfamide 10 g/m², carboplatin 1200 mg/m², and etoposide 1200 mg/m² (ICE) divided over 4 days at 28-day intervals. PBPCs were harvested before treatment and mobilized with epirubicin 150 mg/m² administered via an intravenous bolus divided over 2 days and filgrastim 5 microg/kg/d administered subcutaneously. The performed leukaphereses (one to five per patient) yielded a median of 16.6 x 10⁶/kg (range, 1.0 to 96.6 x 10⁶/kg) CD34(+) cells, which was sufficient for three re-infusions. Fifty patients (72%) completed the treatment according to schedule. Nine patients completed two courses, and six patients completed

one course of treatment. The increase in dose-intensity was 290% that of a standard ICE regimen. The median duration of myelosuppression was similar between courses, namely 4 days (range, 1 to 12 days) for leukocytes less than 0.5 x 10⁹/L and 4 days (range, 0 to 22 days) for thrombocytes less than 20 x 10⁹/L. Febrile neutropenia developed in 66% of courses, severe diarrhea in 14%, mucositis in 10%, and nausea and vomiting in 21% of courses. There were six cases of toxic death (9%), most of which occurred in the first year of accrual and thus were attributable to the learning curve. The antitumor effect of the regimen was reflected in an 86% remission rate (95% confidence interval [CI], 74% to 93%), with 51% of patients achieving a complete response (95% CI, 38% to 63%). Median overall survival was 18 months for patients with limited disease and 11 months for patients with extensive disease [138].

RISKS OF STEM CELL THERAPY

Hepatic veno-occlusive disease or veno-occlusive disease (VOD) is one of the most frequent complications after stem cell transplantation. It is a complication of high-dose chemotherapy given before a bone marrow transplant. [139]. Respiratory complications are other typology of side effect. In fact, the major limitations to the successful use of HSC transplantation include respiratory complications and graft versus host disease. Lung dysfunction occurs in up to 50% of subjects after HSC transplantation, and pulmonary complications are among the most common causes of morbidity and mortality after this procedure.

Obliterative bronchiolitis (OB) is a multifactorial process involving both alloimmunologic and non-alloimmunologic reactions. Usually OB develops as a late complication (after the first 100 days) of HSC transplantation. Clinical data suggest that non-alloimmunologic inflammatory conditions such as viral infections, recurrent aspiration, and conditioning chemo-radiotherapy may also play a role in the pathogenesis of OB after HSC transplantation. [140,141].

Bronchiolitis obliterans organizing pneumonia (BOOP). Although the pathogenesis of BOOP following HSCT is poorly understood, involvement of an allo-immunologic reaction has been again considered. In animal studies, BOOP develops following infection with reovirus, and a significant role for T cells and Th1-derived cytokines, including interferon- α , was

implicated in the development of disease [142,143]. In other non-HSCT settings BOOP has been seen in association with infection, drugs, radiation therapy, and a number of connective tissue disorders [144] A trial where 33 patients randomly submitted to either AHSCT or selected CD34⁺ didn't show any advantage with antigen selection, but confirm immunomodulatory action of HSC in joint microenvironment [145].

EBMT registry identified 34 patients with severe JIA treated with to BM harvest, positive stem cells selection, T cells depletion and re-infusion. 18 patients had a complete remission of JIA, 6 patients had a partial remission while 7 hadn't remission. 70% of subjects develop at least one infection, mainly during the aplastic period. 3 patients died after transplantation of infections complications. The protocol could be improved by prophylactic administration of antiviral drugs and intravenous immunoglobulin until immune system return competent [146].

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The use of Anti-Neoplastic Action of a Phenothiazine (Promethazine) in Low Dose in Cancer

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Keywords: Promethazine, Cancer, Anti-Neoplastic action

It has been known for several hundred years that certain conditions, identified late in the 19th century as Gram negative infections, can cause tumour regression and, on occasion, remission[1]. A small number of cancers responding to attacks of erysipelas have been reviewed. Mild attacks tended to produce temporary regression. The more virulent the infection, the more favourable the prognosis; in some instances tumours disappeared over a period of a few weeks [2]. The active principle, endotoxin, was isolated and characterised seventy years ago [3, 4]. Endotoxin causes haemorrhagic necrosis in transplanted tumours [3, 4], as typically described in the S180 (Crocker) sarcoma [5]. Endotoxin derived from a strain of *E. coli* totally uncoupled oxidative phosphorylation in the S180 sarcoma within 4hr of administration[6,7]. Whereas the adenosine triphosphate level within the same tumour plummeted by 99% 24hr after endotoxin, the value in the liver did not alter significantly[8].

The first clinical applications of phenothiazines date from sixty years ago [9, 10]. Phenothiazines, of which fifty-nine were listed in 1989 [11], soon found a variety of applications, namely, as antipsychotics, antihistaminics, anti-emetics, anticholinergics and tranquillizers [12]. Anti-emetic properties were soon exploited as adjuncts to conventional cancer treatment [13].

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With such a multiplicity of uses, early reports of anti-cancer activity in chlorpromazine (CPZ), comprising prolongation of survival times in tumour-bearing animals[14], selective disruption of high-energy phosphate production in isolated tumour mitochondria [15,16] and tumour regression in man[17-20], were hardly surprising. What is so striking is that CPZ targets mitochondria [15, 16] in exactly the same manner as endotoxin [6, 7]. The foregoing properties [13-20] have been reviewed [21-24] together with mechanism of action [21, 25]. Of 297 psychotropic substances examined for anti-cancer activity in a mouse leukaemia screen, six phenothiazines and five phenothiazine isosteres were among the sixteen agents found to be active[25], but the effects were judged too feeble for clinical exploitation. Thirteen Japanese patents for phenothiazines as anti-cancer drugs were listed in *Chemical Abstracts* between 1973 and 1986[23]. The isostere clomipramine decreased metastatic spread in the Lewis lung carcinoma [26].

Three additional properties of phenothiazines associated with anti-neoplastic activity were later described [22, 27-29]. All are shared with tamoxifen [30], and include calmodulin antagonism (see 22, 27 for reviews), inhibition of protein kinase C [28], and reversal of multidrug resistance (MDR) [29]. Despite this

impressive body of evidence, which includes anecdotal reports of favourable clinical results with CPZ [17-20, 24]; perazine [20], PMZ [23, 25] and the isostere chlorprothixene [19], the application of the anti-neoplastic properties of phenothiazines and their isosteres to the treatment of cancer remains disregarded. The wholly unexpected development of an irreversible form of drug resistance as a result of intermittent medication, described here for the first time, inconsistency of response, and confusion between the anti-neoplastic effects of this group of agents and orthodox cancer treatments may feature among the principal reasons for neglect.

A call [18] for clinical trials of cancer therapy with CPZ made as far back as 1972 continues to be ignored. Around the same time Mahmud treated inoperable pancreatic carcinoma with intravenous PMZ (50mg), then giving calcium gluconate and papaverine by the same route; therapy was continued with oral PMZ (25mg t.i.d.). His three patients survived for at least thirteen years [32]. A rationale for cancer therapy with PMZ, together with preliminary results, appeared in 1996[24]. Greater sensitivities to thioridazine have been recorded in neuroblastoma and glioma cell lines than in non-malignant brain cells and selected neurones [33]. A preliminary study of the effectiveness of clomipramine in the treatment of brain tumours is encouraging [34].

The circumstances in which this pilot study has been conducted have been difficult. Letters to medical practitioners requesting case details consistently went unanswered; in a few instances feedback indicated that enquiry of patients and their families was resented. In consequence the information available has been patchy and basic. The importance of placing the project into a comprehensive historical context has been recognised.

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H1N1 Postmortem Findings and Diagnosis

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Abstract

Swine Flue (H1N1) is the 21st century threat to human population. The aim of this paper is to report the postmortem finding of 4 cases of sudden collapse and death after short history of pyrexia and flue like symptoms. The cases were received as suspected legal cases of death were received within one hour of death and autopsy performed soon. The possibility of swine flue infection was considered and protective measures for the staff were taken. Two of the patients had positive confirmatory laboratory test for H1N1 infection.

Conclusion: proved by gross and microscopic histology study that the H1N1 infection is not a mere bronchopneumonia but it can turn into a fatal hemorrhagic bronchopneumonia.

Keywords: Postmortem, Hemorrhagic bronchopneumonia, H1N1 virus

Four cases were referred to the forensic unit of Mosul by the police and by the emergency department of Al-Jumhuri hospital as suspected death on arrival and legal deaths within a period of 20 days during November 2009. The cases were from different governorate. They were received within the first hour of death. Pre-mortem history from the close relatives who live with the deceased as very suggestive of H1N1 infection. Three cases were previously healthy and one case (case-3) was a child crippled by cerebral palsy (CP) and wide spread muscle atrophy. All of them were single. All were suffering from flue-like symptoms for very short period of time (2-3) days before death with pyrexia and rapid deterioration and exaggeration of chest problem. Two cases (case 3 and 4) were medicated by a nurse the day before death only. They didn't receive any medical supervision. The patients and their relatives considered the illness as simple flue which needs no medical advice. There was no clear family history of flu or other infections in 3 cases.

External examination showed no trauma marks or injuries, no sign of chronic disease or specific illness in all cases.

All four cases had the same gross pathology on postmortem (Acute Hemorrhagic Bronchopneumonia) with different severity.

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Postmortem chest X-ray was performed in 2 cases (cases 03-04) and it was highly consistent with a picture of severe wide spread bronchopneumonia, by the wide spread fluffy cotton wool like appearance of the diseased lung field. Two cases (01, 02) had whole left lung upper lobe involvement with wide spread hemorrhage, one case (02) with wide spread emphysematous bullae scattered all over the lobe surface measuring 1 -3 cm in diameter. Superadded bacterial infection is a serious factor which we couldn't investigate bacteriologically on the lung specimens. It was possible to take lung secretions from only 2 cases (3 and 4) because of lack of preservative. Both cases (3 and 4) were RT-PCR positive for (H1N1). The test was performed in the central public health laboratory of Baghdad. The aim of this paper is to report the postmortem finding of 4 cases of sudden collapse and death after short history of pyrexia and flue like symptoms Table-1.

CONCLUSION

As proved by gross and microscopic histology study that the H1N1 infection is not a mere bronchopneumonia but it can turn into a fatal hemorrhagic bronchopneumonia

Case	History	Postmortem findings
1 17 Year old Female	Chest pain & tightness associated with cough, fever for less than day. Presented to emergency department with severe tachypnea, died on arrival.	Internal gross examination (figure-1): hemorrhagic changes of the left lung (upper lobe) with fibrinous adhesions of the parietal pleura and surface of the lung. Lower lobe was grossly normal, right lung looks grossly normal, pleural fluid was normal in amount. Other viscera all normal grossly examination of the diseased lobe showed Congested lung with large focus of parenchymal hemorrhage.
2 35 year-old man	Died suddenly while taking a bath, following 3 days of pyrexia and flue like illness. He received home medication only for the flue symptoms. He was using dexamethasone for the previous few months (for athletic reasons?).	Internal gross examination of the viscera (figure-2) : hemorrhagic left lung upper lobe with emphysematous bullae all over the surface of the diseased lung ranging in diameter between 1 -3 cm with fibrinous adhesions of the parietal pleura to the lung surface , all other viscera were grossly normal including the right lung and the lower lobe of the left lung. Microscopically, most of the alveoli showed destruction of the alveolar wall but some showed mild to moderate edema with numerous alveolar macrophages and mild Hyperplasia of type II pneumocytes, with congestion of blood vessels, some alveoli showing mild to moderate chronic and acute inflammatory cells infiltrate. The bronchioles showing infiltration by inflammatory cells mostly mature lymphocytes, plasma cells and polymorph neutrophils. The liver showed mild chronic inflammatory infiltrate of the portal tract. Picture is consistent with non-specific inflammation with emphysematous changes of the lung.
3 10 year old child	Pyrexia & flu like symptoms 2 days before death. Received single antibiotic injection by a nurse. Other children in the family also had flue	External examination: debilitated crippled child with wide spread muscle atrophy and bony deformities. CXR (postmortem): opacification of the whole right lung (Figure-4). Internal examination (Figure-3): congested whole middle lobe of the right lung but no clear hemorrhage or adhesions or bullae, other lobes and other lung were normal, other viscera were normal. Lung tissue showed marked edema of the alveoli and numerous alveolar macrophages with mild hyperplasia of the type II pneumocytes, marked diffuse congestion of the blood vessels , some of the alveoli showing hyalinization of the alveolar wall, others showing infiltration by inflammatory cells (mature lymphocytes, plasma cells, polymorph neutrophils), the bronchioles showing marked inflammatory infiltrate, chronic and acute inflammatory cells to a degree that the lumens are occluded by inflammation. Bronchopneumon
4 19 year old man	Pyrexia for 3 days with breathlessness and tight chest associated Received diarrhea. Received unknown medication for chest infection by a village doctor?	External examination shows no trauma, but dehydration signs with whitish froth from mouth .Gross examination of viscera (Figure-5) revealed inflated lungs were extraordinarily with smooth pleural surface; with wide spread hemorrhagic patches, moderate bilateral plural effusion, and other viscera all normal. Gross pathology: Pneumonectomy specimen, 770 Gm, hemorrhagic sub pleural bullae measuring 5.2 cm in largest dimensions. Left lung, pneumonectomy, post-mortem examination: Multiple sections examined and reveal the following pathological changes: Extensive congestion and occupation of the dilated alveoli by mixed inflammatory cells population (lymphocytes, neutrophils, alveolar histiocytes and type II pneumocytes). Type II pneumocytes are increased in number. Hyalinized thickening of alveolar walls with destruction of the bronchioles and focal endothelitis of small blood vessels. The picture is consistent with severe hemorrhagic bronchopneumonia. CXR (postmortem) (Figure-6): wide spread fluffy patches all over both lungs.

Figure (1): A: Lower lobe of left lung (normal),
 B: Fibrinous adhesions of the pleura,
 C: Left lung (upper hemorrhagic lobe).
Figure (2): A: Upper lobe of left lung,
 B: Apex of upper lobe of left lung.
Figure (3): A: Right lung (visceral surface
 of middle lobe) B: Right lung: costal
 surface of middle lobe

Figure(4): CXR (postmortem) of case 4 showed opacification of the whole right lung

Figure (5): A (both lungs visceral surfaces) B (both lungs costal surfaces)

Figure 6: Chest X-ray (PM) wide spread fluffy patches all over both lungs.

Pediatric Surgery in Al-Qadisiya : Report of Rare Cases

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to report 3 rare pediatric surgery cases observed in Al-Qadisiya:

1. A rare atypical parasitic rachiopagus rachipagus parasitic twin,
2. Urethral diverticula and anterior urethral valves
3. Inguinal hernia with a persistent Mullerian duct syndrome and transverse testicular ectopia

Keywords: *Pediatric surgery, Rare cases*

CASE (1)

Asymmetric and parasitic conjoined twins are rarer anomalies of monochorionic monoamniotic twins, consisting of an incomplete twin attached to the fully developed body of the co-twin. Prenatal diagnosis of conjoined twins with B-mode ultrasound (US), computed tomography (CT) [3], three dimensional US, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has been reported [1-6]. Parasitic conjoined twin diagnosed in utero has been reported in few cases previously [7, 8]. But literature review failed to identify a case of pygopagus tetrapus parasitic twin detected in utero. Afetus-in-fetu is an encapsulated, pedunculated vertebrate tumor. It represents a malformed monozygotic, monochorionic diamniotic parasitic twin included in a host (or auto-site) twin. Characteristically the fetus-in-fetu complex will be composed of a fibrous membrane (equivalent to the chorioamniotic complex) that contains some fluid (equivalent to the amniotic fluid) and a fetus suspended by a cord or pedicle. The presence of a rudimentary spinal architecture is used to differentiate a fetus-in-fetu from a teratoma, since teratomas are not supposed to develop through the primitive streak stage [9-15] days).

Several cases have been formally recognized by some as fetus-in-fetus, while categorically rejected by others. Seven cases have been detected in utero. An estimated frequency of 0.02:10,000 is commonly reported in the literature, but this number is based on the unsubstantiated assumption that fetus-in-fetu represents 5% of conjoined twins. Further, the current trend is to consider that fetus-in-fetu does not represent a form of conjoined twins. The male-to-female ratio in the 39 reports that we reviewed was M1.3:F1. This is in contrast with conjoined twin, which occurs predominantly in girls [9-15].

Case report: A baby was born at 34 weeks to 30-year-old primgravid woman with history of 10 years secondary infertility. She was receiving clomiphene citrate tablets. Healthy, non-consanguineous parents, without maternal illness, drug intake, or familial congenital abnormalities or twinning. Previous ultrasonographic examination reported polyhydramnios. Birth done by caesarean section, and 2 days later the patient was admitted to the Maternity and Child Teaching Hospital –pediatric surgery unit. Birth weight was 3.600 g, length was 45 cm, and cephalic circumference was 32 cm. Apgar scores were 7 and 8 at one and 5 minutes, respectively. Characteristics of the membranes and placenta were unavailable. Upper trunk external appearance was normal. There were 3 upper limbs

(one with three fingers attached to the parasitic mass in thoracolumbar at the back) and 2 lower limbs. The parasitic vertebral column showed a well-differentiated spinal cord and, beside it, a third morphologic left kidney with adrenal gland and ureter of indefinable destination on ultrasound. Parasite structures were vascularized via major anastomosis. And regarding the precise history of the mother, a 30-year-old multigravid woman referred to maternal unit for targeted ultrasonography due to polyhydramnios at 28th week of gestation. The woman had no family history of congenital anomalies and had taken clomiphene tab. during her pregnancy. Her obstetric background consisted of two first trimester abortions. Screening for gestational diabetes was negative. Sonographic examination initially revealed a single fetus and polyhydramnios with amniotic fluid index 30 cm. The fetus appeared normal except a mass at sacrum. Further evaluation with US identified that the fetus has normal apparent single head, spine, thorax, abdomen, two upper and two lower normal limbs, and two relatively well developed rudimentary upper limbs at thoracolumbar area .

Detailed anomaly scanning of the autosite with ultrasound revealed normal findings except the parasite at thoracolumbar area region. Upper and lower limbs of the autosite were moving freely but no movement was detected at the parasite. Short and deformed long bones were also present in the parasitic limbs. A Cesarean section was performed at 34th week of gestation and a live male infant weighing 3600 g was delivered. The placenta was single and normal. The infant appeared to be normal except the parasitic co-twin (Figure 1).

The infant was further evaluated with US and MRI that confirmed that parasitic conjoined twin had relation with the spinal cord at T 7 to L 2 thoracolumbar vertebrae. One week after birth, the infant underwent surgery. The parasitic upper limbs were totally excised with whole the parasitic tissue [figure-2].

Post-operative period was uneventful and the newborn was discharged as healthy. Post-natal and post operative follows-up were normal at three-month-old. Pathologic examination demonstrated skin covered parasitic body; Parasite parts included incomplete upper limb, hemipelvis, thoracolumbar vertebral column, spinal cord, and one kidney with ureter, small bowel, lung tissue and adrenal gland. At three month of age the infant developed hydrocephaly the C-T scan revealed evidence of ventriculomegaly the parents were counseled again by pediatric surgeon and neurosurgeon for V-P shunt which was done at Al-Najaf Teaching Hospital \ neurosurgical unit , post operative follows-up were normal at 1.5 year-old.

Conjoined twinning is a fascinating congenital abnormality with devastating consequences for the twins and the family. Conjoined twins develop from a single fertilized ovum and result from failure of the division of the embryonic disk until after day 13 from conception. Seventy percent of conjoined twins are female, and 40% are stillborn [16]. Conjoined twins are categorized based on the region of connection. In one attempt to universalize the current nomenclature of conjoint twins, Spencer [17] proposed a simple and logical new classification based on the theoretical site of union. Parasitic twins are rare form of conjoined twins and are consisting of an incomplete twin (parasite) attached to the fully developed body of the co-twin (autosite). It is classified [18] as (1) an externally attached parasitic twin, (2) an enclosed fetus in fetu, (3) an internal teratoma, or (4) an acardiac connected via the placenta. Prenatal recognition of conjoined twins and precise characterization of the malformations are required for optimal obstetric management. Currently, sonographic diagnosis of conjoined twins may be straightforward if fusion of fetal parts is obvious. In utero diagnosis of conjoined twins was reported previously [19-22]. But prenatal diagnosis of parasitic conjoined twins is relatively difficult because of changing fetal positions and the rarity of these abnormalities as with any rare medical entity. Parasitic conjoined twins identified at birth were reported [23-26], but so far two cases diagnosed *in utero* with US and MRI were presented in the literature [27, 28]. Polyhydramnios is a secondary finding that occurs in 50% of conjoined twin pregnancies [29, 30]. Hence the site and extent of twin fusion are variable; a careful evaluation with US may help to identify parasitic conjoined twins *in utero*. Differential diagnosis includes parasitic twin, fetus in fetu (internal parasite) and teratoma. Presence of rudimentary lower limbs with foot in our case suggested the parasitic conjoined twin. The prognosis depends on the site and extent of twin fusion. In our case, during routine prenatal examination, the woman had three US scanning and had no abnormal findings noted until she was referred for polyhydramnios at 34 weeks' gestation, suggesting that prenatal diagnosis is relatively difficult. Rarity of the condition may lead to misdiagnosis or undiagnosed. Although our case was referred for detailed US due to polyhydramnios, its etiology is not clear and parasitic site might have vascular malformation that may lead to increased volume of circulation, like in the cases having teratoma and arteriovenous malformations. Hyperdynamic cardiac activity and increased cardiac output might caused polyhydramnios in our case. Even though it is rare, a parasitic conjoined twin should be considered in the differential diagnosis when polyhydramnios is present. Prenatal diagnosis

in our case helped in counseling with the parents and in management of the case and delivery.

Figure-1

Rachipagus parasites (most consisting only of supernumerary limbs) show vertebral union above the sacrum with neural or bony connections to the autosite [31, 32]. Monitoring must be continued postoperatively in the ICU. Because surgery is prolonged. Fluid and electrolyte balance should be closely monitored. Sepsis is a major cause of morbidity and mortality, and precautions must be exercised, particularly when large skin defects are present.

Figure (2): postoperative, complete excision of the mass, limb with tree digits, tissues of liver with small gallbladder, small bowel and spleen.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, rachipagus parasitic twin is a rare form of conjoined twin with a favorable outcome. Obstetrician should be aware of the existence of a parasitic twin during prenatal examinations and the importance of the differential diagnosis of parasite and teratoma. Delivery at a tertiary center is highly suggested for optimal neonatal intensive care and pediatric surgical intervention.

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CASE (2)

The persistent Mullerian (paramesonephric) duct, or the uterine hernia, syndrome is a rare disorder of male sexual development characterized by the persistence of the uterus, fallopian tubes and upper vagina in otherwise normally virilized boys. Despite the normal male genotype and the subsequent normal development of fetal testis, Mullerian structures do not regress due to failure in production or in response to the anti-Mullerian hormone. Since the secretion and action of testosterone is not affected, the Wolffian (mesonephric) duct derivatives and the external genitalia of the fetus progress in the normal male direction. An intersex condition is, therefore, not usually suspected but the malformation is incidentally detected during operative treatment of associated abnormalities such as inguinal hernia and undescended testis, generally in the first year of life. The syndrome was first described by Nilson in

1939 as hernia uteri inguinalis [1]. Subsequently, approximately 150 cases have been reported and a familial association has been found in some cases [2, 3].

The diagnosis of persistent Mullerian duct syndrome is often established when a uterus and/or fallopian tube is found along with undescended testis in a genotypically and phenotypically normal male child during repair of inguinal hernia. Anatomic variants include fallopian tube or uterus within the inguinal canal, testis and tubes in a hernia sac or bilateral cryptorchidism with the testes embedded in the broad ligaments. The vas deferens is intimately adhered to the uterus lateral wall. Initial procedure consists of hernia repair, replacement of structure within pelvis and karyotype. After diagnosis follow-up management has been controversial. A few suggest partial removal of the uterus (leaving vas deferens intact on a thin pedicle of myometrium) and fallopian tubes with testicular fixation. Most content that surgical excision of persistent MDS structure may result in ischemic or traumatic damage to the vasa deferentia and testes and optimal management is orchiopexy leaving the uterus and fallopian tubes in situ. The testes in MDS are at risk of malignant degeneration [4, 5, 6, 7]. The relative risk of testicular tumor is not increased in patients with persistent Mullerian duct syndrome if orchiopexy is performed before two years of age. The observation that most cases of persistent Mullerian duct syndrome are bilateral is noteworthy. Anti-Mullerian hormone is secreted by the Sertoli cells of the fetal testis and acts ipsilaterally. The sensitivity of Mullerian duct to this hormone is present only during the ambisexual stage of the embryonic period. Persistent Mullerian duct syndrome is a rare form of male pseudohermaphroditism, affected subject are, by definition, genotypically (46, XY) and phenotypically male. Affected male may be infertile. It is transmitted as an autosomal recessive trait.

Transverse testicular ectopia (TTE) is one of the rarest forms of testicular ectopia. In this condition, 2 testes are located on one inguinal side and the opposite inguinal canal and scrotum is empty. TTE associated with PMDS is much rarer [8, 9, 10, 11].

A case of PMDS with TTE discovered incidentally during surgery for inguinal hernia and undescended testes in a 1.4 year-old boy is presented with a literature review.

Genetic analysis has shown that around 45% of cases are caused by mutations in the anti-Müllerian hormone gene (AMH; 19p13.3). Mutations

in the gene encoding the AMH receptor (anti-Müllerian hormone receptor, type II, AMHR2; 12q13) are responsible for a further 40% of cases, with around half of these patients carrying the same mutation (a 27 -base pair deletion in exon 10).

Alternative Names: PMDS, Pseudohermaphroditism, Male Internal, Hernia Uteri Inguinale, Persistent Oviduct Syndrome, Female Genital Ducts in otherwise Normal Male, Mullerian Derivatives, Persistent [12,13].

We present a case of Transverse testicular ectopia of the left testis that presented to our pediatric surgery unit at the Maternity and children Teaching hospital with right inguinal hernia and an impalpable testis in the left scrotum. His parents were not related, and there was a family history of undescended testis (his brother).

A 1.4 year-old boy was operated. Right herniotomy was performed and left testis was found in the right inguinal canal (Figure- 1) which was brought to the left scrotum and anchored through suprapubic subcutaneous tunnel. During the exploration of the right inguinal region, pulling of the right gonad in the hernia sac caused protrusion of another gonad (Figure-1). The macroscopic appearance of both gonads was testis associated with fimbria-like structures. Both gonads had vas deferenses and vascular supplies.

During operation, the right inguinal exploration revealed a normal testis within the right scrotum associated with an indirect inguinal hernia. The uterus, fallopian tubes and both testes were unexpectedly found within the hernia sac (Figure-1).

During dissection, the left testis was encountered in the right inguinal canal. Each testes was noted to have its corresponding spermatic cord, and had two vasa deferentia which were separated, the two testes were of a good size identical in appearance. Each had its own vascular pedicle. The patient underwent bilateral proximal salpingectomies, leaving the fimbria with each epididymis, hysterectomy and pedicles of myometrium left with the vasa deferentia. The cervix was split longitudinally in the midline to achieve successful bilateral orchidopexy after mobilizing the internal spermatic vessels (Figure-2).

After right inguinal herniotomy the left testis with an extra ordinary long spermatic cord was brought to the left scrotum and anchored through suprapubic subcutaneous tunnel. Biopsy specimens were taken from both gonads and the histopathology showed them to be testes and revealed normal hypoplastic uterine tissue.

Figure(2): The cervix was split longitudinally in the midline to achieve successful bilateral orchidopexy after mobilizing the internal spermatic vessels

Figure (1): Right herniotomy was performed and left testis was found in the right inguinal canal. Pulling of the right gonad in the hernia sac caused protrusion of another gonad. The uterus, fallopian tubes and both testes were unexpectedly found within the hernia sac.

Müllerian (paramesonephric) ducts and Wolffian (mesonephric) ducts are the anlagen of the female and male reproductive tracts, respectively. In the XY fetus, the testis differentiates by the end of the seventh gestational week. Sertoli cells begin to secrete AMH, which is responsible for the regression of the Müllerian ducts. The AMH binds to a specific Type II serine-threonine kinase transmembrane receptor (AMHR-II). Human *AMH* gene is localized on chromosome 19p13.3-p13.2, and *AMHR2* gene on 12q13. The type of persistent Mullerian duct syndrome caused by mutation in the *AMH* gene will

be referred to as Type I, which which forms due to mutation in the AMH receptor (*AMHR*) will be designated as Type II [14]. In 45%, a mutation in *AMH* gene was detected; in 39% mutation of the Type II receptor of AMH was detected; in 16% the cause is unknown [15]. There are two morphological forms of PMDS. Female form (10-20%) is characterized by the presence of bilateral cryptorchidism with no herniation of Mullerian duct structures and testes. Uterus and fallopian tubes are fixed in the pelvis and testes are embedded in the broad ligament. Male form (80-90%) is characterized by the presence of unilateral cryptorchidism with contralateral inguinal hernia

containing the Mullerian structures and the testes. Male form is subdivided into two types. In type-I, hernia sac contains uterus, both fallopian tubes and both testes (hernii uteri inguinalis with TTE). This patient belonged to type-I. In type-II, hernia sac contains uterus, ipsilaterally fallopian tube and ipsilateral testis (classic hernii uteri inguinalis) [16, 17]. One testis is usually in the scrotum, the uterus and fallopian tube being pulled into the canal by traction on the undescended testis. The contralateral testis and the fallopian tube may also appear in the hernia sac, as in our patient. The "female" type is associated with both enough to reach the scrotum, orchidectomy should be performed [18]. Cross-orchidopexy is required in transverse testicular ectopia [19]. As in our case, clinically, patients suffering from PMDS present during infancy, childhood or adulthood with cryptorchidism, inguinal hernia or infertility [20, 21, 22].

PMDS is usually discovered incidentally at the time of orchidopexy or inguinal hernia repair in children since the PMDS does not affect organogenesis of male external genitalia and the Mullerian remnants are not palpable on abdominal examination. Because incidental discovery during pediatric surgery, the initial procedure may need to include replacement of the gonads and Müllerian structures within the pelvis and repair of the inguinal hernia. After confirmation of the diagnosis of PMDS, definitive surgery should be performed to remove the corpus of the uterus and fallopian tubes to enable fixation of the testes in the scrotum. Hysterectomy is indicated only when Mullerian structures limit intrascrotal placement of the testes [23].

The patient or his family should be informed of the diagnosis, the surgical options, and the need for long-term follow-up. Finally, genetic counseling must be offered in order to prevent further cases according to the family wishes.

TTE should be suspected preoperatively in patients who have unilateral inguinal hernia associated with a contralateral non-palpable testis []. If TTE is found, this it represents an indication to search for PMDS. PMDS is usually coincidentally detected in surgical operations [24, 25] as it was in our patient.

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CASE (3)

Anterior urethral valves and diverticula are rare. Most anterior valves (40%) are located in the bulbous urethra, but they can also be located at the penoscrotal junction (30%) and penile urethra (30%) [1]. They are composed of folds located on the ventral aspect of the urethra that rise during voiding, resulting in urethral obstruction [2]. Anterior urethral diverticula communicate with the urethra and are found on the ventral aspect of the urethra between the bulbous and mid-penile urethra [1]. Although many authors distinguish

between anterior urethral valves and diverticula, others consider them the same entity. It has been proposed that valves cause proximal urethral dilatation with the formation of a saccular diverticulum [1]. Conversely, progressive enlargement of a diverticulum can result in a distal valve-like flap. Embryologic theories of anterior urethral diverticula formation include a developmental defect in the corpus spongiosum leading to formation of a diverticulum, cystic dilatation of urethral glands, and sequestration of an epithelial rest [2]. McLellan et al. [3] have demonstrated connections between an anterior urethral diverticula and cowperian ducts, proposing that anterior urethral diverticula and valves arise from the anterior lip of a ruptured cowperian duct syringocele. Patients with diverticuli typically manifest urinary incontinence, dysuria, perineal pain, or a genital or perineal mass. Surgery is the treatment of choice in all cases, aiming to secure complete removal of the lesion.

A 2 - year - old male child presented to the pediatric surgery unit at The Maternity and Child Teaching Hospital at Al-Qadisiya, Iraq with a large swelling on the ventral surface of the penis, inability to pass urine and dribbling of urine since 1 year of age. However he could pass urine when his family used to apply pressure on the swelling. Over the last year the size of swelling had gradually increased. There was an associated history of intermittent fever and dysuria. On general examination, he was well nourished and normotensive. Local examination of the perineum and the external genitalia revealed a large cystic swelling on the ventral aspect of the penis distal to the penoscrotal junction [figure 1-A].

On applying pressure on the swelling, urine was seen dribbling easily from the external meatus [figure 1-B]. The swelling was transilluminant. Both testicles and spermatic cords were normal. On abdominal examination, bladder was distended and palpable. An ultrasound examination was done. An anechoic well-defined swelling with low level internal echoes and a regular wall was seen at base of the penis. The nipple of the swelling was seen to be dipping into the spongiosum. Both the testes were seen separately and were normal. On voiding a sudden increase in the size of the swelling was noted. Its communication with the anterior urethra could be demonstrated. A voiding cystourethrogram (a VCU was attempted more than one time because the patient did not so cooperate) revealed the diverticulum and confirmed the ultrasound findings. The rest of the urethra and bladder was normal. Urine analysis showed evidence of urinary tract infection. Renal functions were within normal limits.

Unfortunately no facilities for cystoscopy. Following investigations and prior to surgery a 10F stent was inserted for drainage. The patient underwent an open diverticulectomy and urethroplasty with reinforcement of the corpus spongiosus [figure 3

and 4]. Repair of the urethral tube was done using 5-0 vicryle sutures. Post-operative period was uneventful. Stent was removed after 14 days and patient could pass urine voluntarily with good stream without any leak.

Figure (1): The diverticulum presented as a scrotal mass.

Figure (2): The diverticulum ; urine was seen dribbling from the external meatus.

Figure (3): Surgical detail: Full exposure of the diverticulum following its complete dissection

Figure (4): Visualization of the urethral defect after resection of the diverticulum.

Congenital urethral diverticula are classified as saccular or globular according to radiologic appearance; the saccular type is more common [4]. The valves and diverticula are located on the ventral aspect of the urethra [5]. The etiology of anterior urethral valve is not entirely clear. Dilatation of peno-urethral glands, incomplete urethral duplication defective fusion of a segment of the urethral plate and focally incomplete development of the corpus spongiosum with ballooning of the urethral mucosa due to inadequate support are all

probable etiologies [4]. Most children present with poor urinary stream, recurrent UTI and difficulty *in* voiding with appearance of a reducible swelling at the ventral aspect of distal penis while voiding. In this case, diagnosis was accomplished by VCUG and careful clinical examination [6]. Preoperative evaluation should include either a retrograde urethrogram or voiding cystourethrogram and cystourethroscopy for proper assessment. Surgical management depends upon the etiology of the diverticulum [7]. A palpable mass, at the ventral

surface of the mid penile urethra or the penoscrotal junction, which empties on pressure, should alert the clinician to the diagnosis. The aim of management is to achieve optimal valve ablation and free urinary flow. Cystoscopic valve ablation may be achieved using electro-resection or laser ablation [8, 9]. If facilities for endoscopic ablation are not available, open valve resection is equally good. Other options are vesicostomy in infants with severe vesico-ureteric reflux, urethroplasty in cases with thin urethra and diverticulectomy in those with associated urethral diverticulum [10]. The treatment of choice is surgical removal of the diverticulum and urethroplasty. In some cases an endoscopic approach has been applied to small diverticuli, provided the corpus spongiosum and supporting tissue are intact [11]. Open surgery in the form of a diverticulectomy remains the option of choice. If the urethral defect is very large, extragenital free grafts can be used, placed ventrally [12], to avoid the formation of fistulas and relapses derived from simple closure techniques.

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